

Laser Ionization and Spectroscopy of Actinides

Summarizing the project results of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network's Early Stage Researchers

In memory of Dr. Bruce A. Marsh - initiator and network coordinator of LISA

Editor: Dr. Katerina Chrysalidis

Laser Ionization and Spectroscopy of Actinides

Summarizing the project results of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative
Training Network's Early Stage Researchers

In memory of Dr. Bruce Alan Marsh - initiator and network coordinator of LISA

Editor: Dr. Katerina Chrysalidis

The Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network LISA (**L**aser **I**onization and **S**pectroscopy of **A**ctinides), funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program, aimed to train the next generation of atomic, nuclear and laser scientists by conducting research to increase our understanding of the atomic and nuclear properties of the chemical elements known as the actinides. Of long-standing interest to the fields of fundamental atomic and nuclear physics, this effort is an essential prerequisite for unravelling the structure of the superheavy elements at the end of Mendeleev's table. This knowledge is required for the effective production, identification and handling of these elements, and is thus a necessary foundation for our goals of understanding and exploiting the potential for practical applications of the actinides in the fields of medical physics, nuclear applications and environmental monitoring. Our consortium of world-leading experts in radioactive ion beam research and applications, laser spectroscopy, scientific laser technologies (industrial partners) and nuclear and atomic theorists recruited and trained 15 Early Stage Researchers. LISA formed a cohesive and symbiotic collaboration for training young scientists in the pursuit of the following research objectives: Development of laser-based actinide ion beam production and purification techniques; development of laser technologies; measurement of ionization potentials and electron affinities; extraction of atomic and nuclear properties from laser spectroscopy studies; enhancement of the prospects for direct use of the actinide isotopes themselves (theranostic applications), or the application of techniques for their detection (environmental monitoring).

LISA was structured into 7 work packages (WP), separated according to specific types of technical or research challenges, training, communication and management, but highly interlinked to ensure a close interaction between the ESR fellows. This structure was designed to expose all trainees to the breath of activity types across the network and also to foster working relationships that will endure long after the project ends.

The following contributions were prepared by the ESRs and summarize their projects. At the time of writing of this compilation of results, almost all the ESR have completed their participation in the network. Some have either finished their doctoral theses and have successfully defended them, are still on track to complete their thesis work or have found employment in closely related fields of industry or government organizations.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program (Grant No. 861198 project LISA MSCA ITN).

Preface - A historical overview of the laser-based research and development leading towards LISA

Europe has always had a strong tradition in nuclear research, for the most part carried out at independent, nationally run accelerator facilities hosted in different countries. It was almost 20 years ago, that an integrated infrastructure initiative called EURONS was proposed to maximize and coordinate future scientific and technological challenges identified within the European community. EURONS, the new European infrastructure for nuclear structure research was a framework composed of 45 laboratories in 21 countries. This initiative, as well as future efforts, built upon a successful and rich interplay between theory and experiment, including universities and large-scale infrastructures. EURONS comprised a coherent ensemble of transnational access facilities (TNAs), joint research activities (JRAs) and networking activities (NAs). The joint research activities were implemented to identify and coordinate the necessary technical developments to support the research infrastructures, geared towards specific scientific goals.

Within EURONS, a group of partners including KU Leuven, GSI, JYU, CERN-ISOLDE, U-Mainz, IN2P3 and U-Manchester formed a research activity called LASER, Laser techniques for Exotic Nuclei Research. The goals of the activity were multifaceted: to develop the necessary tools and to perform research and development to enable the resonance ionization laser ion source RILIS to produce pure ground state and isomeric beams of exotic nuclei and to develop in-source spectroscopy of said nuclei. The need for enhanced ion manipulation techniques were readily identified following the implementation of the first radiofrequency quadrupole cooler-buncher devices at ISOLDE and JYFL at the beginning of the millennium. Accumulation, cooling and bunching of radioactive ion beams would be necessary to improve the capabilities of ISOL and IGISOL facilities to facilitate measurements with unprecedented sensitivity for the most exotic species. One may note that in parallel, the trapping community focused their efforts on a separate joint research activity called TRAPSPEC, though later partners from both communities merged efforts. Although not implemented for experiments, the LASER community prepared the groundwork for polarization of nuclei which would feature more selectively in some facilities later. One notable activity within LASER was to develop a prototype Ti:Sapphire laser system along with higher harmonic generation capabilities at Mainz University and to apply this new system for resonance laser ionization. As we all know, this system rapidly found its way to several facilities not only within Europe but also worldwide, forming the backbone of many laser systems at ISOL laser ion sources and spectroscopy stations. It is a testament to the efforts of many

younger researchers at that time that our current crop of finishing Early Stage Researchers within LISA have been able to get hands-on training using these laser systems today.

These European initiatives are funded for four years, and so prior to the final year of EURONS it was very clear that the community wished to continue to support the facilities and connected research projects and network activities. ENSAR, the European Nuclear Structure and Applications Research emerged from EURONS and started a new four-year period in 2010. It was clear from the success of the efforts of LASER that the research activities would again feature within ENSAR, under a new activity named PREMAS, low-energy beam PREparation, MANipulation and Spectroscopy. PREMAS aimed to focus efforts on the continued development of the application of lasers and ion traps to directly benefit the access facilities. Novel radioactive ion beam production methods, sources of pure and intense beams, and advanced ion-beam manipulation techniques for spectroscopy as well as instrumentation were all featured as work packages. Much of this effort was in acknowledgement of the facility user demand for improvements in the selectivity of radioactive ion beam production, while also catering for the exciting possibilities these efforts were creating in connection to novel spectroscopy for ground-state nuclear structure properties.

It was within the framework of ENSAR that novel environments for spectroscopy were explored, with one notable development driven by KU Leuven, that of preparing a rigorous foundation for in-gas jet spectroscopy which will be playing a critical role in the (near) future experimental setups at the low-energy branches of S3 GANIL, MARA in JYFL and connected to RADRIS at GSI. Of course, the traditional ISOL facilities were not forgotten, and new developments were proposed to also investigate new laser ionization zones at hot cavities. Many years of developments were slowly coming to fruition with respect to the laser ion source and trap (LIST) device, to dramatically improve the selectivity of the RILIS workhorse and to pave the way for future novel spectroscopies including the perpendicular-illuminated LIST (PI-LIST), which has now shown great promise in dramatically reducing the effect of Doppler broadening in the hot cavity environment on spectral linewidths. The laser developments that would be required to realize the PI-LIST approach, specifically injection-locking techniques of solid-state lasers, were a part of the PREMAS research activity, continuing throughout RESIST in ENSAR2. Let us not forget the efforts of the trapping community to demonstrate to the wider nuclear spectroscopy community that Penning traps could be successfully connected to decay spectroscopy setups. Such efforts were largely realized at Jyväskylä, with up to 50% of the Penning trap experiments later being devoted to trap-assisted decay spectroscopy. The combination of different ion manipulation techniques, as well as the merging of laser spectroscopy and resonance laser ionization with decay and trap-based spectroscopy has driven some of the most exciting developments over the years. CRIS, in-gas cell spectroscopy and in-gas jet spectroscopy all played roles throughout the ENSAR period.

The laser community was an incredibly important source of research and development of direct benefit to the facilities within ENSAR, and this continued into ENSAR2 which was submitted to the EU in 2014, running from early 2015 to 2019. RESonance Ionization techniques for SeparatoRS, RESIST, was formed of 8 institutes: JYU, GANIL, INFN, CERN-ISOLDE, CNRS, GSI, KU Leuven and U-Mainz. By now, RILIS, IGLIS (Ion Guide LIS) and the LIST techniques were highly successful and very much in demand. RESIST therefore aimed to refine these methods and ensured they would be available not only at ISOL facilities but also for the first time at in-flight facilities. To enhance the production of the exotic nuclei of interest as one goes further from the valley of stability to the extremes of the nuclear chart in both neutron deficiency, neutron

richness and towards the heaviest elements, must be matched by continued efforts to suppress contamination that in many cases has hampered access to certain regions of the nuclear chart. With the next generation of large-scale facilities on the horizon, this was of critical concern to the activities of RESIST in ENSAR2. The ability to selectively produce and study exotic nuclei (as well as nuclei closer to stability) is key to supporting the exploration of open science questions in nuclear structure, nuclear astrophysics, fundamental physics as well as applied research in material sciences, life and bio-medical sciences. These questions are continually being evaluated and the most recent list can be found in the draft executive report of the NuPECC Long Range Plan 2024.

From EURONS to ENSAR2, the laser community featured in all integrated infrastructure initiatives and was recognized as a strong, coherent activity, not only providing the necessary developments of immediate support to the access facilities, but also high-impact scientific output. The community has always been proud of the younger generation of researchers which keep the field very much alive, and which drive new ideas that cross into different disciplines. By recognizing our strong scientific and technical foundations while being able to quickly identify new opportunities has enabled a steady scientific renewal. This was exemplified by the very real concern that it would be difficult to “reinvent the wheel” of EURONS, ENSAR and ENSAR2. The laser community therefore decided upon two approaches towards the end of the ENSAR2 period. We would continue to support and play a role as a potential research activity in the next framework call, and we would consider how to diversify and seek alternative sources of funding via a Marie Curie International Training Network (ITN) call.

In 2018, the nuclear research community called for new research activities to be included in ERINS, a new access framework for EU scientists involved in research with radioactive ions. Again, ERINS would be an ensemble of access facilities, joint research activities and network activities. Once more, it was hoped that ERINS would strengthen the coherence of the community around certain research topics with a focus of defining future directions for the field. In particular, ERINS aimed to strengthen links between basic radioactive ion beam research and societal applications at access facilities. In response to the community call, key partners from previous laser-based initiatives came together with a unifying goal of diversifying our research objectives, with an underlying theme of promoting specific developments to produce radioactive nuclei for societal benefits.

LIONESS, Lasers IOns and Nuclei for Environmental Science and Society, was accepted as one of the few joint research activities in ERINS. The objectives of LIONESS were to develop state-of-the-art laser-based techniques for applications in environmental-based science in actinide and lanthanide elements, and to explore new and efficient resonance ionization schemes that target future radioisotopes of interest to the medical community. The complexity and footprint of our high resolution and highly sensitive techniques would be brought to the tabletop, to make these methods more attractive to external users from applied fields. Laser systems which have been the backbone of our activities would hopefully be transformed to turn-key systems with support from industrial partners. Scientific research would target chemical properties, atomic and nuclear structure physics of those elements lacking in stable isotopes, with an emphasis towards environmental studies. This would address an obvious lack of basic atomic spectroscopy of elements scarcely produced (actinides) or with complex atomic structure (lanthanides and actinides). For the first time, cross disciplinary studies would target both atoms and molecules. ERINS would sadly not be funded. Fortunately, more recently, EUROLABS was funded which

has allowed the continuation of the access support to the European facilities. Changes were made to ensure that most of the funding went to support facility access, with minimal contributions given to research and network activities. The laser community has not suffered however, due to the careful planning that was invested into the parallel application for a new Marie Curie ITN. LISA, Laser Ionization and Spectroscopy of Actinides, has built upon the previous EU framework initiatives: LASER, PREMAS, RESIST and LIONESS, expanding to include many new partners, both academic and industrial. Scientific and technical development continues to play a role; however, the focus has turned towards the training of a new generation of fantastic young multidisciplinary scientists.

The proceedings which follow highlights the success story of LISA through contributions from the young researchers. In addition to celebrating the achievements of the next generation of scientists, we also acknowledge the efforts of our coordinator and dear friend, Bruce Marsh, who sadly passed away before the end of this network. His contributions to the field played an important role throughout the previous framework programs and he will be sorely missed.

Iain Moore

Contents

Preface	iii
1 Production of Ra-225 and Ac-225 ion beams from irradiated Th-based targets for medical purposes	1
<i>J.D. Johnson</i>	
2 Laser Resonance Ionization Spectroscopy with PI-LIST	7
<i>A. AH Jaradat</i>	
3 Target developments for extraction of actinides from thick ISOL targets	17
<i>M. Au</i>	
4 Production and study of actinides at IGISOL via decay spectroscopy and laser spectroscopy techniques within the LISA framework	25
<i>A. Raggio, I. Pohjalainen, I.D. Moore</i>	
5 Laser spectroscopic investigations on the actinide atomic and nuclear structures	33
<i>M. Kaja</i>	
6 Experimental and theoretical investigations of negative ions	39
<i>M. Nichols</i>	
7 Development of the IGLIS technique at KU Leuven and its application in the JetRIS and S³-LEB experiments.	45
<i>F. Ivandikov, A. Claessens, R. Ferrer, P. Van den Bergh, P. Van Duppen</i>	
8 In gas jet laser spectroscopy optimization for high resolution measurement of actinides	71
<i>A. Ajayakumar</i>	
9 Developments of laser techniques towards high-resolution laser spectroscopy of actinide homologs	77
<i>J. Wessolek</i>	
10 The quest for laser spectroscopy of the heaviest actinide elements	83
<i>J. Warbinek</i>	
11 Multi-element ultra-trace detection of radionuclides in environmental samples	93
<i>D. van Eerten</i>	

12 Relativistic multiconfigurational calculations of the atomic structure of the actinides	99
<i>J.S. Andrews</i>	
13 High Precision Calculations of Energies, Lifetimes and Hyperfine Structure of Ac⁺ for Laser Resonance Chromatography	105
<i>G. Geehan</i>	
14 C-WAVE laser development as a turn-key solid-state alternative to CW dye laser.	111
<i>M. Urquiza-González</i>	
Closing remarks	117

Chapter 1

Production of Ra-225 and Ac-225 ion beams from irradiated Th-based targets for medical purposes

J.D. Johnson^a, C. Bernerd^b, T. E. Cocolios^a, C. Duchemin^b, L. Lambert^b, R. E. Rossel^b and T. Stora^b

^a Instituut voor kern- en stralings-fysica (KU LEUVEN)

^b CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

From November 2020 to September 2023, beams of Ra-225 (14.9 d) and/or Ac-225 (9.92 d) have been produced and collected 8 times at CERN-MEDICIS, of which four for beam development and four for production. This contribution highlights the experiences that have been gained during these years of operation. The first two development studies used Ac mass markers to determine the ionization efficiency of Ac through surface ionization and a dual resonance laser ionization scheme. The temperature regimes necessary for Ac to reach vapor pressures sufficient to form pico-ampere current ion beams when heated from its nitrate salt on an inert rhenium foil and mimic matrix are likewise reported from these development tests. The four production runs are then discussed, through which pre-clinically relevant quantities of Ac-225 and Ra-225 were produced. Further development experiments were performed in order to determine the mass separation enhancement factor of Ac-225 over its co-produced isotopic cousin Ac-227 (21.8 y), but are discussed elsewhere. The results confirm the ability of mass separation to suppress the Ac-227 to activities below the exemption limit per Ac-225 patient dose.

1.1 Production of medically relevant isotopes

Nuclear physicists are most often interested in the isolation of a single nuclide so that its structure can be studied with a variety of spectroscopic techniques. The challenge in isolating these nuclides from an irradiated target has always been present, as typically other 'contaminant' nuclides are produced in nuclear reactions. This can range from single contaminants up to thousands. In any case their presence complicates the spectroscopic study of the nuclide of interest as it is more difficult to probe it without un-desired 'background'. Some of the first experiments on radioactive ion beam production by ionization and mass separation from irradiated targets were performed by O. Hanssen et al [1]. Their setup consisted of neutron irradiation of U and baking powder in vacuum. The decomposition of the baking powder provided gases that transported the fission

reaction products down a beamline into an ion-source, after which mass separation was performed. The researchers successfully isolated selected isotopes of Kr-88 and Kr-89 (half lives of 2.8 h and 3.2 m) from the large amount of other isotopes produced in U.

Although 70 years have passed since these first isotope separation by mass separation experiments, similar techniques are still used today. The ‘online’ approach to mass separation is continued at the ISOLDE facility in CERN, where 1.4 GeV protons impinge on a constantly heated target that is coupled to an ion source. Baking soda is no longer in common usage, but instead specially engineered target microstructure to facilitate rapid diffusion and effusion of produced isotopes is relied upon. The produced isotopes are ionized, mass separated and delivered to one of many possible experimental stations for spectroscopy studies. It has been realised that the versatility of this technique to produce isotopes of most elements can be translated to the production of medically relevant isotopes too. As medically relevant isotopes have half-lives of typically several hours or more, the need for ‘on-line’ extraction can be relaxed, and an ‘off-line’ version of ISOLDE can be envisaged. To realise this, the following steps have been implemented at the MEDICIS facility at CERN since 2017. a) A target coupled to an ion source (the target unit) is irradiated, either directly or parasitically with the 1.4 GeV proton beam. b) The target unit is remotely coupled to the front-end of a mass separator. c) The target unit is heated, gradually increasing the diffusion and effusion speed of produced isotopes until released in appreciable quantities. d) Atoms of the isotope of interest are ionized in the ion source, mass separated and implanted. The technique exploited at MEDICIS is not so different from that used 70 years ago by Hanssen et al, and nonetheless, research is still ongoing for optimal production. For example, the precise temperatures required for release are dependent on the element, its chemical form, and the target in which it is produced. The type of ion source, its material, its nominal operating temperature are also element dependent. The contaminants that one hopes to suppress are all isotope dependent. The precise set of challenges faced in the production of any given isotope are thus almost all unique. Furthermore, the demand for reliable separation of isotopes with high activities necessitates constant development on several frontiers. This often leads to the need to optimising the radioactive ion beam production efficiency. This comprises the diffusion, effusion and chemical form efficiency, that together make up the release efficiency, followed by the ionization efficiency shown in equation 1.

$$\epsilon_{RIB} = \epsilon_{diff}\epsilon_{eff}\epsilon_{chem}\epsilon_{ion} \quad (1.1)$$

When producing an ion beam of a medical isotope for the first time, it is important to quantify the contributions of these ‘sub-efficiencies’, to the total efficiency of the radioactive ion beam production, ϵ_{RIB} . Several medical isotopes have been produced at MEDICIS, each having undergone beam development work to determine the optimal target and ion source parameters. [7, 2, 3, 5, 4, 6]. Of these, one of the most promising for its clinical use is Ac-225. The rest of this contribution summarises the research of its optimal production at MEDICIS from 2020 to 2023 that has been carried out within the framework of the LISA network.

1.2 Laser ionization efficiency of Ac

The first Ac-225 development experiment was performed to measure the ionization efficiency of Ac at the MEDICIS separator. For details, see ref [7]. Through previous work of Ferrer et al [9] and

Raeder et al [8], two efficient ionization schemes were identified for Ac. For maximum ionization efficiency, both were employed simultaneously for this experiment and all subsequent work in Ac-production discussed in this contribution. The sample for the ionization efficiency experiment was a ^{225}Ac solution that was evaporated and dried on a Re foil, chosen for its high melting and boiling point and chemical inertness. This sample was then placed in a target unit as a ‘mass marker’ and a separation experiment was performed. The ion source was heated to 2000°C while the target container was heated to 1900°C , whereupon a beam of Ac-225 was observed. Analysis of the integrated ion beam current as well as dedicated γ , $\gamma\gamma$ and α spectroscopy measurements were used to calculate the quantity of Ac-225 collected. The ratio of this to the starting quantity of Ac-225 in the sample measured by decay spectroscopy was then used to infer the ionization efficiency. Corrections for beam transmission were applied and an assumption was made that Ac was only released in a mono-atomic gaseous form. An ionization efficiency of 15.1(6)% for the dual-resonance laser ionization scheme with a Re ion source at a temperature of 2000°C was calculated.

In order to begin to probe the effusion efficiency, ϵ_{eff} , the same experiment was performed with the exception that the ^{225}Ac solution was deposited and heated to dryness on a ThO_2 felt. This was done so that the Ac-225 would penetrate into the pore structure of the ThO_2 material, and when heated, the release would depend on the chemical and surface interactions with the Ac-225 and the ThO_2 matrix. When performing this experiment, a similar ionization efficiency was observed, but with the target temperature of 2240°C required. From this study we hypothesised that the thermal decomposition of the ThO_2 material led to an oxygen rich environment, facilitating the formation of the refractory Ac_2O_3 compound. HSC calculations reinforced this hypothesis, showing that a temperature of several hundred degrees higher was required to produce $\text{Ac}(\text{g})$ at a given concentration when the presence of excess ThO_2 was included. We concluded that on the condition of reaching the high temperatures discussed, the surface chemistry and ‘near-surface effusion’ component of ϵ_{RIB} was negligible.

1.3 Radioactive ion beam production efficiency of Ac-225

With negligible effusion cost incurred at high temperatures, and an ionization efficiency of 15.5(6)%, production runs of Ac-225 were performed in the year 2023, making use of 100g ThC_x targets. Two targets were used for four production runs, with the first one being irradiated three times for three independent collections, while the latter was irradiated a single time. The in-target activities calculated with CERN-FLUKA are shown in Table 1.1. In each case, the goal was to collect Ac-225 with high efficiency. In the irradiated targets, Ra-225 is also produced at typical activities of 15% that of the Ac-225.

Collection	Targ. Mass (g)	Previous irrads.	p.o.t (uAh)	Ac-225 (MBq)	Ra-225 (MBq)
May-23	98.9	0	42	1030	149
Jun-23	98.9	1	40.7	997	144
Aug-23	98.9	2	159	611	100
Sep-23	105.2	0	95	2400	348

Table 1.1: The in-target activities of Ac-225 and Ra-225 at the start of collection for the four production runs in 2023. p.o.t. indicates the total protons on target.

Ra has a lower vaporization enthalpy than Ac and so is expected to be released quicker from

an irradiated target. Furthermore, it has a first ionization potential of 5.27892 eV with an ionic to atomic ground state multiplicity factor of 2, compared to the ionization potential and multiplicity ratio of 5.380 eV and 1/2 in Ac respectively. It is therefore also expected to be surface-ionized more efficiently. Selectivity of Ac-225 over Ra-225 was thus expected to only be possible by employing the technique of ‘thermochromatography’ i.e., first setting the target container at a temperature at which the Ra-225 vapor pressure is sufficient such that it is depleted within the order of a day, before increasing the target temperature up to that necessary for the Ac-225 vapor pressure to increase up to a level such that it forms a Faraday-cup readable (> 1 pA) beam current. Selectivity is thus obtainable by first depleting the Ra-225 through release. In practice, co-collection of Ra-225 and Ac-225 is not problematic as Ra-225 is the beta-decay parent of Ac-225, and is thus a "useful" contaminant.

The four collections proceeded as discussed in detail in ref. [11]. Illustrative examples of the beam currents observed in the May and June runs are shown in Figure 1.1.

Fig. 1.1: Ion beam current evolution during the May and June collections (bottom panel) along with target and ion source temperature (top panel)

In all four collections, Ra was observed at high beam currents ($> \text{nA}$). It was positively identified through its characteristic isotopic ratio from irradiated Th targets (see figure in Ref. [10]). The target temperatures at which it was collected in the four runs were , 1660 °C, 1700 °C, 1700 °C and 1850 °C. with preliminary collection efficiencies on the order of 40%, 25%, 20 % and 40 % determined through gamma decay spectroscopy of the collected samples.

In the four collections, the resonance laser ionization scheme discussed earlier was set up in the MELISSA laboratory and was used as a useful tool for positive identification of Ac-225 in the collections of May and June. In the run of August the target was not able to be heated to a temperature necessary for Ac release. In the September run, an Ac-225 laser signal was observed but due to facility scheduling constraints, the collection was stopped before pursuing the Ac collection. The Ac-225 collection efficiencies are thus only reported for the May and June

collections, and are each on the order of less than 1 %.

From these results we can draw three main conclusions on Ac-225 production. A) Most of the Ac-225 that was collected originated from decay feeding of Ra-225, as the latter was collected with such high collection efficiencies. B) While it is possible to reach target temperatures necessary for Ac-225 beam production, its release time is so long, that it is hardly close to being depleted before facility constraints stop the collection. Thus, even at high temperatures, it was difficult to determine the full release efficiency as the collection was in each case terminated before depletion. An ‘extra’ efficiency term must thus be appended to those in Equation 1.1, reflecting facility pragmatism: ϵ_{prag} that dominates ϵ_{RIB} of Ac-225. C) The collection efficiency of Ra-225 decreased for each subsequent collection from a re-used target, while it returned to the high value of the order of 40 % once a fresh target was once again provided in the September collection. We conclude that ‘punishing’ the target at the high temperatures required for Ac-225 extraction are detrimental for the porous micro-structure of the target and reduce the release efficiency of Ra-225 and Ac-225 alike, leading to less Ac-225 production in the long-run where target re-use is foreseen.

1.4 Outlook

As an outlook we highlight that Ra-225 production allows the collection of more Ac-225 than from implantation of the Ac-225 ion beam itself. Experiments should therefore be performed to evaluate the extent of target degradation when only heating the target to temperatures necessary for Ra collection. Furthermore, by forgoing the collection of Ac-225, the lasers in MELISSA can instead be used for resonance laser ionization of Ra. Several schemes exist[12, 13], but the one that corresponds to the potential capabilities of the MELISSA laboratory is the 482.7, 459.2 nm scheme that can be achieved with the ongoing development of the Raman laser for providing the necessary frequency of the first step.

A possible optimum production strategy for Ac-225 production could be to process targets in two steps. a) Apply radiochemistry to an irradiated target to elute a Ra-225 fraction as an Ac-225 generator, and a ‘dirty’ Ac-225 fraction that contains Ac-227. This process can be performed with high efficiency [14]. b) Apply resonance laser ionization and mass separation to the Ac eluate deposited in the target unit as a mass marker. In this way, the Ac-225 generated in the target is valorized.

Bibliography

- [1] Kofoed-Hansen, Otto Møgens. "The birth of on-line isotope separation." (1976).
- [2] Duchemin, Charlotte, et al. "CERN-MEDICIS: A review since commissioning in 2017." *Frontiers in medicine* 8 (2021): 693682.
- [3] Mamis, Edgars, et al. "Target Development towards First Production of High-Molar-Activity 44gSc and 47Sc by Mass Separation at CERN-MEDICIS." *Pharmaceuticals* 17.3 (2024): 390.

- [4] Bernerd, C., et al. "Production of innovative radionuclides for medical applications at the CERN-MEDICIS facility." *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 542 (2023): 137-143.
- [5] Heinke, Reinhard, et al. "Efficient production of high specific activity thulium-167 at Paul Scherrer Institute and CERN-MEDICIS." *Frontiers in medicine* 8 (2021): 712374.
- [6] Van de Voorde, Michiel, et al. "Production of Sm-153 with very high specific activity for targeted radionuclide therapy." *Frontiers in Medicine* 8 (2021): 675221.
- [7] Johnson, Jake D., et al. "Resonant laser ionization and mass separation of ^{225}Ac ." *Scientific Reports* 13.1 (2023): 1347.
- [8] Raeder, S. et al. In-source laser spectroscopy developments at Trilis—Towards spectroscopy on actinium and scandium. *Hyperfine Interact.* 216, 33–39 (2013).
- [9] Ferrer, R. et al. Towards high-resolution laser ionization spectroscopy of the heaviest elements in supersonic gas jet expansion. *Nat. Commun.* 8, 1–9 (2017).
- [10] Johnson, Jake D., et al. " ^{227}Ac content of resonance-laser-ionized and mass-separated ^{225}Ac samples from proton spallation of thick Th-based targets at CERN-MEDICIS" In preparation
- [11] Johnson, Jake D., et al. "Production of ^{225}Ac from high-energy proton irradiated Th-based targets using mass-separation techniques." In preparation.
- [12] Goodacre, T. Day, et al. "Radium ionization scheme development: The first observed autoionizing states and optical pumping effects in the hot cavity environment." *Spectrochimica Acta Part B: Atomic Spectroscopy* 150 (2018): 99-104.
- [13] Mertes, Florian, et al. "Ion implantation of ^{226}Ra for a primary ^{222}Rn emanation standard." *Applied Radiation and Isotopes* 181 (2022): 110093.
- [14] Robertson, Andrew KH, et al. " ^{232}Th -spallation-produced ^{225}Ac with reduced ^{227}Ac content." *Inorganic Chemistry* 59.17 (2020): 12156-12165.

Chapter 2

Laser Resonance Ionization Spectroscopy with PI-LIST

Asar AH JARADAT^{a,b}

^a CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

^b University of Manchester, Manchester, The United Kingdom

Laser resonance ionization spectroscopy directly coupled to an isotope production target offers exceptional sensitivity for nuclear structure studies, particularly on isotopes with low production and extraction yields with the isotope separation on-line (ISOL) technique. However, its spectral resolution is typically constrained by Doppler broadening at ion source temperatures (≈ 2000 °C), limiting resolution to 1-10 GHz. A novel laser ion source design, recently implemented at ISOLDE, enables in-source spectroscopy with experimental linewidths as narrow as 100 – 200 MHz, significantly enhancing resolution. It is based on the Laser Ion Source and Trap (LIST) design, spatially separating the ion beam generation and laser-atom interaction regions, minimizing non-laser-related ionization mechanisms. The Perpendicularly Illuminated LIST (PI-LIST) upgrade reduces Doppler broadening by employing a crossed laser/atom beam geometry.

In the framework of LISA, this work entails the first-time on-line application of PI-LIST at ISOLDE for studying neutron-rich actinium isotopes. And a discussion regarding the technique's general applicability to ISOL facilities, efficiency challenges, technical implementation issues, and further optimization avenues.

2.1 Introduction

On-line in-source laser resonance ionization has demonstrated exceptional sensitivity in probing nuclear structures in isotopes with low production and extraction yields [28, 9]. However, its spectral resolution is limited by Doppler broadening within the high-temperature environment necessary for atom volatilization. Operating at temperatures around 2000 °C, this imposes a resolution constraint of 1-10 GHz, which is insufficient for precise measurements of nuclear magnetic and quadrupole moments that often require resolution finer than the GHz scale. Enhanced resolution capabilities are also crucial for discriminating between different nuclear isomeric states within a single isotope, surpassing conventional mass selection techniques employing dipole magnets.

A novel laser ion source design aims to achieve in-source spectroscopy with experimental linewidths of 100 – 200 MHz, significantly improving resolution. Based on the Laser Ion Source and Trap (LIST) concept [10, 11], laser ionization occurs downstream from the hot cavity within a

radiofrequency quadrupole (RFQ) structure to minimize non-laser-related ionization. The Perpendicularly Illuminated LIST (PI-LIST) [12] employs a crossed laser/atom beam geometry to reduce Doppler broadening by solely targeting transversal velocity components of the atom beam effusing from the hot cavity.

Recent applications of this technique at JGU Mainz for off-line nuclear structure investigations have been highly successful, particularly for long-lived radioactive isotopes such as promethium [25], technetium [19], and californium [27], using a transversal laser introduced through a vacuum vessel window at the separator frontend. However, this approach is not suitable for on-line facilities as ISOLDE, where the highly radioactive frontend area in direct proximity to the isotope production target is inaccessible during operation, and optically transparent materials potentially suffer from irradiation. The adaptation of the PI-LIST to these constraints involves transporting the spectroscopy laser beam off-center within the beam line, and performing perpendicular deflection in the LIST corpus itself directly downstream the hot cavity exit. Equivalence of this method to the one mentioned above, to enable resolution capabilities below 100 MHz and applicability in hyperfine structure studies was demonstrated off-line at Mainz University [16]. An illustration of the on-line adapted PI-LIST ion source is given in Fig. 2.1.

Fig. 2.1: On-line adapted version of the Perpendicularly Illuminated Laser Ion Source and Trap PI-LIST. The narrow-bandwidth spectroscopy laser is guided off-center through the beam line and adapted ion optics, and deflected perpendicularly just at the entrance of the RFQ structure, where the density of the effusing atom beam from the hot cavity is highest. As this laser only addresses velocity classes in its propagation direction, the Doppler broadening is greatly reduced in comparison to probing the longitudinal direction of the hot vapor cloud. Figure taken from [15].

A vital part of the high resolution spectroscopy setup is a suitable narrow-bandwidth laser. As in experimental setups working in the same resolution regime of laser spectroscopy, pulsed laser light with a linewidth in the low 10s MHz can be produced by utilizing a stable continuous wave

source that injection-seeds a stabilized ring cavity. A respective setup also commonly used with the PI-LIST is described in [24].

2.2 Milestones

The following sections compiles several milestones and key aspects that were achieved during the project duration.

2.2.1 First On-line Implementation of PI-LIST at ISOLDE for Study of Octupole Deformation in Actinium Isotopes

The first on-line implementation of PI-LIST at ISOLDE took place in May 2022, preceded by a long campaign of preparation for technical prerequisites, further described in [15]. Being at the heart of the LISA activities, the experiment aimed to pin down the border of possible octupole deformation in neutron-rich actinium isotopes by high-resolution laser spectroscopy [14]. It followed up on earlier in-source work at TRIUMF in conjunction with state-of-the-art EDF calculations [26]. Figure 2.2 shows a comparison of available experimental data and EDF calculations on changes in mean square charge radii of Ac isotopes before the PI-LIST experiment. Inclusion of octupole asymmetry is required to reproduce the trend. Mapping of the predicted kink around $^{230-232}\text{Ac}$ would provide additional very strong evidence for adequateness of this description. High fidelity data on nuclear moments can be used to complement the results.

Besides the need for improved spectral resolution to unambiguously determine changes in charge radii and nuclear moments, the enhanced sensitivity of the PI-LIST due to the suppression of prevalent francium and radium contamination is vital.

Fig. 2.2: Comparison of available experimental data and EDF calculations on changes in mean square charge radii of Ac isotopes before the PI-LIST experiment. A distinct kink around $^{230-232}\text{Ac}$ is predicted to be a telltale sign. Figure adapted from [26].

High resolution spectroscopic results were obtained with utilizing a suitable narrow-bandwidth laser. An injection-seeded, stabilized ring cavity was used to provide Fourier-limited pulsed laser light [24] of ≈ 20 MHz bandwidth in fundamental output. The cavity was seeded by a commercial Sirah Matisse Ti:sapphire cw laser provided by the CRIS collaboration in a setup as described in [6]. Actinium isotopes in the range of $^{224-231}\text{Ac}$ could be investigated - the results are subject to an upcoming publication. Figure 2.3 exemplarily shows the achieved resolution of down to

200 MHz, in comparison to the calculated Doppler broadening as it would occur at a temperature of 2000 °C in the hot cavity.

Fig. 2.3: Achieved experimental resolution of 200 MHz at a ^{227}Ac resonance with the PI-LIST at ISOLDE during its first on-line application. Figure taken from [15].

In this experiment, the goal of greatly reducing the Doppler broadening for narrower experimental linewidth was achieved, as well as collecting data to elucidate the phenomenon of octupole deformation in this area of the Nuclear Chart. Limited efficiency of the system though required the use of broader lasers for the weakly produced $^{230,231}\text{Ac}$ isotopes. Avenues to systematically improve this figure of merit are presented at the end of this work.

2.2.2 Production of Clean RIBs and Laser Spectroscopy of Pu and Np Isotopes

The isotope portfolio of radioactive ion beam (RIB) facilities using thick targets (such as ISOLDE) is considered to contain only nuclei with less protons than the target material, if solely the typical nuclear reactions with the primary beam such as spallation, fragmentation and spallation are regarded. Different pathways though lead to the production of species with higher atomic number [2], namely plutonium and neptunium, for the heaviest available target bulk material uranium.

In order to investigate yet unknown nuclear properties with laser spectroscopy, the LIST was employed to suppress the overwhelming uranium admixture from evaporating target material in this regime [3]. The PI-LIST operation mode was not available in this experiment. Isotope yields for $^{236-240}\text{Pu}$ and $^{235-239}\text{Np}$ were extracted and the low-resolution data analysed. On the basis of the results, it proved necessary to employ PI-LIST to achieve sufficient resolution for unambiguous assignment of nuclear structure observables, and to reduce the leaking of the (partially parasitically laser-ionized) dominant ^{238}U into neighbouring masses by utilizing a separator with higher mass resolution. Thus, an addendum [4] to the experiment letter of intent was formulated and partially approved, the execution is pending.

2.2.3 PI-LIST Feasibility Study at TRIUMF

TRIUMF (Tri University Meson Facility) in Vancouver, Canada, is in the process of designing and commissioning a new high-profile RIB facility, ARIEL, the Advanced Rare Isotope Laboratory. ARIEL will provide two additional rare isotope beams with unique properties to the experimental facilities in the ISAC experimental areas¹. Interest in a PI-LIST-type ion source for the new facility was expressed, also based on the experience with the TRIUMF version of the standard LIST, the Ion Guide Laser Ion Source IG-LIS [23]. Thus, a feasibility study to assess the integration of the PI-LIST unit into the planned beamline of the new construction was conducted during a secondment. It was concluded that it is indeed possible to accommodate the requirements of the PI-LIST ion source into the commissioning of the ARIEL facility. Equivalent as to ISOLDE, the only obstacle of an off-center laser beam path before perpendicular reflection is the extraction electrode. Its current design also allows for additional lateral orifices to provide direct line-of-sight between mirrors in a LIST corpus and the laser launch point.

A setup of the PI-LIST with lateral window access was also built at TRIUMF, in an off-line laser development facility of the TRILIS group. A shorter, 45mm long version of the ISOLDE PI-LIST was shipped to TRIUMF, assembled and fit with Kimball Physics systems into an existing atomic beam unit. Laser beams were provided from an adjacent laser laboratory. The infrastructure would allow systematic characterization of the influence of distance between hot cavity and LIST corpus (see also section 2.2.4) as the oven is mounted on a linear actuator. Additionally, the TRIUMF radiofrequency supply system to the IG-LIS is based on square wave pulses instead of a sinusoidal supply, and the setup can be used to characterize this system with the ISOLDE-type LIST. Unfortunately, this setup had to be abandoned before completion as the data acquisition system was not functional within the time constraints of the secondment. The TRILIS group is keeping it to conclude the measurements as soon as workforce can be dedicated.

2.2.4 Ion Source Geometry and Efficiency Optimization Study at Mainz

As the experimental application of the PI-LIST proved its unrivaled ability to conduct high-resolution laser spectroscopy scans directly at the ion source, it also revealed the significant loss of efficiency associated. A major loss channel between hot cavity and ionization in the LIST volume is the inferior geometrical laser-atom spatial and temporal overlap. A vast fraction of the effusing atoms escapes without the chance of interacting with laser photons.

The change in the rate of ion signals within a tubular volume, which is determined by the diameter of the collinear lasers along the central axis of the LIST, was examined experimentally in relation to its distance from the exit of the heated cavity in [13], see the excerpted Fig. 2.4. This was possible in the off-line version of the LIST at Mainz University by longitudinally displacing the perpendicular laser along the lateral entrance window. A rapid surge occurs just after the repelling electrode, up to the point corresponding to the location of the highest electric potential along the central axis. From here on, all created ions are pushed towards extraction. Subsequently, an inversely quadratic trend is detected, as expected from the atom density in a cone-like effusion. In this older off-line version of the PI-LIST, the repellers measure 1 mm in thickness and are positioned with a 1 mm gap between them, and the overall length of the corpus is 45 mm.

An approach to increase the efficiency is to optimize the shape of the effusing cone of atoms coming out of the atomizer tube to have more overlap with the laser beams. In the present

¹<https://www.triumf.ca/ariel-advanced-rare-isotope-laboratory>

Fig. 2.4: Dependence of laser ion signal from the distance of the point where the lateral laser is introduced. Upper panel shows respective electric potential along the central axis. Figure taken from [13].

low pressure regime (mean free path length \gg tube dimensions, i.e. negligible particle-particle interactions), it is predominantly governed by the ratio of diameter and length of the tube and can be described analytically [17, 18, 21, 8]. Thin, capillary-type tubes will produce a more directed beam.

During a secondment at the LARISSA group of Prof. Klaus Wendt at the Institute of Physics at Mainz University, the infrastructure described above was utilized to evaluate the influence of different hot cavity geometries in real experimental conditions. Three different variants of a 34 mm long cavity (standard source with 3 mm inner diameter, reduced inner diameter of 1.5 mm, and insertion of seven 0.5 mm inner diameter capillaries into a standard source) were installed consecutively, and the measurements performed analogue to [13] on the sample element manganese. Relative data comparison indeed confirms an advantage of the capillary-type setup. The results are subject to an upcoming publication, and are backed up with Monte Carlo simulations of the trajectories of emitted atoms, in a similar way as in, e.g., [20]. Also influences of potential geometrical misalignment can be investigated systematically with this approach, and after validation of the model, more unconventional cavity geometries can be assessed before being constructed. Complementary methods to investigate the atom density are, e.g., planar laser-induced fluorescence (PLIF) used for supersonic gas jet characterization [29], or deposition of the atom cone onto foils in different distances and investigation of the spatial distribution by methods such as null ellipsometry [5].

In addition to the efficiency increase, a more directed atom stream would also potentially profit spectral resolution. The distribution of lateral velocity classes is compressed. A planned campaign to systematically investigate this effect in the same setup had to be abandoned due to the strict time restrictions of the secondment.

2.3 Ongoing Upgrades And Future Plans

While the first on-line experiment with the PI-LIST was a very successful milestone of the technique, limitations were also clearly identified. The most crucial one is the efficiency, while advances in contamination suppression can also be achieved. Figure 2.5 gives an overview of the multitude of avenues that are currently explored to improve the young technique. Some of them are tackled already in the sections outlined above.

Fig. 2.5: Overview of a multitude of improvement avenues of the PI-LIST.

The various areas identified for potential improvement are briefly outlined as follows:

- **Atomizer geometry:** A better directed atom beam would lead to increased geometrical overlap with the laser beams, as described in section 2.2.4.
- **DC offset:** One restriction of extracting laser-ionized particles is the shape of the electric potential in the LIST corpus. The closer the potential ridge can be moved towards the hot cavity exit, the more the most atom-dense volume becomes accessible. The potential can be influenced by changes in the electrode geometry, or additional employed voltages. The feasibility of superimposing a DC voltage onto the RF quadrupole rods was shown within a CERN summer student project [1]. The ion guide mode to extract directly from the hot cavity to resemble standard RILIS operation will also profit from enhanced extraction.
- **RF phase / laser pulse synchronization:** Extraction efficiency of produced ions can potentially be dependent on the exact phase of the RF cycle when they are created. This can be especially significant for the small volume of creation in PI-LIST mode. Following a study of this effect with TRIUMF's IG-LIS [22], a corresponding investigation is planned at CERN's Offline2 separator facility.

- **Contamination optimization:** Non-laser ionized contamination was found to react systematically different to the confining RF field than laser-ionized species of choice. Recreating this effect in a simulation infrastructure would help to pin down the spatial origin of the contamination, potentially surface-ionization on sub-optimally cooled repeller electrodes. The identified areas are than subject to design reviews.
- **Internal mirrors:** Efficiency in PI-LIST mode can be improved by covering a larger volume with the perpendicular laser. This can be achieved by multi-pass reflections or introduction via different lateral beam paths. Increase of the mirror reflectivity (currently around 60 %, mechanically polished stainless steel) to assist this approach was shown to be achievable by, e.g., additional aluminum coating. Further investigations are carried out in collaboration with the CERN coating service.
- **Hot cavity voltage polarity:** Suppression of ions formed already in the hot cavity can be assisted by inverting the voltage gradient of its ohmic heating current from standard operation. In order to do this in operation, e.g. when switching from ion guide to LIST mode, a fast high current H-bridge setup can be employed [16]. A respective system was constructed in collaboration with Mainz University and awaits testing in experimental conditions.

While these investigations are ongoing, the PI-LIST has attracted wide interest across the user community, also beyond application in the LISA field. For example, a recent campaign studies its applicability in the lanthanide region of the Nuclear Chart [7].

2.4 Acknowledgment

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program (Grant No. 861198 project LISA MSCA ITN).

Bibliography

- [1] Latefa S A A Kh Alzabi. Upgrade to the RF supply system for ISOLDE’s laser ion source LIST. Technical report, 2023. <http://cds.cern.ch/record/2871583>.
- [2] M. Au et al. Production of neptunium and plutonium nuclides from uranium carbide using 1.4-GeV protons. *Physical Review C*, 107(6), 2023.
- [3] Mia Au et al. In-source laser resonance ionization spectroscopy of neptunium and plutonium. Technical report, CERN, Geneva, 2022. <http://cds.cern.ch/record/2809416>.
- [4] Mia Au and Jothers. Addendum - In-source laser resonance ionization spectroscopy of neptunium and plutonium. Technical report, CERN, Geneva, 2023. <http://cds.cern.ch/record/2872429>.
- [5] R. M. A. Azzam and N. M. Bashara. *Ellipsometry and polarized light*. North-Holland Pub. Co. and sole distributors for the U.S.A. and Canada Elsevier North-Holland, Amsterdam and New York and New York, 1977.

- [6] K. Chrysalidis et al. First demonstration of Doppler-free 2-photon in-source laser spectroscopy at the ISOLDE-RILIS. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 463:476–481, 2020.
- [7] Katerina Chrysalidis et al. Yield measurements for lanthanide elements with Ta-foil target and a LIST ion source. Technical report, CERN, Geneva, 2022. <http://cds.cern.ch/record/2834598>.
- [8] P. Clausing. Ueber die Strahlformung bei der Molekularstroemung. *Zeitschrift fr Physik*, 66(7-8):471–476, 1930.
- [9] Valentin Fedosseev et al. Ion beam production and study of radioactive isotopes with the laser ion source at ISOLDE. *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics*, 44(8):084006, 2017.
- [10] D. A. Fink et al. First application of the Laser Ion Source and Trap (LIST) for on-line experiments at ISOLDE. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 317:417–421, 2013.
- [11] D. A. Fink et al. On-line implementation and first operation of the Laser Ion Source and Trap at ISOLDE/CERN. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 344:83–95, 2015.
- [12] R. Heinke et al. High-resolution in-source laser spectroscopy in perpendicular geometry. *Hyperfine Interactions*, 238(1), 2017.
- [13] R. Heinke et al. Atom beam emersion from hot cavity laser ion sources. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 463:449–454, 2020.
- [14] Reinhard Heinke. Investigation of octupole deformation in neutron-rich actinium using high-resolution in-source laser spectroscopy. Technical report, CERN, Geneva, 2020. <http://cds.cern.ch/record/2717945>.
- [15] Reinhard Heinke et al. First on-line application of the high-resolution spectroscopy laser ion source PI-LIST at ISOLDE. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 541:8–12, 2023.
- [16] Reinhard Matthias Heinke. *In-source high-resolution spectroscopy of holmium radioisotopes - On-line tailored perpendicular laser interaction at ISOLDE's Laser Ion Source and Trap LIST*. PhD thesis, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz, 2019.
- [17] Martin Knudsen. Die Gesetze der Molekularströmung und der inneren Reibungsströmung der Gase durch Röhren. *Annalen der Physik*, 333(1):75–130, 1909.
- [18] Martin Knudsen. Die Molekularströmung der Gase durch Öffnungen und die Effusion. *Annalen der Physik*, 333(5):999–1016, 1909.
- [19] T. Kron et al. Hyperfine structure study of Tc97,98,99 in a new laser ion source for high-resolution laser spectroscopy. *Physical Review C*, 102(3), 2020.

- [20] Yuan Liu and Michael Smith. Computational Studies of Solid Stoppers for Generating Intense Exotic Radioactive Ion Beams at FRIB.
- [21] Herbert Mayer. Ueber eine experimentelle Methode zur Messung von Molekularstrahlung. *Zeitschrift fr Physik*, 52(3-4):235–248, 1929.
- [22] Maryam Mostamand. *Laser developments and study of Rydberg and autoionizing Rydberg states in Tm, La and At using resonant ionization laser spectroscopy*. Ph.D. thesis, The University of Manitoba, 2020.
- [23] Sebastian Raeder et al. An ion guide laser ion source for isobar-suppressed rare isotope beams. *The Review of scientific instruments*, 85(3):033309, 2014.
- [24] V. Sonnenschein et al. Characterization of a pulsed injection-locked Ti:sapphire laser and its application to high resolution resonance ionization spectroscopy of copper. *Laser Physics*, 27(8):085701, 2017.
- [25] Dominik Studer et al. High-resolution laser resonance ionization spectroscopy of 143-147 Pm. *The European physical journal. A, Hadrons and nuclei*, 56(2):69, 2020.
- [26] E. Verstraelen et al. Search for octupole-deformed actinium isotopes using resonance ionization spectroscopy. *Physical Review C*, 100(4), 2019.
- [27] Felix Weber et al. Nuclear moments and isotope shifts of the actinide isotopes Cf249–253 probed by laser spectroscopy. *Physical Review C*, 107(3), 2023.
- [28] X. F. Yang et al. Laser spectroscopy for the study of exotic nuclei. *Progress in Particle and Nuclear Physics*, 129:104005, 2023.
- [29] A. Zadvornaya et al. Characterization of Supersonic Gas Jets for High-Resolution Laser Ionization Spectroscopy of Heavy Elements. *Physical Review X*, 8(4), 2018.

Chapter 3

Target developments for extraction of actinides from thick ISOL targets

M. Au^{a,b}

^a CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

^b Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz, Mainz, Germany

The application of the ISOL method is investigated for the production of nuclides in the elusive actinide region of the nuclear chart. Actinide nuclides were produced at CERN-ISOLDE using 1.4-GeV protons incident on bulk targets and identified using a variety of techniques including resonance laser ionization, decay spectroscopy, and time-of-flight mass spectrometry. Resonance laser ionization is investigated for the production of atomic actinide ion beams and molecular formation techniques are investigated for extraction of actinide nuclides and production of actinide molecules.

3.1 Introduction

The actinides are an especially difficult set of elements to handle. All isotopes of the actinides are radioactive and only occur in limited amounts in nature. With the exception of several thorium and uranium isotopes, the actinides available on Earth are produced naturally in the decay of other actinides, or artificially through nuclear reactions. The factor that currently limits both the study and use of the actinides is their availability in a form accessible for potential experiments and applications.

The Isotope Separation On-Line (ISOL) method (Fig. 3.1) is used at a selection of dedicated facilities worldwide to produce, extract, ionize and deliver a wide variety of radioactive ion beams by nuclear reactions of accelerated particles with thick targets. CERN-ISOLDE [15] is one such ISOL facility, which offers a substantial catalogue of measured and documented yields for more than 1000 radioactive isotopes [16, 13]. The aim of this project was to develop techniques to extend this catalogue to include the actinide elements.

The initial aims of the project were to:

1. Investigate novel target concepts, optimized for the extraction of actinides from thick ISOL targets.
2. Develop laser-based actinide ion beam production and purification techniques (ion source technology, laser technology, atomic spectroscopy, laser excitation schemes).

3. Develop techniques related to the production of actinide ion beams by laser-induced molecular break-up and/or resonance photo-ionization.

The deliverables and milestones include the successful creation and detection of actinide molecules, and on-line tests of actinide production, extraction, dissociation and ion beam production.

Fig. 3.1: The Isotope Separation On-Line (ISOL) method of isotope production

3.2 Summary of Results

3.2.1 Atomic actinide ion beams

The production of atomic ion beams was investigated for the elements with atomic numbers 89-94. Actinium was resonantly laser-ionized, facilitating experimental studies of the isotopes $^{224-231}\text{Ac}$. ^{228}Ac was produced and delivered for the study of β -delayed fission in the actinide isotopes [2]. The newly-implemented PI-LIST technique described in chapter 2 was used to perform high-resolution in-source laser spectroscopy of Ac nuclei [22, 24], showing trends in the nuclear charge radius in the region of octupole-deformed nuclei. The experiment achieved a resolution of 400 MHz with a narrow-band laser system combining a Matisse continuous-wave Ti:Sa laser with a seeded ring Ti:Sa cavity for the isotopes $^{224-229}\text{Ac}$, and a resolution of 800 MHz using a dual-etalon Ti:Sa laser for the isotopes $^{230,231}\text{Ac}$, spanning a range of 8 isotopes of actinium. Data is under analysis [23, 24].

Of all the light actinides, thorium is the most refractory. In metallic form, it has a melting point of 1750°C and a boiling point of 4787°C . It also has a large adsorption enthalpy on tantalum [12, 19], making it very likely to stick to the surfaces of the target container. Because of its refractory properties, direct production and extraction of laser-ionized thorium atomic ion beams was not attempted. Instead, the delivery of specific radioactive thorium isotopes was achieved using decay parents. The isotope ^{229}Th , which has gained significant interest for applications of its uniquely low-lying isomer, was investigated at ISOLDE by delivering laser-ionized ^{229}Ac in addition to surface-ionized ^{229}Ra and ^{229}Fr , which all β -decay into ^{229}Th and enable experiments to study the radioactive thorium isotope of interest without direct extraction of thorium from the ISOL target [27].

Protactinium, the third element in the actinide series, is less refractory than thorium and has high predicted cross-sections for in-target production, particularly for isotopes close to the target nucleus. Protactinium has several isotopes with half-lives that are long in the context of the ISOL technique (^{231}Pa with 32,760 years, ^{233}Pa with 26.967 days and ^{230}Pa with 17.4 days). Despite this, earlier protactinium experiments conclude that it “may well be the most difficult of all to extract from natural sources” [17]. The extraction of atomic ion beams of Pa from thick ISOL targets was predicted to be very difficult despite the promising production rates, but was attempted within this work using a UC_x target with a rhenium surface ion source. From published resonance laser ionization schemes and protactinium atomic energy levels [28], several two-step laser schemes were attempted. No resonance behaviour was observed for the longest-lived isotopes ($^{231,233,230}\text{Pa}$). It was concluded that protactinium is too refractory, adsorbs too strongly onto the materials used for the target material and container, or forms refractory molecules with carbon or oxygen in the target. Protactinium may require techniques beyond simple heating for extraction.

As the ISOL target material available with the highest atomic number, uranium is present in bulk quantities and can also appear as a surface-ionized contaminant in the actinide mass region when using uranium targets. A resonance laser ionization scheme [30] requiring a single Ti:Sa laser with second harmonic generation was implemented for uranium, enabling the ionization of uranium atoms and identification of contamination. Radiogenic uranium isotopes are likely produced in reactions between ^{238}U targets and high-energy protons, but since the radioactive U is chemically identical to the target material, extraction is very challenging. Radiogenic uranium was not observed as a laser-ionized atomic ion beam.

Transuranium species—with more protons than the target nucleus—had barely been investigated at facilities with proton driver beams which typically use ^{238}U as the target nucleus with the most nucleons. Neptunium is additionally very refractory, limiting extractable quantities from the target. Despite the challenges posed by its chemical properties, Np is an interesting case motivated by a lack of experimental measurements of atomic or nuclear structure beyond the long-lived isotope ^{237}Np [14] and more recently $^{237,239}\text{Np}$ [25]. One proton number higher than neptunium, plutonium similarly requires nuclear reactions beyond the typical reactions of fission, fragmentation and spallation considered at ISOL facilities with proton driver beams. Within this project, the elements neptunium and plutonium were identified for the first time at ISOLDE. Extracted and mass-separated ion beam rates for $^{235-241}\text{Np}$ and $^{234-241}\text{Pu}$ were measured and compared with predictions from simulations, and results have been published [10]. Using these results, further studies were proposed [8] to perform in-source spectroscopy using the Laser Ion Source and Trap (LIST) [22, 24]. The experimental campaign was approved and performed. Data analysis is in progress.

3.2.2 Molecular actinide ion beams

The formation of volatile molecules has been used as a method to deliver beams of otherwise non-volatile elements that are limited by the release process of the ISOL technique [12, 26, 18]. Molecular sideband extraction is also used as a technique to improve beam purity. Importantly, molecular beams themselves are of significant interest for fundamental physics research.

Radioactive molecules provide opportunities to probe physics beyond the Standard Model and investigate still-unsolved questions of modern physics, notably the origins of baryon asymmetry. Observables with sensitivity to charge-parity (CP)-violating effects such as electric dipole moments

(EDMs) are specifically enhanced in radioactive molecules and require studies of multiple probe systems to disentangle possible sources of CP-violation using complementary searches. Each molecular species has distinct sensitivity to the different nuclear, hadronic, and leptonic CP-violating observables, depending on its electronic structure. A conclusive study of the different sources of CP violation thus requires the development of multiple experiments using molecules that offer complementary sensitivity to CP-violation sources [21]. Radioactive molecules which contain heavy, deformed nuclei possess especially enhanced nuclear CP-violating properties and higher molecular sensitivity to the properties of interest, making heavy radioactive molecules a pathway to pursue extreme factors of improvement in inherent sensitivity [1, 3]. Most molecules with sensitivity to fundamental effects are unavailable due to limited production and open questions about the nature of their structure. The production and spectroscopy of RaF [34, 35, 33] and AcF [4] at ISOLDE are pioneering developments towards characterizing new probes within this rapidly-growing field.

At the heart of RIB facilities such as ISOLDE, the target and ion source are responsible for the production, extraction, ionization, and delivery of the ion beam [26]. A natural application of the ISOL method towards the production of radioactive molecules is to form the species of interest in the target and ion source unit, followed by ionization and extraction as an ion beam as routinely done for atomic ion beams of interest. Volatile molecules were used to extract actinide nuclides in the form of molecular fluoride ion beams [9]. Actinium, uranium, neptunium, and plutonium molecules were observed [6].

Unfortunately, this method does not apply to all molecules of interest, particularly fragile configurations that are not stable in high-temperature environments. To create these molecules at ISOL facilities, other techniques that provide lower-temperature environments for molecular formation are needed, with the requirement that these techniques must keep the ability to integrate with the radioactive species produced in the target through accelerator-driven nuclear reactions. This project pursued the formation of molecules from mass-separated ion beams in a helium-buffer-gas-filled radio-frequency-quadrupole cooler-buncher ion trap by reactions with residual gas impurities. Varying the interaction time in the trap was shown to affect the formation rates of molecular species, providing a method to produce molecules of interest at ambient temperature. The techniques used for formation of these actinide molecules have been published in Ref. [9] and discussed further in Ref. [6].

Ac^+ , AcF^+ , and AcF_2^+ were identified by α - and γ -decay spectroscopy measurements using the ISOLDE Fast Tape Station [32] as well as by time-of-flight mass measurements using the ISOLTRAP Multi-Reflection Time-of-Flight mass spectrometer (MR-ToF MS) [36]. Successful production of AcF^+ enabled the first laser spectroscopy studies of the AcF molecule [5, 6]. Results are presently under analysis.

3.2.3 Offline developments for molecular ion beams

At online facilities, time and resources are a limiting constraint for conducting technical developments. These studies benefit from systematic investigations at “offline” facilities without direct irradiation capabilities. ISOLDE’s offline 2 mass separator facility [29] features copies of key ISOLDE infrastructure and offers a platform to conduct technical developments towards ion beam formation in a systematic way. ISOLDE’s offline 2 mass separator facility has been upgraded with two new gas systems and time-resolved single-ion-counting data acquisition, towards studies of molecular formation, ionization, breakup and fundamental properties [11].

The new upgrades are used to conduct a proof-of-concept systematic study on the production of barium fluoride molecules as an offline homologue to the radium fluoride molecules produced [33, 20] and studied online at ISOLDE. The publication [11] demonstrates the formation and study of molecular ion beams directly from the ion source, and shows a preliminary set up for the investigation of molecules prepared in the RFQcb ion trap. Future upgrades beyond Ref. [11] are in progress, comprising the addition of a mass-separation stage and beam identification capabilities after the Offline 2 RFQcb [7] as an upgrade of the ToF drift section [11]. The proposal to add mass spectrometry infrastructure after the RFQ such as a Wien filter, a deceleration stage coupled to a ToF device, or an MR-ToF was funded. Design and procurement of components for the next upgrade are underway as described in Ref. [31]. The upgraded mass-separation step after the RFQcb would allow the Offline 2 facility to separate and identify masses of interest in the resulting cooled and bunched beams after the RFQ. The effects of in-trap molecular formation and dissociation could then be systematically studied at the offline mass separator before moving this technology to ISOLDE for use with radioactive ion beams in the formation and preparation of molecular beams for studies of fundamental physics.

3.3 Conclusions

This project concludes with the development of experimental infrastructure and techniques applied to the production of isotopes in the actinide region [6]. The results demonstrate the production and extraction of actinide atomic ion beams of actinium, thorium, uranium, neptunium, and plutonium, as well as actinium, thorium, uranium, neptunium and plutonium fluoride molecular ions with different considerations for the production and available isotopes of each actinide element. The selection of actinide isotopes which can be produced and studied at ISOL facilities as atoms or molecules with high-energy proton driver beams using the current state-of-the-art have been identified. The infrastructure, including single-ion counting capabilities, and the results, including information about target and ion source operational parameters, release properties, expected intensities and contamination, are already being used to conduct further experiments on the actinide elements in their atomic and molecular forms.

3.4 Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European’s Union Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program (grant number 861198 project ‘LISA’ MSC ITN)

Bibliography

- [1] R. Alarcon et al. Electric dipole moments and the search for new physics, 2022.
- [2] A. Andreyev, B. . Andel, S. Antalic, A. E. Barzakh, T. Berry, M. J. G Borge, J. A. Briz, A. Broniš, T. E. Cocolios, K. Chrysalidis, J. G. Cubiss, H. De Witte, K. Dockx, D. V. Fedorov, V. N. Fedosseev, L. M. Fraile, L. Gaffney, G. Georgiev, P. T. Greenlees, L. J. Harkness-Brennan, R. Heinke, A. Illana, J. Johnson, D. T. Joss, D. S. Judson, U. Koester, J. Konki, J. Kurcewicz, I. Lazarus, R. Lică, M. Madurga, N. Marginean, B. A. Marsh, C. Mihai, P. L.

- Molkanov, P. Mosat, E. Nacher, A. Negret, K. Nishio, R. D. Page, S. Pascu, A. Perea, V. Pucknell, P. Rahkila, E. Rapisarda, S. Rothe, M. D. Seliverstov, A. Stott, C. Sotty, M. Stryczyk, O. Tengblad, I. Tsekhanovich, P. Van Duppen, V. Vedia, R. Wadsworth, N. Warr, S. G. Wilkins, Y. Watanabe, Y. Hirayama, M. Mukai, S. Imura, H. Watanabe, A. Algora, and P. Jones. Feasibility studies towards the systematic investigation of the β -delayed fission in the neutron-rich actinides. Technical report, CERN, Letter of Intent to the ISOLDE and Neutron Time-of-Flight Committee, 2020.
- [3] G. Arrowsmith-Kron et al. Opportunities for Fundamental Physics Research with Radioactive Molecules. *Reports on Progress in Physics*, 2024.
- [4] M. Athanasakis-Kaklamanakis et al. Laser ionization spectroscopy of AcF. *CERN-INTC*, (CERN-INTC-2021-053 / INTC-P-615):1–12, 2021.
- [5] M. Athanasakis-Kaklamanakis, S. G. Wilkins, A. A. Breier, and G. Neyens. King-Plot Analysis of Isotope Shifts in Simple Diatomic Molecules. *Physical Review X*, 13(1):11015, 2023.
- [6] M. Au. *Production of actinide atomic and molecular ion beams at CERN-ISOLDE*. Doctoral thesis, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz, 2023. CERN-THESIS-2023-228.
- [7] M. Au, M. Athanasakis-Kaklamanakis, and S. Rothe. A mass spectrometer for molecular ion beam development at ISOLDE OFFLINE. Technical report, CERN, Aug 2021.
- [8] M. Au, A. Borschevsky, K. Chrysalidis, R. Crosa-Rossa, C. Düllmann, R. Heinke, A. Jara-dat, M. Kaja, B. Marsh, I. Moore, A. Raggio, S. Rothe, S. Stegemann, D. van Eerten, and C. Walther. In-source laser resonance ionization spectroscopy of neptunium and plutonium. Technical report, CERN, Letter of Intent to the ISOLDE and Neutron Time-of-Flight Committee, Geneva, 2022.
- [9] M. Au et al. In-source and in-trap formation of molecular ions in the actinide mass range at CERN-ISOLDE. *Nucl. Instrum. Methods B*, 541:375–379, 2023.
- [10] M. Au et al. Production of neptunium and plutonium nuclides from uranium carbide using 1.4-GeV protons. *Phys. Rev. C*, 107(6):064604, 2023.
- [11] Au, M and others. Developments at CERN-ISOLDE’s OFFLINE 2 mass separator facility for studies of molecular ion beams. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research, Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 541(May):144–147, 2023.
- [12] J. Ballof. *Radioactive Molecular Beams at CERN-ISOLDE*. Doctoral thesis, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz, 2021. CERN-THESIS-2021-226.
- [13] J. Ballof, J. Ramos, A. Molander, K. Johnston, S. Rothe, T. Stora, and Ch. E. Düllmann. The upgraded ISOLDE yield database - a new tool to predict beam intensities. *Nucl. Instrum. Methods B*, 463:211–215, 2020.
- [14] M. Block, M. Laatiaoui, and S. Raeder. Recent progress in laser spectroscopy of the actinides. *Progress in Particle and Nuclear Physics*, 116:0–1, 2021.
- [15] R. Catherall et al. The ISOLDE facility. *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics*, 44(9):1, 2017.

- [16] CERN-ISOLDE. The ISOLDE yield database, version 0.2. <https://cern.ch/isolde-yields>, 2021. [Online; accessed 01.03.2022].
- [17] N. Edelstein, J. Fuger, L. Morss, and J. Katz. *The Chemistry of the Actinide and Transactinide Elements*. Springer, 2006.
- [18] R. Eder, H. Grawe, E. Hagebø, P. Hoff, E. Kugler, H. L. Ravn, and K. Steffensen. The production yields of radioactive ion-beams from fluorinated targets at the ISOLDE on-line mass separator. *Nuclear Inst. and Methods in Physics Research, B*, 62(4):535–540, jan 1992.
- [19] B. Eichler, S. Hübener, and H. Rossbach. Adsorption flüchtiger Metalle auf metallischen Oberflächen und ihre Anwendung in der Kernchemie: Berechnung der Enthalpie der dissoziativen Chemisorption von Monooxiden der Seltenerdmetalle und Actinoide. Technical report, Rossendorf Fachinformations-Zentrum. Zentral-Inst., Dresden, 1986.
- [20] R. F. Garcia Ruiz et al. Spectroscopy of short-lived radioactive molecules. *Nature*, 581(May):396–400, 2020.
- [21] K. Gaul and R. Berger. Global analysis of cp-violation in atoms, molecules and role of medium-heavy systems, 2024.
- [22] R. Heinke, M. Au, C. Bernerd, K. Chrysalidis, T. E. Cocolios, V. N. Fedosseev, I. Hendriks, A. A. Jaradat, M. Kaja, T. Kieck, T. Kron, R. Mancheva, B. A. Marsh, S. Marzari, S. Raeder, S. Rothe, D. Studer, F. Weber, and K. Wendt. First on-line application of the high-resolution spectroscopy laser ion source PI-LIST at ISOLDE. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 541:8–12, May 2023.
- [23] R. Heinke et al. Investigation of octupole deformation in neutron-rich actinium using high-resolution in-source laser spectroscopy. Technical report, CERN, Proposal to the ISOLDE and Neutron Time-of-Flight Committee, Geneva, 2020.
- [24] R. Heinke and A. Jaradat. Implementation of PI-LIST at ISOLDE. Technical report, EU H2020 LISA MSCA ITN, Oct. 2022.
- [25] M. Kaja. *Resonance laser ionization of neptunium isotopes*. Doctoral thesis, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz, 2000. In preparation.
- [26] U. Köster et al. Progress in ISOL target–ion source systems. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 266(19-20):4229–4239, oct 2008.
- [27] S. o. Kraemer. Observation of the radiative decay of the ^{229}Th nuclear clock isomer. *Nature*, 617(May):706–710, 2022.
- [28] P. Naubereit, T. Gottwald, D. Studer, and K. Wendt. Excited atomic energy levels in protactinium by resonance ionization spectroscopy. *Physical Review A*, 98(2):1–6, 2018.
- [29] S. Rothe, M. Au, J. Ballof, E. Barbero, M. Bissell, A. Boucherie, and M. Bovigny. Targets and ion sources at CERN-ISOLDE — Facilities and developments. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research, Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 542(June):38–44, 2023.

- [30] M. R. Savina et al. High Useful Yield and Isotopic Analysis of Uranium by Resonance Ionization Mass Spectrometry. *Analytical Chemistry*, 89(11):6224–6231, 2017.
- [31] M. Schuett et al. Developments at the CERN-ISOLDE Offline 2 mass separator. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research, Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 541(May):82–85, 2023.
- [32] S. Stegemann et al. The CERN-ISOLDE fast tape station. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research, Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 541(May):169–172, 2023.
- [33] S. M. Udrescu et al. Isotope shifts of radium monofluoride molecules. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 127:033001, Jul 2021.
- [34] S.-M. Udrescu et al. Precision spectroscopy and laser cooling scheme of a radium-containing molecule. *accepted in Nat. Phys.*, 2023.
- [35] S. G. Wilkins et al. Observation of the distribution of nuclear magnetization in a molecule, 2023.
- [36] R. N. Wolf et al. ISOLTRAP’s multi-reflection time-of-flight mass separator/spectrometer. *International Journal of Mass Spectrometry*, 349-350(1):123–133, sep 2013.

Chapter 4

Production and study of actinides at IGISOL via decay spectroscopy and laser spectroscopy techniques within the LISA framework

Andrea Raggio^a, Iain D. Moore^a and Ilkka Pohjalainen^a

^a Accelerator Laboratory, Department of Physics, University of Jyväskylä, FIN-40014 Jyväskylä, Finland

A research program on actinide elements has been developed within the LISA framework at the IGISOL facility, University of Jyväskylä Accelerator laboratory JYFL-ACCLAB. The aim is the study of nuclear structure properties via the use of nuclear decay spectroscopy and laser spectroscopy techniques. The program is focused on two objectives. Firstly, the study of neutron-deficient actinides produced online via light ion-induced fusion-evaporation reactions, in a region in which reflection-asymmetric shapes have been predicted by theoretical models. Secondly, a high resolution laser spectroscopy measurement of the 76-eV ^{235m}U isomeric state, the second lowest known excited state in the nuclear landscape, produced following the alpha decay of ^{239}Pu . The results and the development carried out at the IGISOL facility towards these goals are reported.

4.1 Introduction

A renewed interest in the study of actinide isotopes over the past few years has emerged due to evidence for rich nuclear structure evolution, in particular in the neutron-deficient region, where theoretical models predict the most pronounced reflection-asymmetric shapes [2, 3, 1]. Such pear-shaped nuclei are of particular interest to more fundamental physics explorations, as the additional octupole correlations that generate the collective shapes results in a large enhancement of symmetry-violating properties, for example the Schiff moment [4, 5]. A future measurement of this moment would help to constrain sources of charge-parity (CP) violation, which have been proposed in seeking explanations for the observed asymmetry between matter and antimatter in the universe. In addition, the actinide elements host unique cases of interest in which state-of-the-art atomic and nuclear theoretical models are challenged in their predictive capabilities. This is the case for the two well-known low-energy isomers in ^{229}Th [6, 7] and ^{235}U [8], the former proposed

as a potential candidate for a nuclear clock, with the recent result of the first laser excitation of a nuclear state [9].

Despite the interest, ground-state nuclear structure properties in the region remain largely unexplored, mainly due to the challenges in the production of these exotic nuclei and the limited availability of macroscopic quantities of stable species [10]. In this regard, the IGISOL (Ion Guide Isotope Separator On-Line) facility [11] at the University of Jyväskylä Accelerator laboratory (JYFL-ACCLAB) offers a unique environment to develop methods and research on actinide elements thanks to the availability of accelerated beams from the local K130 cyclotron combined with different production methods based on the ion-guide technique [12]. The ion guide technique offers a chemically insensitive extraction method for radioactive isotopes with respect to other ISOL-based facilities, a desirable characteristic particularly in the actinide region in which the refractory properties of the elements of interest pose limitation in their production and study.

Within the LISA project, an extended research program towards the study of actinide elements has been pursued at the IGISOL facility. The research focuses on the development of a range of production methods for low-energy beams of exotic actinide isotopes and the use of complementary spectroscopic techniques. This includes high resolution laser spectroscopy and nuclear decay spectroscopy. The former provides access to information such as the evolution of mean-square charge radii through the measurement of isotopic shifts in atomic transitions, in addition to nuclear electric quadrupole and magnetic dipole moments obtained via the atomic hyperfine structure [13]. Decay spectroscopy studies, on the other hand, provide a window to the measurement of decay modes of nuclei, as well as energies (Q-values), branching ratios, half-lives, excited states, spins and parities and so forth, basic nuclear structure information that is surprisingly lacking in the region of interest.

4.2 Implementation

The research has been structured around two complementary objectives. The first is the development of a research program tailored in the production of neutron-deficient actinide isotopes. The second objective is dedicated to the study via high resolution laser spectroscopy of the ^{235m}U isomeric state. In the following Sections (4.2.1,4.2.2), the development and results towards these goals are reported.

4.2.1 Production and study of neutron deficient actinides

Neutron deficient actinides were produced by the use of on-line light ion-induced fusion-evaporation reactions on long-lived actinide targets which are manufactured in collaboration with the nuclear chemistry department of Mainz University [14]. Different primary beams are available, including protons, deuterons and other light-ion species. Throughout the LISA project, all experiments have used protons due to flexibility in both energy as well as intensity. In order to assess the independent isotopic yields obtained with different beam and target combinations, and to obtain basic nuclear spectroscopic data, a dedicated decay spectroscopy setup has been developed and upgraded during three experimental campaigns, leading to the latest design named VADER (Versatile Actinides DEcay spectROscopy setup) [15] (see Fig. 4.1). VADER has initially been commissioned at the end of a beam line of the IGISOL mass separator, in which ions at 30-kV potential can be delivered. The system has been designed to accommodate thin implantation C foils surrounded by a compact

geometry detection system composed of an array of silicon and LN2-cooled silicon-lithium (Si(Li)) detectors, and a number of broad-energy germanium (BeGe) detectors. This suite of detectors allows the measurement of alpha particles following the alpha decay of the implanted nuclei and the subsequent electrons emitted as a result of internal conversion of the populated excited states, in addition to gamma rays produced by the de-excitation of excited states. The coincident detection of these different decay products allows for a complete reconstruction of the nuclear level scheme. One highlight of this work followed the successful production of ^{225}Pa and ^{221}Ac in proton-induced reactions on a ^{232}Th target. By employing different coincidence conditions between detectors, the level scheme of ^{221}Ac was reconstructed and interpreted in terms of parity-doublet bands which are a signature of the presence of reflection asymmetry[16], demonstrating the capabilities of the method.

New proposals have been submitted from external collaborators to employ VADER after the JYFLTRAP Penning trap, to allow for trap-assisted purification of beams prior to nuclear decay spectroscopy. In addition, in 2025, the IGISOL facility will host a more advanced decay spectroscopy station, SEASON (Spectroscopy Electron and Alpha in Silicon bOx couNter), developed by CEA Saclay. The detection efficiency for alpha particles (electrons) is expected to be a factor of 3 (7) greater than VADER [17]. SEASON will initially be benchmarked against VADER by studying the same reaction as employed in the LISA project. A future campaign of measurements using different targets (^{238}U , ^{242}Pu ...) will offer access to a wider region of actinide isotopes, indicating the ongoing importance of the scientific study of such nuclei.

Fig. 4.1: Cross-sectional view of the VADER decay spectroscopy station. The in-vacuum silicon detectors are labeled. Three germanium detectors (not shown) are placed behind the two side flanges that host the segmented quadrant silicon detectors (QuadSi1 and 2), as well as the top flange. Figure adapted from [15] under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0.

4.2.2 Development toward high resolution laser spectroscopy of ^{235m}U isomeric state

The second objective is focused on the measurement of the second lowest-lying isomeric state throughout the nuclear chart, the 76-eV isomer in ^{235}U , via high-resolution laser spectroscopy utilizing the IGISOL collinear laser spectroscopy (CLS) setup [18]. Before a final experiment on the isomer can be realized, several developments have been implemented. The first two are connected to the isomer production which is needed to conduct the study. Unlike the online method of fusion-evaporation reactions, a more appropriate method for the production of ^{235m}U is via the alpha decay from the parent ^{239}Pu , with a summed $\sim 99\%$ alpha decay branching ratio. A set of more than 15 ^{239}Pu alpha-recoil sources has been produced in collaboration with ESR 11 in the Radio-chemistry Department of Mainz University. These sources have been produced employing the molecular plating technique [19] over substrates of either Si or Ti, in a disc-shaped format of 22 mm in diameter. An extensive characterization of the sources has been carried out to determine the activity, source thickness and possible impurities via alpha/gamma spectrometry and Rutherford Back Scattering (RBS) techniques. These parameters are known to have a critical impact on the resulting recoil efficiency from the source and thus play an important role on the available yield for subsequent experiments. In addition to these materials-characterization studies, the direct detection of the conversion electrons from the de-excitation of the isomeric state has been performed using a new setup called DICE (apparatus for Detection of Internal Conversion Electrons) [20].

In order to produce an isomeric beam of ^{235m}U , the alpha-recoils from the ^{239}Pu sources need to be thermalized and injected into the IGISOL mass separator. This is achieved by the use of a suitable gas cell in which the charged recoils are stopped in an ultra-pure helium buffer gas and guided through an extraction nozzle into a radiofrequency (RF) sextupole ion guide. Here, the low energy ions are transferred through a differential pumping section to a high vacuum region, and are subsequently accelerated to 30 kV potential towards the dipole magnet. Intensive gas cell development work has been carried out by testing different configurations with the aim of maximizing the extraction efficiency of the isomer from the gas cell, to produce a sufficient yield for a CLS experiment. Three different designs have been tested and characterized, culminating in the alpha-recoil gas cell Mk. III version depicted in Fig. 4.2. In this configuration a set of 12 sources has been carefully installed to maximize the active surface area and therefore the recoil yield. In addition to a typical helium gas pressure of ~ 55 mbar, a positive bias of ~ 25 V has been applied to the source mounts which has been found to be critical for an enhancement of the extraction efficiency. After mass separation, the ions are delivered to a multi-channel plate (MCP) detector at the focal plane of the mass separator. A combined yield of 6000 cps has been recorded in both 2+ and 3+ charge states while a negligible amount of 1+ ions was observed. This can be understood via the relationship between the ionization potential of the different U charge states, with those of impurities in the helium gas. Due to the high purity of the gas, a considerable 1+ charge state fraction was not expected. An additional test employing a controlled injection of a He:Xe mixture at 0.1% concentration in the purified He buffer gas, to obtain a Xe concentration level of 1 part-per-million in the stopping medium, has shown the ability to selectively convert the 3+ fraction to 2+. The resulting yields are considered sufficient for a CLS experiment. Nevertheless, the absence of singly charged ^{235m}U ions poses a potential obstacle for the laser transitions considered for this study, which were initially selected to be performed on the 1+ ion.

Fig. 4.2: Exploded and cross-section view of the alpha-recoil gas cell MkIII. The orange disks represent the molecular plated ^{239}Pu sources, mounted on a custom built modular hexagonal structure. The yellow arrows represent the ultra-pure He gas flow used to thermalize the recoils and drive them to the output nozzle. The total volume of the gas cell is approximately 600 cm^3 , with a typical extraction time from the source location of 100s of ms.

The third and final development carried out during the period of LISA is related to the CLS groundwork needed to characterize the spectroscopic efficiency of different ionic transitions and to produce reference values prior to the isomeric state measurement. A set of 10 transitions, in the 300-nm wavelength range, have been investigated using a discharge ion source equipped with a natural U sample. The lines, in the 1+ system, were tested within the CLS setup, where the 30 kV ion beam is overlapped with a counter-propagating laser beam. When laser frequency is in resonance with the transition of interest, the electrons are promoted to the excited state of the selected transition, which then decays spontaneously via fluorescence de-excitation releasing a photon that can be detected using photo-multiplier tubes in the so called Light Collection Region (LCR). The Doppler velocity compression of the 30 kV beam results in a measurement of the transition with a resolution in the 10s MHz range, close to the natural linewidth of the transition. Isotope shifts have been measured for $^{234,235}\text{U}$ with respect to the reference ^{238}U , in addition to the hyperfine structure of ^{235}U , allowing the refinement of the HFS parameters of the ground state and first metastable state of the 1+ system and the measurement of 8 new magnetic dipole and electric quadrupole hyperfine parameters for higher lying levels in the $32000\text{--}35000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range. Figure 4.3 shows the measured transitions for the three isotopes of interest.

Fig. 4.3: Transitions in U^+ measured in the 300-nm range. The resulting spectral lines from $^{234,235,238}U$ are shown in green, red and blue, respectively. Each transition (labeled with wavelength in vacuum) has been centered on the reference resonance of ^{238}U . As can be seen, the span in frequency space required to cover the different isotopes is considerable however is rather typical for such heavy elements.

4.3 Summary and Outlook

The use of long-lived actinide targets in combination with the proton-induced fusion-evaporation reactions employed at IGISOL has proven to be a good method to produce and study neutron-deficient actinides. Several experiments have been carried out, both with the aim of characterizing the production yields with different target materials and deposition methods, and to study the properties of the short-lived nuclei produced in the reactions. Nuclei up to 10 evaporated nucleons away from the target material have been studied with modern nuclear decay spectroscopy techniques, opening a window of possibilities for the future. The use of novel Drop-on-Demand (DoD) targets [14] of long-lived actinide species is also under investigation, to further increase the extent of nuclei reachable by the technique. A yield production check of isotopes closer to the target material, where the reaction cross sections are generally higher, is also planned, to evaluate the feasibility of performing collinear laser spectroscopy measurements in which the yield requirements are more stringent than those for decay spectroscopy experiments. Due to the long half-lives of less exotic nuclei, such yield measurements cannot be performed via decay counting methods and thus will be performed using ion counting after the Penning trap.

In parallel to the above mentioned studies, the development of an isomeric beam of ^{235m}U has produced promising results, opening a window to the possibility of a near-future high resolution collinear laser spectroscopy measurement of the isomeric state. However, the charge state in which the isomer is produced remains an obstacle, since the (strongest) spectroscopic transitions current under consideration are in the singly charged ion. In this regard, investigations are undergoing,

such as the possibility of using the collinear line charge exchange cell to further manipulate the charge state of the isomeric beam. In parallel, measurements are also planned to explore transitions in the doubly charged ion.

Compilation of Milestones and Deliverables

In the following table a list of milestones and deliverables of the LISA Work Package 5 (WP5) associated to this contribution is reported.

Code	Title	Description	Date
LISA-MS23	Offline study of atomic transitions in uranium	Performing a collinear laser spectroscopy measurement on U isotopes produced by a U electric discharge source	30.09.2021
LISA-D5.2	Laser Ablation Source	Technical report on the design and simulation of an off-line laser ablation source	30.04.2022
LISA-D5.3	Off-line U studies	Scientific report on the analysis of the collinear laser spectroscopy data produced on U	30.04.2022
LISA-D5.6	Exotic U studies	Report on the development towards the ^{235m}U isomeric state study	31.10.2023

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 861198–LISA–H2020–MSCA–ITN–2019 as well as from the Academy of Finland under project number 339245.

Bibliography

- [1] Cao, Y. et al., “Landscape of pear-shaped even-even nuclei” *Physical Review C* 102.2 (2020): 024311.
- [2] Butler, P. A. and Nazarewicz W. “Intrinsic reflection asymmetry in atomic nuclei”. *Reviews of Modern Physics* 68.2 (1996):349.
- [3] Butler, P. A. “Octupole Collectivity in Nuclei”. *Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics* 43.7 (2016):073002.
- [4] Engel, J. et al., "Time-reversal violating Schiff moment of ^{225}Ra ." *Physical Review C* 68, no. 2 (2003): 025501.
- [5] Flambaum, V. V., "Enhanced nuclear schiff moment and time-reversal violation in th ^{229}Th -containing molecules." *Physical Review C* 99.3 (2019): 035501.

- [6] Kraemer, S. et al., "Observation of the radiative decay of the ^{229}Th nuclear clock isomer". *Nature* 617.7962 (2023): 706–710.
- [7] Thielking, J. et al., "Laser spectroscopic characterization of the nuclear-clock isomer ^{229m}Th ". *Nature* 556.7701 (2018): 321–325.
- [8] Ponce, F. et al., "Accurate measurement of the first excited nuclear state in U 235". *Physical Review C* 97.5 (2018): 054310.
- [9] Tiedau, J. et al., "Laser excitation of the Th-229 nucleus". *Physical Review Letters* 132.18 (2024): 182501.
- [10] Block, M. et al., "Recent progress in laser spectroscopy of the actinides." *Progress in Particle and Nuclear Physics* 116 (2021): 103834.
- [11] Moore, I. D. et al., "The IGISOL technique-three decades of developments.". *Hyperfine interactions* 223, no. 1 (2014): 17-62.
- [12] Äystö, J. "Development and applications of the IGISOL technique.". *Nuclear Physics A* 693.1-2 (2001): 477-494.
- [13] Koszorús, Á. et al., "Nuclear structure studies by collinear laser spectroscopy.". *The European Physical Journal A* 60, no. 1 (2024): 20.
- [14] Haas, R. et al. "Development and characterization of a drop-on-demand inkjet printing system for nuclear target fabrication." *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 874 (2017): 43-49.
- [15] Raggio, A. et al., "VADER: A novel decay station for actinide spectroscopy." *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 540 (2023): 148-150.
- [16] Rey-Herme, E., et al., "Level structure of Ac 221 and Fr 217 from decay spectroscopy, and reflection asymmetry in Ac 221." *Physical Review C* 108.1 (2023): 014304.
- [17] Rey-Herme, E. "Octupole deformation in ^{221}Ac and development of the SEASON detector". *Nuclear Experiment [nucl-ex]*. Université Paris-Saclay, 2023UPASP064 (2023).
- [18] de Groote, R. P., et al. "Upgrades to the collinear laser spectroscopy experiment at the IGISOL." *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 463 (2020): 437-440.
- [19] Vascon, A. et al., "The performance of thin layers produced by molecular plating as α -particle sources." *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment* 721 (2013): 35-44.
- [20] Reed, L. E. et al., "DICE: Apparatus for Detection of Internal Conversion Electrons." In *EPJ Web of Conferences*, 285 (2023): 01002.

Chapter 5

Laser spectroscopic investigations on the actinide atomic and nuclear structures

Magdalena Kaja^a, Klaus Wendt^a

representing part of the LISA consortium and the Fermium collaboration

^a Institute of Physics, Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz, 55099 Mainz, Germany

This report encapsulates a comprehensive research endeavor aimed at advancing mid- and high-resolution multi-step laser resonance ionization spectroscopy of various actinide isotopes. The project involved diverse research objectives, including the development of efficient and selective excitation/ionization methods, exploration of atomic and hyperfine structures, and determination of isotope shifts. Key outcomes include Deliverable D4.4, providing fundamental resonance ionization data for ten lighter actinides, and a series of publications detailing significant findings. Notably, publication two focuses on the development and application of the Field Ionization Laser Ion Source and Trap (FI-LIST), while publications three and four delve into the exploration of neptunium's atomic structure.

5.1 Project description

The project aimed to conduct mid- and high-resolution multi-step laser resonance ionization spectroscopy on minute samples of various actinide isotopes, achieving maximum sensitivity. Research objectives were diverse, encompassing the development of efficient and selective excitation/ionization methods, exploration of atomic and hyperfine structures, and determination of isotope and isomer shifts. These goals were pursued using high repetition-rate, pulsed, narrow-bandwidth laser radiation from JGU Titanium:sapphire laser systems. Elements studied included Ac, Th, Pa, U, Np, Pu, Am, Cm, Bk, and Cf ($Z=89-98$), employing both direct in-source and cross-beam configurations within a quadrupole structure. Handling permissions were secured for all long-lived isotopes with lifetimes extending beyond years, and suitable mass spectrometers and detection systems were readily available. Access to the targeted species was facilitated through close collaboration with JGU's nuclear chemistry and research reactor units.

5.2 Deliverable

Deliverable D4.4: Basic resonance ionization data from Ti:Sa laser spectroscopy for 10 lighter actinides was provided on 23rd May 2023. It contains basic resonance ionization data from Ti:Sapphire laser spectroscopy for ten lighter actinides Ac, Th, Pa, U, Np, Pu, Am, Cm, Bk and Cf. The ionization potential of these actinides as well as a number of three- and two-step excitation/ionization schemes are reported. Extensive and meticulous searches were conducted to identify individual excitation schemes suitable for resonance ionization spectroscopy (RIS). However, despite efforts to access all historical data, it is acknowledged that the list may not be entirely exhaustive.

Fig. 5.1: Compilation of two-step schemes for 10 lighter actinides presented in deliverable D4.4.

5.3 Publications

During this project, the ESR5 was involved in the following published studies.

1. **Investigation of the atomic structure of curium and determination of its first ionization potential** [1].

The atomic structure of curium was investigated using resonance ionization spectroscopy, populating three different excited energy levels from the ground state. Wide-range scans for a search of second excitation steps were performed, and the spectra were analyzed to identify Rydberg levels and auto-ionizing resonances. The ionization potential was determined to be $48\,330.68(16)\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This result, obtained through Rydberg convergences and DC electric

field ionization, deviates by 6.7 from the previous literature value of $48\,324(2)\text{cm}^{-1}$ and is about ten times more precise.

2. Characterization of the field ionization extension for the laser ion source and trap: Measurement of the ionization potential of ytterbium [2].

The development and application of the Field Ionization Laser Ion Source and Trap (FI-LIST) at the RISIKO mass separator at Mainz University were reported. The FI-LIST, adapted from the LIST unit used at Mainz and CERN-ISOLDE, was designed for field ionization of highly excited atoms in a homogeneous electric field. Performance was assessed with ionization potential measurements on ytterbium, achieving a relative precision of $3 \cdot 10^{-6}$, in excellent agreement with the literature value.

Fig. 5.2: Technical drawing with half-cut of the Field Ionization Laser Ion Source - FI-LIST. Picture taken from [2].

3. Resonant laser ionization of neptunium: investigation on excitation schemes and the first ionization potential [3].

Fig. 5.3: Two-step excitation schemes investigated in neptunium. Picture taken from [3].

The atomic structure of neptunium (Np) was investigated using two-step resonance ionization spectroscopy. The study identified two-step ionization schemes for trace analysis and nuclear

structure investigations by exploring ground-state transitions and transitions to high-lying or auto-ionizing states. The lifetimes of two excited states at $25\,342.48\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $25\,277.64\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were measured as $230(12)\text{ ns}$ and $173(9)\text{ ns}$, respectively. The first ionization potential (IP) was determined through field ionization of high-lying, weakly-bound states using a static electric field, resulting in an IP value of $50\,535.54(15)\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which aligns with the current literature value but with over ten times higher precision.

4. Probing the nuclear structure of $^{237,239}\text{Np}$ by laser spectroscopy [4].

Nuclear ground state properties of $^{237,239}\text{Np}$ were investigated using high-resolution laser spectroscopy at the RISIKO mass separator at Mainz University. Isotope shifts and hyperfine parameters were determined in two atomic ground-state transitions at 398.80 nm and 395.61 nm . This data enabled the calculation of the previously unknown nuclear moments of the short-lived isotope ^{239}Np , including a nuclear magnetic dipole moment and an electric quadrupole moment, using the known nuclear moments of ^{237}Np as a reference.

5. Nuclear moments and isotope shifts of the actinide isotopes $^{249-253}\text{Cf}$ probed by laser spectroscopy [5].

High-resolution laser spectroscopy on $^{249-253}\text{Cf}$ was performed at the RISIKO mass separator at Mainz University, investigating three atomic ground-state transitions. Hyperfine parameters and isotope shifts were measured, revealing changes in mean-squared charge radii across the deformed nuclear shell closure at $N = 152$. Improved nuclear magnetic-dipole moments for ^{249}Cf and first-time measurements for ^{251}Cf and ^{253}Cf , along with spectroscopic quadrupole moments for ^{249}Cf and ^{253}Cf , were determined.

6. First on-line application of the high-resolution spectroscopy laser ion source PI-LIST at ISOLDE [7].

A specialized resonance ionization laser ion source (PI-LIST) developed for high-resolution spectroscopy below typical hot cavity Doppler broadening limits, particularly for on-line experiments at CERN-ISOLDE was presented. The PI-LIST achieves a spectral linewidth of $200\text{--}300\text{ MHz}$, with potential for sub- 100 MHz , utilizing perpendicular laser/atom beam interaction in a radio-frequency quadrupole unit downstream of the hot atomizer cavity. Compared to standard in-source laser ionization, efficiency reduction factors range from a few hundred to over a thousand, offering enhanced nuclear structure investigations at thick target radioactive ion beam facilities without requiring dedicated experimental beam line setups.

7. Opportunities and limitations of in-gas-cell laser spectroscopy of the heaviest elements with RADRIS [6]

The radiation detection resonance ionization spectroscopy (RADRIS) technique allows for laser spectroscopic investigations of the heaviest elements, produced in atom-at-a-time quantities from fusion-evaporation reactions. Laser spectroscopy is conducted in a buffer-gas environment to enhance efficiency and thermalize high-energy evaporation residues behind the velocity filter SHIP. However, the cyclic measurement procedure, combined with filament collection for neutralization and ion confinement followed by pulse-heat desorption, imposes constraints on the technique's applicability. This paper evaluates some of these limitations and the opportunities arising from this unique measurement setup.

Publications two, three, and four were centered on the primary focus of the ESR5 PhD study titled "Shining light on neptunium: Laser spectroscopy for probing atomic structure". The study aimed to explore the atomic structure of neptunium including for example investigation of the ionization schemes (see Fig. 1.2), analysis of the electronic levels including their lifetime, and determination of the ionization potential (IP) [3]. The latter was not possible to be determined using commonly used techniques and apparatuses in the LARISSA laboratory, that were presented in the study on curium [1]. Consequently, a new ion source unit named Field Ionization Laser Ion Source and Trap (FI-LIST) was developed and characterized on ytterbium [2]. This device enabled the determination of the IP using the saddle-point model, involving the ionization of highly excited atoms in a static homogeneous electric field. As illustrated in Fig. 1.3, FI-LIST bears resemblance to the well-known and recently online-tested PI-LIST [7, 10], upon which it was based. Additionally, measurements of hyperfine spectra of two ground state transitions in the $^{237,239}\text{Np}$ were conducted. That allowed the determination of hyperfine parameters and nuclear moments of ^{239}Np as well as isotope shifts between ^{237}Np and ^{239}Np . ESR5 also contributed to experiments performed at CERN-ISOLDE, associated with either PI-LIST [10] or actinides [8, 9].

Acknowledgements

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement project number 861198 (LISA) Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network (ITN).

The Fermium collaboration

Mainz University: Julian Auler, Sebastian Berndt, Holger Dorrer, Christoph E. Düllmann, Vadim Gadelshin, Raphael Hasse, Magdalena A. Kaja, Nina Kneip, Mustapha Laatiaoui, Andrea T. Loria Basto, Christoph Mokry, Thorben Niemeyer, Dennis Renisch, Jörg Runke, Matou Stemmler, Petra Thörle, Norbert Trautmann, Felix Weber, Klaus Wendt. **GSI Darmstadt:** Michael Block, Manuel Gutiérrez-Torres, Sebastian Raeder, Kenneth van Beek, Jessica Warbinek. **HIM Mainz:** Premaditya Chhetri, Tom Kieck, Jeremy Lantis, Danny Münzberg, Steven Nothhelfer, Elisabeth Rickert, Dominik Studer. **TU Darmstadt:** Thomas Walther. **Oak Ridge National Laboratory** Julie Ezold, Ashley Harvey, Kristian Mhyre, Samantha Schrell, Shelley Van Cleve. **FSU Tallahassee:** Thomas Albrecht-Schönzart, Alyssa Gaiser, Joseph Sperling. **HÜBNER Photonics:** Korbinian Hens, Volker Sonnenschein, Mitzi Urquiza-González. **GANIL:** Alexandre Brizard, Nathalie Lecesne. **ILL Grenoble:** Ulli Köster. **CERN:** Reinhard Heinke, **University of Gothenburg:** Dag Hanstorp, Nagoya University, Hideki Tomita.

Bibliography

- [1] N. Kneip et al., "Investigation of the atomic structure of curium and determination of its first ionization potential", *Eur. Phys. J. D* 76, 190 (2022). doi:10.1140/epjd/s10053-022-00510-7.
- [2] M. Kaja et al., "Characterization of the field ionization extension for the laser ion source and trap: Measurement of the ionization potential of ytterbium", *Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. B* 547, 165213 (2024). doi:10.1016/j.nimb.2023.165213.
- [3] M. Kaja et al., "Resonant laser ionization of neptunium: investigation on excitation schemes and the first ionization potential", *Eur. Phys. J. D* 78, 50 (2024). doi:10.1140/epjd/s10053-024-00833-7.

- [4] M. Kaja et al., "Probing the nuclear structure of $^{237,239}\text{Np}$ by laser spectroscopy", submitted to *Eur. Phys. J. A* on 19/03/2024 (Submission ID: EPJA-107738, status: under revision).
- [5] F. Weber et al., Nuclear moments and isotope shifts of the actinide isotopes $^{249-253}\text{Cf}$ probed by laser spectroscopy, *Phys. Rev. C* 107, 034313 (2023). doi:10.1103/PhysRevC.107.034313.
- [6] S. Raeder et al., Opportunities and limitations of in-gas-cell laser spectroscopy of the heaviest elements with RADRIS, *Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res. B* 541, 370-374 (2023). doi:10.1016/j.nimb.2023.04.044.
- [7] R. Heinke et al., "First on-line application of the high-resolution spectroscopy laser ion source PI-LIST at ISOLDE", 541, 8-12 (2023). doi:10.1016/j.nimb.2023.04.057.
- [8] M. Au et al., "In-source laser resonance ionization spectroscopy of neptunium and plutonium", Tech. rep., CERN, Geneva (2022). URL <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2809416>
- [9] M. Au et al., "Addendum - In-source laser resonance ionization spectroscopy of neptunium and plutonium", Tech. rep., CERN, Geneva (2023). URL <http://cds.cern.ch/record/2872429>
- [10] R. Heinke, "Investigation of octupole deformation in neutron-rich actinium using high-resolution in-source laser spectroscopy", Tech. rep., CERN, Geneva (2020). URL <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2717945>

Chapter 6

Experimental and theoretical investigations of negative ions

Miranda Nichols^{a,b}

^a Department of Physics, University of Gothenburg, SE-412 96, Gothenburg, Sweden

^b Instituto de Ciencias Fisicas, Universidad Nacional Autonoma de Mexico, Ap. Postal 43-8, Cuernavaca, Morelos, 62251, Mexico

The project of Early Stage Researcher 6 (ESR06), originally set to measure the electron affinity of an actinide, had to be adapted due to unforeseen circumstances. During their secondment with the CRIS experiment at ISOLDE-CERN, $^{238}\text{U}^-$ was successfully produced via two consecutive electron capture reactions. These results led to the theoretical work of the ESR, where they computed electron capture cross-sections for bare ion collisions with hydrogen using the Crank-Nicolson method. Having proven the method agrees with experiments and other theoretical models, they now plan on calculating actinide collisions. In Gothenburg, a high-precision method for measuring electron affinity values, applied to cesium and rubidium, showed applicability for francium and actinides. Stockholm studies using the DESIREE cryogenic storage ring demonstrated the manipulation of bound anionic states with lasers, also promising for actinide research. Overall, although photodetachment studies were delayed, the groundwork laid seems encouraging future work on actinide anions.

6.1 Project introduction

Negative ions exhibit heightened sensitivity to electron-electron correlation effects, making them ideal for benchmarking atomic structure models that surpass the independent particle model. Although the electron affinities (EAs) of most light elements have been extensively measured, experimental investigations on heavier elements, particularly the actinides, are limited because of their radioactive nature and the challenges associated with their production. This project aimed to investigate the atomic structure of actinides by measuring their EAs, thereby enhancing our understanding of actinides and developing methods for radioactive negative ion beam production. The primary objective was to construct a state-of-the-art beamline at the Collinear Resonance Ionization Spectroscopy (CRIS) experiment within the ISOLDE online facility at CERN. This beamline was planned to be equipped with the Gothenburg ANion Detector for Affinity measurements by Laser PHotodetachment (GANDALPH) detector, allowing any radioactive isotope produced at ISOLDE to form negative ions through a charge exchange cell. The goal was to measure the EAs of actinides, filling significant gaps in experimental data and enhancing our understanding of their electron correlation effects and atomic properties.

Additional aims included versatility for future research at CRIS, enhancing experimental capabilities at ISOLDE, and contributing to scientific knowledge and applications. The system was designed with flexibility in mind, enabling the measurement of EAs for any isotope produced at ISOLDE. This versatility would support a wide range of future experiments in nuclear and atomic physics, with practical implications in plasma physics, astrophysics, and material science.

At the beginning of the project, only a single EA of a radioactive isotope had been measured and published (^{128}I). The first EA to be measured was suggested for thorium (Th) due to its expected EA around 1.2 eV, making it relatively easy to study with commercially available lasers. Subsequent measurements for uranium (U) and actinium (Ac) were also planned, with results to be compared with theoretical work to improve our understanding of actinide atomic structures.

The project included two planned secondments with the CRIS experiment. The first, during months 25 to 31, was for the installation of GANDALPH at CRIS. The second, during months 38 to 40, was for the EA measurement of an actinide

6.2 Milestone and deliverable

The milestone of this project was the technical design of the new beamline for installation of GANDALPH at CRIS. This was accomplished. More details can be found in the milestone report. The deliverable of this project was to measure to have an electron affinity measurement of an actinide online at CERN-ISOLDE. This will not be accomplished before the end of the network. More information can be found in the Adaptations section.

6.3 Adaptations

Due to circumstances such as COVID and ISOLDE scheduling, the project aim had to be adjusted. This section will therefore highlight the adaptations made to ensure the overall work still contributed to the ultimate goal of building knowledge on the actinides.

The ESR was working with the CRIS experiment from November 2021 to September 2022. During this period, they participated in four beamtimes, one of which being the LOI on measuring polonium (Po) anion production in a charge exchange cell for the eventual electron affinity measurement online at ISOLDE [4]. In this experiment, they discovered that measuring Po^- production would require more intervention than anticipated due to the radioactive contamination. Consequently, they switched to ^{238}U and measured the negative ion production from this isotope, which was successful [3]. Measuring the production curve of U^- was necessary for further measurements. Although the EA of U has already been measured, this actinide would be an ideal first measurement to use to benchmark our methods.

This leads to the theoretical work that the ESR has since engaged in, which is necessary for future actinide anion production. They compute electron capture cross-sections in straight-line and real trajectories. Initially, this was done with hydrogen-like ions [6] to test the method and compare to experimental data. Next, this will be applied to heavy systems such as the actinides, for which no experimental data and little theoretical data is available. The method being used is called Crank-Nicolson, which is an implicit, second-order method. For heavy systems, the calculations will use the Thomas-Fermi-Amaldi potential, the precursor to density functional theory. This compliments the work done with U^- at ISOLDE.

Next, the work done on stable systems in Gothenburg was also in preparation for measurements on actinides. The group has developed a high-precision method to measure electron affinity values using partial cross-sections by selective excitation and resonance ionization. This method has been already been applied to cesium (Cs) [1] and rubidium (Rb) [2]. Eventually, this method can be applied to francium (Fr), which has an unmeasured EA value, and actinides, which have complicated open f-shell configurations and in turn many angular momenta coupling.

Lastly, studies have been made in Stockholm uses a cryogenic storage ring, DESIREE where negative ions can be stored for 1000s of seconds and probed repeatedly. In a recent experiment, we measured the isotope shift across the stable isotopes of tin (Sn) with a resonant transition within the anion. It demonstrated that the population of bound anionic states can be manipulated with a narrow-band continuous wave laser. This method is promising for actinides due to the likelihood of bound states in the anions [5].

In summary, due to scheduling priorities set by the ISOLDE physics coordinator and the CRIS collaboration steering committee, no photodetachment studies will take place before the conclusion of the LISA ITN. However, we remain positive that with the work performed and outlined in this section, we will be able to perform such studies as soon as beam time gets allocated during the online period at ISOLDE.

6.4 Publications and proposals

6.4.1 *High-resolution measurement of the electron affinity of cesium*

In this work, we present a high precision experimental determination of the electron affinity of cesium. A collinear laser-ion beam apparatus was used to investigate the partial photodetachment cross section for the cesium anion, leaving the neutral atom in the $6p\ ^2P_{3/2}$ excited state. A resonance ionization scheme was used to obtain final-state selectivity, which enabled the investigation of a sharp onset of the cross section associated with a Wigner s -wave threshold behavior. The electron affinity was determined to be 0.4715983(39) eV. This determination of the electron affinity of cesium not only adds to the precision of known atomic quantities but also enhances our understanding of electron correlation effects in negative ions. The experimental approach used in this study demonstrates a robust method for investigating other negative ions with similar properties. This research contributes valuable data that can be utilized in theoretical models and practical applications involving negative ions in various fields such as plasma physics, astrophysics, and material science [1].

6.4.2 *The electron affinity of rubidium: a state selective measurement*

Building on this methodology, we applied the same experimental setup and techniques to determine the electron affinity of rubidium. Using the same experimental scheme, we investigated the partial photodetachment cross section for the rubidium anion, leaving the neutral atom in the $5p\ ^2P_{3/2}$ excited state. This approach allowed us to observe a similar sharp onset of the cross section associated with a Wigner s -wave threshold behavior in rubidium. The electron affinity was determined to be 485.887(4) meV. The precision and reliability of our methods, as demonstrated in the cesium experiment, ensured accurate measurement of the electron affinity for rubidium. The resulting data not only expands our knowledge of electron affinities across different elements but also emphasizes the versatility and effectiveness of our experimental techniques [2].

6.4.3 *Investigating radioactive negative ion production via double electron capture*

The relative cross sections for radioactive negative ion production via double electron capture have been measured for collisions between a 40 keV projectile beam of uranium-238 and potassium vapor. This was performed at the CRIS experiment at CERN-ISOLDE and is a step towards measuring the EAs of elements that cannot be efficiently produced in negative ion sources at radioactive ion beam (RIB) facilities. This includes short-lived radioactive isotopes that have low production quantities and elements that systematically have smaller EAs than work functions of available ion source materials. By developing negative ion production by charge exchange, we aim to make these studies feasible at RIB facilities [3].

6.4.4 *Measuring the electron affinity of polonium*

In this proposal, submitted to and accepted by the ISOLDE and neutron Time-of-Flight Experiments Committee (INTC), we applied for time to measure the EA of Po, which remains unmeasured. Po^- cannot be produced in the negative surface ion source used for previous studies of negative ions at ISOLDE as its EA is smaller than the work function of the LaB6 surface ionizer. We will instead produce Po^- by double electron capture in a charge exchange cell (CEC) available at CRIS, where we successfully have shown that negative ions (LOI-225) can be produced. The photodetachment experiment will be conducted using the GANDALPH detector, which will be placed behind CRIS. There are no previous experimental investigations of the EA of Po, while calculations indicate it to be 1.469 eV [4].

6.4.5 *Lifetimes of the 2D_J in the tin anion and isotope shift measurements*

We have measured the lifetimes of the 2D_J states in the Sn negative ion at the cryogenic storage ring, DESIREE at Stockholm University. These states have the same parity as the ground state and therefore decay mainly via a forbidden $M1$ transition meaning that the states will be long lived (10-100s for Sn^-). Hence, the transitions are extremely narrow, making high resolution experiments feasible. Furthermore, we were able to measure the isotope shift between $^{116}\text{Sn}^-$ and $^{124}\text{Sn}^-$ using a method, which to our knowledge, has never been used. This work is still in manuscript form with a follow up experiment planned in Fall 2024 [5].

6.4.6 *Trajectory effects on charge exchange and energy loss of H^+ , He^{2+} , Li^{3+} , and Be^{4+} ions colliding with atomic hydrogen*

In this work, we investigate the collision process of bare ion projectiles with $Z = 1, 2, 3,$ and 4 incident on atomic hydrogen for energies in the range 0.1 to 900 keV/u. We solve the time-dependent Schrödinger equation for the electron by implementing a Crank-Nicholson implicit method in a numerical lattice. For the projectile and target nuclei, a classical description coupled to the quantum electron is proposed to obtain the electron-nuclear dynamics within a semi-classical impact parameter approach. We complement our study with straight trajectory approach to determine the trajectory effects on charge exchange and energy loss by the projectile. The ionization process is treated by means of an absorbing masking function. We find that the charge exchange process

is independent of the trajectory for the energy regimen considered. The energy loss by the projectile, for the case of electron-nuclei dynamics, is properly accounted for by the difference of the projectile final and initial kinetic energy. However, for straight line trajectories, the energy loss by the projectile is accounted for by the electronic energy gained by the target. We find a good agreement of the energy loss cross section for the case of the coupled trajectory. However, for the straight line trajectories it overestimated the energy loss of the projectile at low collision energies, consequence of the forced linear motion. The nuclear energy loss has a large contribution at low collision energies consequence of the polarization induced by the ion on the hydrogen target. Good agreement is found with the available experimental data and other theoretical approaches [6].

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 861198.

Bibliography

- [1] Navarro-Navarrete, José E., et al. "A high-resolution measurement of the electron affinity of cesium." *Physical Review A* 109 (2024): 022812.
- [2] Ringvall-Moberg, Annie, et al. "The electron affinity of rubidium: a state selective measurement." Submitted to *Journal of Physics B* (2023): 1-7.
- [3] Nichols, M., M. Athanasakis-Kaklamanakis, et al. "Investigating radioactive negative ion production via double electron capture." In: *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B, Proceedings of the XIX International Conference on Electromagnetic Isotope Separators and Related Topics (EMIS 2022)*, IBS/RISP, Daejeon Korea, 3–7 October 2022 541 (2023): 264-267.
- [4] Nichols, M., M. Athanasakis-Kaklamanakis, et al. "Measuring the electron affinity of polonium." Proposal to the ISOLDE and Neutron Time-of-Flight Committee. January 11, 2023.
- [5] Nichols, M., Gothenburg and DESIREE collaborations, and D. Hanstorp. (List of authors not finalized). Lifetimes of the 2D_J in the tin anion and isotope shift measurements. 2024. Unpublished manuscript.
- [6] Nichols, M. and R. Cabrera-Trujillo. "Trajectory effects on charge exchange and energy loss of H^+ , He^{2+} , Li^{3+} , and Be^{4+} ions colliding with atomic hydrogen." 2024. Unpublished manuscript.

Chapter 7

Development of the IGLIS technique at KU Leuven and its application in the JetRIS and S³-LEB experiments.

Fedor Ivandikov, Arno Claessens, Rafael Ferrer, Paul Van den Bergh, Piet Van Duppen
KU Leuven, Instituut voor kern- en stralingsfysica, Leuven, Belgium

This document reports on the work performed in the course of my PhD program at KU Leuven, specifically the research I participated in as a member of the IGLIS group at Instituut voor kern- en stralingsfysica (IKS), KU Leuven, as well as my contributions and active participation in the collaborations JetRIS (GSI Helmholtzzentrum für Schwerionenforschung) and S³-LEB (GANIL)

7.1 Introduction

The work reported on in this document concerns the PhD program of ESR 7 of the LISA ITN. Specifically the following tasks, as defined in the Work Packages:

- Work Package 2, Task 3 - Optimisation of in-gas-jet laser spectroscopy for high-resolution measurement of actinides
- Work Package 2, Objective - Improve the overall efficiency of the gas cell to gain sensitivity for the shortest actinide isotopes
- Work Package 5, Task 2 - Implementation of laser ablation in gas-cell based approaches;
- Work Package 5, Task 6: Supersonic gas jet developments using specialised de Laval nozzle

7.2 IGLIS laboratory

All the experiments we report on in this document rely on the In-Gas Laser Ionisation Spectroscopy (IGLIS) technique. Here we briefly describe the basics of the technique. A more in-depth description can be found in [4, 5, 8].

A generalised schematic of an IGLIS experiment is presented in Fig. 7.1. The species of interest (this can be a molecule, an atom or an ion) is introduced into the gas cell environment via the

experiment's chosen method of production, e.g., via ablation, as a radioactive ion beam stopped in the gas or as a recoil product from an alpha radiation source. The thermalized particles are then carried by flow (extraction of ionic species may be assisted by electric fields inside the gas cell) into the laser ionisation volume. This volume may be positioned inside the gas cell, with the lasers entering through a window, for in-gas-cell operation, or downstream in a hypersonic jet, where in-gas-jet laser ionisation spectroscopy may take place. The latter of the two arrangements is required for high-resolution Resonance Ionisation Spectroscopy (RIS). The laser-ionised particles are then transported up to the detection stage through a series of Radio-Frequency Quadrupoles (RFQs), ion-optical elements and a dipole magnet for mass selection. The detector may be an ion counter, an alpha radiation detector or a specialised image-based ion detection system.

Fig. 7.1: Generalised schematic of the IGLIS method showing the gas cell, where the RIB is stopped and thermalised, the two laser steps overlapping the gas jet, the RFQs transporting the photoions and the beamline with a dipole magnet for mass separation leading to the detection stage.

The technique's versatility is exemplified in its applications, presented in this report. In-gas-cell laser spectroscopy of ²³²Th described in 7.2.1 benefited from the comparatively simpler laser alignment required for in-gas-cell operation. Resolving the hyperfine structure of ²²⁹Th, as presented in 7.2.2, was made possible by the high-resolution available in in-gas-jet mode of IGLIS. And the JetRIS experiment (7.4) utilises electric fields inside the gas cell environment for fast extraction of stopped ions.

More generally, the IGLIS technique allows us to obtain the values of nuclear moments, spins and charge radii independently of nuclear models. These measurements usually require high resolution and, in cases where production cross sections and short half-lives limit us to rates of a few atoms a second, high efficiency is similarly necessary. The IGLIS technique has been developed and optimised at KU Leuven, employing state of the art laser systems and hypersonic nozzles to meet such requirements.

7.2.1 ²³²Th level search

The latest research project worked on by the IGLIS group at Instituut voor Kern- en Stralingsfysica involved RIS studies of thorium with the final goal of demonstrating the existence of the low-lying nuclear isomer of ²²⁹Th in the singly charged ionic state (Th⁺), using its hyperfine structure to

distinguish it from the nuclear ground state.

This project began with a search for an ionisation scheme for ThII, which would allow for an efficient resonant ionisation from Th⁺ to Th²⁺. An existing scheme[6] is presented in Fig. 7.2. For the ionising step this scheme uses non-resonant two-photon transitions, a process with a comparatively small cross section. A more efficient ionisation scheme would split this step into two: a second excitation step and a final ionisation via an autoionising level (AI). Neither the second excited level, nor the AI state were present in the literature prior to this research. For this reason we undertook a level search campaign.

Fig. 7.2: The Th⁺ to Th²⁺ ionisation schemes used in these measurements. The ionisation scheme is taken from ref. [6].

The level search was conducted using ²³²Th ions produced via laser ablation inside the KU Leuven S³ type gas cell, presented in Fig. 7.3. One of the downsides of using a laser ablation source is its relatively low stability over long term. In our measurements we solve this by adjusting the energy per pulse of the ablation laser as well as continuously scanning the ablation spot over the target in a grid pattern, thus distributing the thermal load over a larger area and slowing down the formation of craters in the target surface.

Throughout the measurements performed with ²³²Th⁺ we commonly used an ablation laser scan range consisting of two points, placed roughly 3 mm apart, with the laser continuously moving between the points every 4 seconds. Ablation was performed using a pulsed Nd:YAG laser with a repetition rate of 20 Hz and a pulse energy in the range of 7-11 mJ. Laser power was attenuated

Fig. 7.3: CAD drawing of the S³ type gas cell (a) and a photo of the ²³²Th ablation target installed in the middle feedthrough of a CF-40 flange (b) with visible damage from prolonged use. The ablation laser is seen entering into the gas cell in (c) through the designated window.

through transport (losses due to reflections) by close to 50%. This setup resulted in high production rates (over 10^6 thorium atoms produced per second), that are stable within 20% over the course of a 1 hour measurement. Ablation in the gas cell environment produces thorium atoms, as well as the singly and doubly charged ions, as can be seen in the mass spectrum in Fig. 7.4.

After setting up and characterising the laser ablation source we performed an extensive level search above the second ionisation potential (IP) of ²³²Th⁺, covering over 2000 cm⁻¹ in energy and finding hundreds of peaks. This dense atomic structure can be explained by the fact that the measurements were performed in a high pressure (80 mbar) environment, where quenching from first, second and Rydberg excited states could occur through collisions with the argon buffer gas.

Fig. 7.4: Mass scan produced with the laser ablation source using a ²³²Th target

This, coupled with the high level density observed in all actinides [3], results in a complicated spectrum, as seen in Fig. 7.6.

Among the observed transitions several stand out as highly efficient ionisation paths. One of these ((99 766.87 ± 0.22) cm⁻¹) was chosen for the ionisation scheme (fig. 7.5).

Fig. 7.5: The ionisation scheme developed for Th⁺ with the newly discovered AI used in the ionising step.

These measurements were conducted using broadband dye lasers. For each of the three transitions in the ionisation scheme a Sirah Credo pulsed dye laser was set to the corresponding frequency, with the second and third step utilising frequency doubling in non-linear crystals. Throughout the scans the typical laser powers were as follows: 400 mW for the first step, 80 mW for the second step and 1100 mW for the ionising step. While the system is capable of operating at 15 kHz, in

order to extend the lifetime of the laser dyes and maximise the energy per pulse, all lasers were operated at a repetition rate of 7 kHz. According to the specification sheets [1], laser bandwidths were 0.06 cm⁻¹ for the first step and 0.08 cm⁻¹ for the second and third steps.

A secondary goal of this project was to determine the second IP of thorium with higher precision than currently available in the literature. Currently, it is estimated to be in the rang of 11.9–12.3 eV [6]. As the dense level structure in the IP region precludes the identification of a Rydberg series, we use the spectrum’s background to identify the threshold in the third step laser energy after which Th⁺ is non-resonantly ionised to Th²⁺ (Fig. 7.6), following the methodology of reference [12]. The second IP was determined to be 99248(46) cm⁻¹.

Fig. 7.6: Th⁺ spectrum in the IP region (top) and the background countrates used to calculate the second IP via threshold (bottom). The horizontal axis is shared between the graphs.

As the laser ablation source produces thorium in a range of charge states, including neutral atoms, we were able to perform RIS studies of ThI. The goal of this stage of the project was try to understand the quenching mechanisms of Rydberg series as well as more precisely determine the first IP of thorium.

Switching to neutral thorium ionisation required a different ionisation scheme. For these measurements we selected the transitions detailed in Fig. 7.7. Here, the first excitation step was taken from literature, while the ionising step utilises an AI state found in the course of this work. The lower energy of the first IP allowed for a two-step scheme to be used, which greatly simplifies laser alignment for the experiment.

With these measurements being performed in the low pressure and low temperature gas jet environment, quenching to lower levels was much less than in the gas cell for Th⁺. This would allow us to determine the first ionisation level with more precision using the Rydberg series, as opposed to observing the non-resonant ionisation threshold. Figure 7.8 shows the initial spectrum taken in the vicinity of the IP of Th I.

Fig. 7.7: The ionisation scheme used in neutral thorium measurements. Both ionisation to the AI and excitation to the Rydberg series are shown for the second step transition. The one color two step scheme present in our measurements is also shown.

Fig. 7.8: Spectra of the ThI Rydberg series taken without (top) RF shielding and after (bottom) the installation of the shield.

Notably, the levels are significantly broader than the bandwidth of the lasers we used (0.06 cm^{-1} according to specification [1]); pressure or power broadening likewise cannot account for the full width of the peaks. Our investigation attributes this broadening to Stark shifts of the atomic levels caused by the interaction between the radio-frequency (RF) electromagnetic fields induced

by the sRFQ downstream of the gas cell (see Fig. 7.8). This was confirmed by the reduction in peak width after we installed a grounded metal mesh to shield the jet region from the fields induced by the sRFQ (Fig. 7.9(b)).

This modification to the setup allowed us to resolve the Rydberg levels (Fig. 7.9(a)), which we later determined to correspond to the range of principal quantum numbers $n = 44$ to $n = 63$. By fitting the energy curve for the observed Rydberg series (Fig. 7.9(b)) we extract the Th I IP to be $50868.41(2)_{\text{stat.}}(11)_{\text{sys.}} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ or $(6.306\,879 \pm 0.000\,014) \text{ eV}$ (1σ uncertainty) [4]. The precise ionisation mechanism as well as a more detailed description of the experiment will be available in a later publication.

Fig. 7.9: The shielding mesh installed in the jet region, preventing field penetration from the sRFQ.

Aside from providing us with a more precise value for the IP of thorium, this measurement serves as the first example of ionisation via excitation to a Rydberg state in the gas jet environment. This mechanism will prove useful for other RIS studies of elements where no known AI state is present in literature (e.g. Ag, No [3] etc.), as transitions to a Rydberg level have cross sections usually two orders of magnitude larger than non-resonant ionisation, making it the default method for such studies.

7.2.2 ²²⁹Th low-lying nuclear isomer

After developing an efficient three-step resonant laser ionisation scheme using the readily available natural thorium isotope we switched to RIS studies of ²²⁹Th. The final goal of this project was to obtain the hyperfine spectrum of the low-lying nuclear isomer of ²²⁹Th. This isomer is of particular interest, as the isomer's low energy of $E_{\text{IS}} = (8.355\,74 \pm 0.000\,03) \text{ eV}$ [15, 7] and long radiative half-life of around 600 s in CaF₂ [15] make it the only currently known candidate for an optical frequency standard that would utilise a transition within the nucleus. This new type of device, a nuclear clock, would have applications in both fundamental research (time variations in physical constants, the search for dark matter) and, more generally, metrology [14].

The first task in this study was to exchange the gas cell laser ablation source producing ²³²Th for a fast extraction gas cell equipped with a ²³³U recoil source. Both the isomeric and ground states of ²²⁹Th are produced, with the branching ratios of 2% and 98% respectively. Figure 7.10(bottom) presents a mass spectrum produced with the new configuration of the setup. Additionally, RIS measurements of the isomer are complicated by the isomer’s short half-life in neutral thorium, as well as in the singly charged ion: the isomer’s energy is close enough to the binding energy of thorium’s outer electrons, which reduces the isomer’s life-time by increasing the probability of internal conversion decay. For the atomic ground state the half-life is 7 μs [13], which is too short for in-gas-jet spectroscopy. This half-life in a singly charged ion is cited to be longer than 10 ms[13], which makes RIS measurements possible, if extraction time from the gas cell is reduced. For this purpose we used the Fast Gas Cell [16], depicted in Fig. 7.10(top). Here, the recoil source is placed in a narrow channel, allowing for evacuation via gas flow in approximately 1 ms.

Fig. 7.10: CAD drawing of the fast extraction gas cell used in ²²⁹Th measurements (top) and the mass spectrum produced by the recoil sources (bottom).

These measurements were conducted using a narrowband laser system composed of a pulsed dye amplifier pumped by a single longitudinal mode Nd:YAG pump laser at 532 nm and 20 kHz maximum repetition rate, and a continuous wave diode laser as the seeding source. This setup allows for high-resolution laser spectroscopy capable of resolving the ²²⁹Th hyperfine structure. A more detailed examination of the system’s capabilities can be found in Ref. [17].

With the system prepared for ²²⁹Th studies, we performed the first measurements with neutral thorium as a benchmark of the system’s performance (fig. 7.11). The graph shows signs of power broadening, with the achieved peak width of 1.2 GHz still above the resolution expected from the narrowband laser system. In a future publication we will present a higher resolution spectrum.

Having benchmarked the system’s performance on neutral thorium we set the system up for RIS studies of ²²⁹Th in its ionic state. Unfortunately, due to difficulties relating to low countrate (on the order of 800 counts/s of Th⁺), aligning three lasers with the entire length of the gas jet and the Th²⁺ background from the recoil source, a conclusive result could not be obtained.

Fig. 7.11: A spectrum of the ²²⁹Th hyperfine structure obtained by in-gas-jet laser spectroscopy using the narrowband laser system. The horizontal axis is the wavenumber of the first excitation step in cm⁻¹.

7.3 IGLIS studies at S³-LEB

While the IGLIS lab at IKS is used for development and optimisation of the IGLIS technique, S³-LEB is one of the online facilities in which IGLIS and in particular in-gas-jet laser spectroscopy will be applied for the production and study of RIBs. This system’s basic function is the same as the setup at IKS with the only differences being the beamline upstream of the sRFQ.

During online operation S3-LEB accepts recoils produced in-flight at SPIRAL2 through a thin entrance window which serves to preserve the vacuum in the S3 beamline while assuring a high buffer gas pressure in the gas cell to stop and thermalize the highly-charged beam from the accelerator. The ions are then fully stopped, neutralised and thermalized in the high pressure (60-500 mbar) argon gas inside the gas cell, from where from the nuclear reaction products are transported by gas flow. Once in the ionisation region, which can be located either inside the gas cell for broadband laser spectroscopy studies or downstream past the nozzle in the low pressure jet chamber, the excitation and ionisation lasers overlap the gas jet, where narrowband laser spectroscopy can be performed. The photoions are subsequently transported by two RFQ ion guides and a Quadrupole Mass Filter (QMF) to the helium-filled cooler-buncher, where the continuous stream of ions is converted into ion bunches to be accelerated to 2 keV and mass separated in the multi-reflection time of flight (MRTof) spectrometer PILGRIM. Finally, the photoions are detected using a MagneToF ion detector. Figure 8.1 features the S3-LEB setup (a) and the laser ionisation scheme of erbium (b) used in this work.

In addition to online operation, where the species of interest is supplied by SPIRAL2 through the entrance window, S3-LEB is capable of offline operation. In this configuration the investigated species can be produced by laser ablation or, as is the case for the measurements described in this report, via evaporation from a filament.

In a recent publication [2] the offline characterisation of S3-LEB is reported on. Conversely to

Fig. 7.12: Schematic of the S³-LEB setup (a) and the erbium laser ionization scheme (b) used in the measurements conducted in [2] and in the current experimental campaign.

the results of [5], where a Mach number of 8.5 was observed in the jet, the resolution attained at S³-LEB was 268 MHz, which indicates a jet with Mach number 4.5. In this study we aim to establish the cause of this underperformance and attempt to achieve the gas jet conditions necessary for high-resolution laser ionisation spectroscopy in S³-LEB.

In the context of this study we consider a gas jet's Mach number to be the local value averaged over a length of 55 mm. In the case of reference [2] the averaging is due to the particular way the spectra were obtained: here, a 55 mm length of the jet is illuminated simultaneously. In the case of our measurements, the jet is sequentially illuminated at different points along the jet axis, producing multiple spectra in different local conditions. From this we calculate the Mach number distribution, the final value is averaged over the first 55 mm of the jet. We refer to this measurement technique as RIS Flow Mapping[5].

A typical RIS flow mapping measurement consists of the following steps: the frequency of one of the laser steps is scanned over the resonance, then the lasers are spatially shifted to move the illuminated volume. These steps are then repeated for a given range of locations, in our case that is the length of the gas jet. The acquired spectra are then analysed to determine how the shape and position of the resonance varies for different points of the jet, producing a spatial distribution of the jet's temperature, velocity (and, correspondingly, the Mach number) and relatively density. An example of such distributions is given in Fig. 7.13.

As in [2], we used the two step laser ionization scheme of Er reported in [11]. The wavelengths of the transitions are given in Fig.8.1.

7.3.1 Improving S³-LEB in-gas-jet resolution

We consider the most likely reason for the system's low resolution to be poor jet formation. As the gas jet leaves the nozzle, it propagates through the vacuum chamber. If the pressure in the jet is lower than the surrounding pressure, the jet collapses and shock waves form. An opposite scenario, where the jet pressure is higher than the background pressure, is also possible, this leads

Fig. 7.13: Example of a laser ionisation spectrum acquired during RIS flow mapping measurements, horizontal axis is in MHz (left), spatial distributions of the FWHM, Mach number and transition centroids along the jet axis for the three isotopes investigated (¹⁶⁶Er, ¹⁶⁸Er and ¹⁷⁰Er), Er_{avg} is the average value for all three isotopes.

to jet underexpansion. For the formation of a collimated jet the pressure at the exit plane of the nozzle (P_{jet}) must be matched to the background pressure in the jet chamber (P_{bg}). Due to the difficulty of measuring P_{jet} , we instead calculate the ratio between stagnation pressure (P_0) and jet chamber pressure inherent to the nozzle used in these measurements:

$$P_0 = 2970 \times P_{bg} \quad (7.1)$$

As shown in Fig. 7.14, straying from the optimal pressure in the jet chamber for a given stagnation pressure will result in either the jet collapsing (overexpansion) or dispersing into an uncollimated stream of gas (underexpansion).

The S3-LEB experimental setup is equipped with pressure gauges measuring both the stagnation and background pressures (Fig. 7.15), however the validity of the gauges' readouts was put into question after repeated measurements not resulting in the expected gas jet conditions, such as those shown in Fig. 7.14. Thus, both pressure gauges were investigated as part of this experimental campaign.

To verify that the pressure gauge in the jet chamber produces correct readings, we conducted a series of measurements at different flow rates of argon and compared the results to the performance curve of the vacuum pump (Fig. 7.16). From this measurement it followed that a calibration coefficient of 0.78 should be used for the pressure readout of the jet chamber pressure gauge.

The pressure inside the gas cell was measured using a transducer installed upstream of the gas cell in the gas distribution system. According to simplified calculations of conductance, the length of the gas line from the gauge to the gas cell introduces an offset of approximately 10 mbar to the readout of the pressure gauge. This value was later refined to 4.67 mbar for $P_0 = 300$ mbar by simulations. In addition to the pressure drop due to conductance, stagnation pressure measurements were complicated by the limited resolution of the pressure gauge (10 mbar). To remedy this, we took a calibration curve of P_0 vs argon flow rate over a wide range of pressures and used the superior precision of the flow meter to set the stagnation pressure.

With these corrections to the pressure readings we could set the argon flow rate and jet chamber

Fig. 7.14: Examples of different flow matching conditions with the optimal matching outlined in green. Figure taken from [5].

pumping speed to values corresponding to optimal flow matching, as measured in [5]. The pressure conditions used in [2] were set to $P_0 = 300$ mbar and $P_{bg} = 0.125$ mbar, which does not correspond to the optimal ratio of $\frac{P_0}{P_{bg}} = 2960$, obtained in [5].

In the scope of this experimental campaign we have tested a range of conditions with RIS flow mapping and found the best flow matching to be achieved at $P_0^* = 300$ mbar and $P_{bg}^* = 0.08$ mbar. After applying the aforementioned corrections to the pressure gauges' readouts ($P_0 = 295.33$

Fig. 7.15: Positions of the stagnation pressure (P_0) and the jet chamber pressure (P_{bg}) gauges.

mbar, $P_{bg} = 0.11$ mbar), this results in a pressure ratio of $\frac{P_0}{P_{bg}} = 2784$. This ratio is closer to the optimal value of $\frac{P_0}{P_{bg}} = 2960$, than the one used in [2]. The remaining discrepancy can be explained by the lacking accuracy of the pressure measurements.

In addition to the aforementioned investigations, the possibility of the nozzle being damaged was considered. This was tested simply by replacing the nozzle with an identical one. The replacement led to no change in performance, thus the possibility of a surface defect or other forms of damage in the nozzle can be eliminated.

After implementing all the improvements mentioned in here, we observed an increase in resolution, compared to that obtained in [2]. Below in Table 7.1 we list the resolution (averaged over ^{166}Er , ^{168}Er and ^{170}Er), jet temperature and Mach number for a stagnation pressure of $P_0 = 300$ mbar and a background pressure of $P_{bg} = 0.0466$ mbar. These pressures were picked as the Mach number distribution along the jet is the closest to optimal conditions of all measurements performed during this campaign.

Table 7.1: Comparison between the resolution and jet parameters achieved in this work and in [2].

	This work	Results from [2]
Full width at half maximum	206(2) MHz	268(5) MHz
Jet temperature	23.6(5) K	46(2) K
Mach number	6.8(1)	4.5(3)

The performance of the system is still below the design specifications of the nozzle ($M = 8.5$). This behaviour can be attributed to the still incomplete match between stagnation and jet chamber pressures P_0 and P_{bg} . In the future we plan to replace the pressure gauges used to measure these values, moving the gas cell pressure gauge closer to the gas cell itself and calibrating the jet chamber pressure gauge.

Fig. 7.16: Comparison between the pumping curve (blue data points) taken from the pump manufacturer’s website and the readout of the pressure gauge in the jet chamber (red curve); the green curve shows the curve after the gauge readout is adjusted by the new calibration factor.

Another potential cause for the low Mach number observed in the measurements could be argon gas nucleation, as described in [5]. An investigation of the effect of heating the gas cell on jet formation should be conducted in the future.

7.4 Simulation-aided optimisation of the JetRIS apparatus

In addition to work in the IGLIS lab at Instituut voor Kern- en Stralingsfysica and S³-LEB at GANIL, the PhD program includes active participation in the JetRIS collaboration. The JetRIS experiment is an application of in-gas-jet laser spectroscopy for short-lived heavy elements used at the GSI Helmholtzzentrum für Schwerionenforschung accelerator facility.

A schematic of the apparatus is presented in Fig. 7.17[10]. A JetRIS measurement includes the gas cell accepting a RIB through the entrance window (titanium or mylar foil of thickness in the range of several micrometers), thermalising the incoming ions in the high pressure (80 mbar) gas cell environment. The ions are then transported from the stopping volume via electric fields to the hot filament placed on a negative electric potential, where the ions are adsorbed and neutralised on the surface. The filament’s high temperature (in excess of 1000 °C) then serves to promptly desorb the neutral atoms in the filament channel, from where they are transported through the

hypersonic nozzle into the low-pressure and low-temperature environment of the gas jet. In the gas jet resonant laser ionisation is used to selectively ionise the evaporated neutrals, allowing for their transport to a PIPS detector downstream via a 90 degree bent RFQ ion guide. The detection stage relies on alpha decay detection to separate the species of interest from background ions, resulting in an exceptionally high signal to noise ratio.

Fig. 7.17: CAD drawing of the JetRIS experiment. Highlighted in green are the recoil source and its mount, located in the stopping volume. The six cage and five funnel electrodes are used to accelerate and focus the ions into the filament channel, which is terminated with the hypersonic nozzle. After extraction from the nozzle into the gas jet the ions are illuminated transversely with the two laser steps. The resulting photoions are then transported to the PIPS detector via a bent RFQ.

The setup had its second beamtime in 2022 performing RIS studies on ²⁵⁴No. The measurements were successful (fig. 7.18), producing a laser ionisation spectrum of nobelium with higher resolution than was previously available in the literature. A further improvement in resolution is within reach, as the obtained spectrum was noticeably power broadened. A full report on the 2022 JetRIS beamtime can be found in [9].

Despite the overall success of the online experiment, the system showed an unexpectedly low

Fig. 7.18: The laser ionisation spectra of nobelium produced in the RADRIS (RIS in gas cell, red curve) and JetRIS (in-gas-jet RIS, black curve, counts x100) experiments. Figure taken from [9].

transport efficiency, requiring long measurement times. For this reason we began an optimisation campaign of JetRIS comprising offline measurements with recoil sources as well as numerical simulations, which would facilitate obtaining a deeper understanding of the system’s operation and pinpoint the bottlenecks in efficiency.

The simulation part of the optimisation campaign was divided into several stages. The first goal was to construct a model of the experiment in online conditions, achieving agreement between experimentally observed and simulated efficiency values. Following that we would modify the model to reflect JetRIS in its offline configuration, allowing us to compare the simulation’s performance to the physical setup in a wider range of configuration available for recoil source measurements. Lastly, we would optimise the JetRIS gas cell for improved efficiency, relying on the verified simulation model to guide the optimisation.

7.4.1 Numerical model of JetRIS

COMSOL Multiphysics was chosen as the simulation environment for this project, with additional Stopping Ranges In Matter (SRIM) calculations used as boundary conditions in the COMSOL model. The simulation models the gas cell, starting with transport from the stopping volume to the filament and ending with the evaporated electrically neutral atoms crossing into the hypersonic

nozzle. We consider gas flow transport within the nozzle and in the gas jet to be adequately described by the specialised simulation software HYPENOZ, developed by Von Karman Institute. Ion extraction from the gas jet via RFQ is considered independent from transport in the gas cell, RFQ efficiency and evacuation time have been measured experimentally to be 80% and 600 microseconds respectively.

The COMSOL model utilises four physics interfaces linked together with three couplings: a laminar flow module in conjunction with heat exchange in fluids are used to calculate the gas flow field in the model. This flow, along with an electrostatic field, affect the ionic and atomic transport of the species of interest through the gas cell. A steady-state calculation of the diluted species (²⁵⁴No in the case of the online experiment) concentration field that is affected by convection, diffusion and ion migration in electric fields is the final output of the simulation. An example of concentration fields for the No⁺ ion is given in Fig. 7.19.

Fig. 7.19: Example output of the COMSOL model of JetRIS, showing the concentration of nobelium ions in the gas cell. The ions are extracted from the stopping volume with the cage and funnel electrodes and guided to the filament. Labels C1 - C5 denote the cage electrodes, labels F1, F5 denote the funnel electrodes.

We can use the gradients of these concentration fields to calculate flux through a given surface. The system's ion efficiency is defined as the ratio of flux through the filament surface to the total flux of No⁺ ions entering the gas cell. Similarly, gas cell extraction efficiency is the ratio of neutral nobelium flux through the nozzle boundary to the total flux of No⁺ ions entering the gas cell. In order to compare efficiency values obtained in the simulation to online experimental values, we have to account for the efficiencies of detection (50%), laser ionisation (8.4%) and RFQ extraction

(80%). Table 7.5 lists the final values obtained through these calculations.

7.4.2 Offline benchmarking of the simulation model

After testing and refining the simulation model in the online conditions used for the nobelium measurements we conducted a series of online measurements to benchmark the model’s performance in a wider range of conditions, in particular by changing the electric field configuration and the pressure in the gas cell. The measurements were performed with the use of an ²²⁵Ac recoil source producing ²²¹Fr recoils, whose alpha decay was observed on an PIPS detector downstream of the gas jet. The system was in the flushing configuration, where the ions would not be neutralised on the filament and evaporated as atoms. The filament was removed from the gas cell and ions would be allowed to pass through the nozzle, guided at first to the filament channel via electric fields and from there by gas flow to the nozzle.

Varying electrode potentials

The first test comprised raising the potential on the last electrode before the filament in an attempt to establish the voltage at which the ions travelling through the gas cell would no longer be able to overcome the potential barrier. The measurement results are presented in Fig. 7.20 and the observed trend is in agreement with the simulation.

Following that, we tested ion transport efficiency for different values of potential gradient between the cage electrodes. The role of such a gradient in the apparatus is to accelerate the ions towards the funnel electrodes, where the ion cloud is shaped into the narrow filament channel. We tested three different potential configurations, the results can be found in Table 7.2.

Cage 1	Cage 6	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	$\epsilon_{sim}(K_{Cs})$	$\epsilon_{exp}(Fr - 221)$	$\epsilon_{sim}(K_{Xe})$	$\epsilon_{exp}(Rn - 219)$
200	130	130	60	45	45	30	25.8%	23.5%	26.0%	2.6%
98	95.5	95	80	65	50	35	33.6%	12.3%	33.6%	0.0%
106	97	95	80	65	50	35	32.9%	23.6%	33.0%	0.6%

Table 7.2: Efficiency measurements with different potential sets, performed with the Ac-225 and Ra-223 recoil sources and simulated with the mobilities of the corresponding homologues - K_{Cs} for Fr-221 recoils and K_{Xe} for Rn-219 recoils. All potentials are given in units of V.

Here, the simulation results differ from the experiment both for the ²²¹Ac source used in these measurements and for the ²²³Ra source used previously. We explain this discrepancy as being due to phenomena unaccounted for in the simulation. There are two effects at play, both of which decrease efficiency inversely proportionally to extraction time. Firstly, the recoil species for the Ra-223 source is Rn-219, which has a half-life of 4 s. Extraction time is heavily dependent on the cage potentials, both their values relative to the funnel electrode potentials and the potential gradient in the cage itself. The first set of potentials listed in table 7.2 produces an extraction time of ~ 200 ms, extraction with flow alone (all electrodes grounded) is on the order of 30 s, while constant potentials for cages 1-6 net an extraction time of 900 ms. This last extraction time is comparable to the half-life of radon and decreases sharply as the cage potential gradient is increased. Figure 7.21 shows the simulated efficiencies for various cage gradients, the extraction times for these configurations, as well as a new metric - species survival. This value is a convolution of extraction efficiency and spontaneous decay distributions in time, so for an infinitely fast extraction or for a stable species survival would be equal to the simulated transport efficiency. The graph shows that factoring

Fig. 7.20: Experimental and simulated efficiencies as functions of funnel 5 potential

radon's prompt decay into the efficiency calculation results in higher efficiencies with a potential gradient in the cage.

The second effect decreasing efficiencies is in-flight neutralization, which is especially noticeable in potential configurations which result in long extraction times. The current campaign uses an Ac-225 source, whose recoils are francium ions, for which charge exchange with argon is mostly negligible, however the radon species used in previous measurements has a much closer ionization potential to argon, resulting in higher losses during transport due to radon neutralization. This phenomenon would further lower the efficiency for system configurations with slow extraction, moving the peak on the species survival line in Fig. 7.21 to higher cage gradients.

Fig. 7.21: Efficiency and timing as simulated for Rn-219 recoils. The green line is the simulated efficiency, without accounting for in-flight decay, the black line is the "survival" - efficiency adjusted for a 4s half-life, the red line is the extraction time. The horizontal axis is the cage potential gradient in V per cage electrode.

Lastly, it should be noted that all measurements with the ²²³Ra source show a much lower efficiency than those with the ²²¹Ac source. This is attributed to the ²¹⁹Rn recoils not sticking to the PIPS detector and decaying somewhere in the detector chamber, thus not contributing to the signal.

The measurements carried out in the current campaign with francium recoils agree with the simulations in that efficient transport is possible with a much shallower gradient than used normally (comparing potential sets 1 and 3). There is, however, a discrepancy between the simulated and measured efficiencies for potential set 2, suggesting that another extraction time-related effect is at play, meaning that the species survival graph from Fig. 7.21 would have a peak at some cage potential gradient higher than that suggested by the 5 min half-life of Fr-221. Further measurements could be used to estimate the lifetime of these processes.

Ion mobility

In the COMSOL model the ion mobility used is that of francium's homologue, cesium. The exact value is $19.92 \frac{cm^2}{Vs}$ [18]. The diffusion coefficient is calculated using the Nerst-Einstein relation:

$$D_{Cs} = \frac{K_{Cs} k_B T}{e} \quad (7.2)$$

Where K_{Cs} is the mobility of cesium in units of $\frac{cm^2}{Vs}$, k_B is the Boltzmann constant in $\frac{J}{K}$, T is the temperature of the gas in Kelvins and e is the elementary charge in Coulombs. The resulting diffusion coefficient is $D_{Cs} = 0.51 \frac{cm^2}{s}$

In order to benchmark ion mobility, measurements at different stagnation pressures P_0 (pressure

in the gas cell) were carried out. From theory, mobility is inversely proportional to number density (and thus to pressure): $K(p, T) = K_0 \frac{1\text{bar}}{P_0} \frac{T_0}{273K}$

And thus rough proportions for efficiency and extraction time can be inferred:

$$\varepsilon \propto P_0 \tag{7.3}$$

$$t_{ext} \propto \frac{1}{P_0} \tag{7.4}$$

P_0	120	100	80	60	40
ε_{sim}	29.7%	27.7%	24.3%	19.1%	12.9%
t_{sim}, ms	223	212	194	153	59
P ratio	0.67	0.80	1.00	1.33	2.00
ε_{sim} ratio	0.82	0.88	1.00	1.27	1.89
t_{sim} ratio	0.87	0.92	1.00	1.26	3.28
ε_{exp}	34.8%	28.2%	24.6%		11.8%
ε_{exp} ratio	0.71	0.87	1.00		2.08

Table 7.3: Measurement and simulation results for different stagnation (in-gas-cell) pressures P_0 . ε is the efficiency and t is the extraction time. The subscript *sim* denotes results of the simulation, while experimental measurements are denoted as *exp*. The values suffixed with "ratio" are the ratios of a given parameter to the value of this parameter at the standard pressure of 80 mbar, e.g. the ε_{sim} line contains the ratios of simulated efficiencies at different pressures to the simulated efficiency at 80 mbar.

Table 7.3 lists the simulated values for efficiency and the ratios of 80 mbar/ P_0 , $\varepsilon_{80\text{ mbar}}/\varepsilon_{P_0}$, $t_{80\text{ mbar}}/t_{P_0}$. The last two lines in the table list efficiency values obtained from the experiment and the same ratios calculated for these efficiencies. Experimental and simulated efficiencies are plotted in Fig. 7.22.

Both in the experiment and in the COMSOL model the cage and funnel potentials were set to the following values:

Shield	Cage 1	Cage 6	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
192	200	130	90	75	60	45	30

Table 7.4: The potentials for cage, funnel and shield electrodes used in the mobility benchmarking measurements. All values are in units of V.

Fig. 7.22: Simulated and experimental efficiencies at different pressures. No experimental data point at 60 mbar was taken.

Agreement is observed between the simulated efficiencies and those calculated from the experiment. This suggests that the COMSOL model correctly reflects ion transport in the real system, at least in flushing mode (no filament, ions transported through the nozzle).

7.4.3 Optimising JetRIS

With the simulation veracity proven, we could use the model to consider the operation of JetRIS from a new viewpoint. Experimentally, the only available data are the efficiency and extraction time. While in the simulation we can observe the entire concentration field, fluxes through every surface of the gas cell and their evolution in time. Careful consideration of those parameters has led to the following conclusions:

1. The stopping volume is oversized
2. The filament's negative potential is chiefly responsible for focusing the ions to a single point, not the funnel
3. The ions and the neutrals travel in their respective parts of the setup at approximately 1 mm/ms

Considering these three points, we developed a new approach to JetRIS. Since the filament's potential alone is enough to focus the ions, we can remove the funnel electrodes, shortening the entire system. This improves transport times in the gas cell. Secondly, we will place the filament more prominently in the gas cell, just outside the filament channel. This drastically increases ion transport efficiency, but delays neutral extraction, as the flow outside the filament channel is significantly slower. The extraction time can be brought back to the previously achieved values by swapping the previously used conical channel for a narrower geometry. Lastly, we will modify the cage electrodes, extending the last one to cover the grounded front flange from the view of ions in the stopping volume. This modification improves ion transport efficiency by more clearly defining the potential near the filament channel. The proposed modified geometry is presented in Fig. 7.23.

Fig. 7.23: Shortened gas cell geometry of JetRIS. The entrance window is shaded in dark green, the two cage electrodes are in light green, filament channel is in orange. The dimensions of this geometry are given in the figure. For comparison, the design used in the online experiment features a total length of 210 mm from the entrance window to the filament channel. The filament channel previously used had a length of 40 mm.

Simulations show these optimisations as a step in the right direction, offering a significant improvement in both efficiency and transport times. The latter is particularly important, as the volume phenomena in the gas cell are still not accounted for in the model, and their impact on efficiency seems to be linearly dependent on transport time. A comparison between the simulated performance of the setup in the configuration used in the 2022 beamtime and the modified setup with no funnel are presented in Table 7.5.

	Beamtime geometry	No funnel
Ion efficiency	11%	68%
Neutral efficiency	6%	66%
Ion ext. time	87 ms	33 ms
Neutral ext. time	103 ms	44 ms

Table 7.5: Comparison between the efficiencies and extraction times for the previous and improved geometries of the gas cell. For ions the extraction time is considered to be the average travel time to the filament, whereas neutral extraction time includes ion travel time to the filament and the time an evaporated atom takes to enter the nozzle, guided by flow.

Before the JetRIS beamtime in 2025 we hope to have machined the necessary parts and implemented these changes. Testing them with a recoil source will inform our decisions on future modifications. If the improvement observed in the simulations is confirmed experimentally, the range of isotopes available for study with JetRIS will be expanded to regions with even shorter half-lives and smaller production cross sections.

7.5 Conclusions

In summary, in this document we report on the progress achieved in the first two years of the PhD program of LISA ITN’s ESR 7. The program includes work on the projects undertaken by

the IGLIS group of KU Leuven, the JetRIS experiment at GSI and participation in the S³-LEB collaboration at GANIL.

In this time the laser spectroscopy group at KU Leuven has completed a comprehensive level search of ThI and ThII, finding atomic levels which have been used to improve existing ionisation schemes for higher efficiency. The first and second ionisation potentials of thorium have been determined with higher precision than previously available in the literature. Additionally the hyperfine structure of ²²⁹Th has been observed using in-gas-jet RIS using KU Leuven’s state of the art hypersonic nozzle and narrowband laser system.

The unexpectedly low resolution observed in spectra obtained at S³-LEB during the offline commissioning run has been investigated as part of the PhD program. We report on the modifications to the system’s operating pressures and the obtained significantly improved spectral resolution.

Numerical simulations of JetRIS have been used to obtain insight into the system’s operation and locate the reason for the experiment’s low efficiency in the 2022 online experiment. A COMSOL simulation model of the setup has been created and experimentally verified using an alpha recoil source of ²²¹Ac. Subsequently the numerical model has been employed to design an optimised gas cell geometry, which should allow for faster extraction times with increased efficiency. Offline development and characterisation of the modified setup are planned in the near future.

Bibliography

- [1] Datasheet credo dye laser. manual, Sirah Lasertechnik, 2021.
- [2] Anjali Ajayakumar et al. In-gas-jet laser spectroscopy with S³-LEB. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 539(3):102–107, 2023.
- [3] Michael Block et al. Recent progress in laser spectroscopy of the actinides. *Progress in Particle and Nuclear Physics*, 116:103834, 1 2021.
- [4] A. Claessens. *Laser ionization spectroscopy of ²⁵⁴No and ²²⁹Th in hypersonic gas jets*. PhD thesis, KU Leuven, 2024.
- [5] R. Ferrer et al. Hypersonic nozzle for laser-spectroscopy studies at 17 K characterized by resonance-ionization-spectroscopy-based flow mapping. *Physical Review Research*, 3(4):043041, 10 2021.
- [6] O. A. Herrera-Sancho et al. Energy levels of Th⁺ between 7.3 and 8.3 eV. *Physical Review A - Atomic, Molecular, and Optical Physics*, 88(1):1–7, 2013.
- [7] Sandro Kraemer et al. Observation of the radiative decay of the ^{229m}Th nuclear clock isomer. *Nature*, 617(7962):706–710, 2023.
- [8] Yu Kudryavtsev, R. Ferrer, M. Huyse, P. Van den Bergh, and P. Van Duppen. The in-gas-jet laser ion source: Resonance ionization spectroscopy of radioactive atoms in supersonic gas jets. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 297:7–22, 2 2013.
- [9] Jeremy Lantis, Arno Claessens, et al. *Physical Review Research*, 2024.

- [10] S. Raeder, M. Block, P. Chhetri, R. Ferrer, S. Kraemer, T. Kron, M. Laatiaoui, S. Nothhelfer, F. Schneider, P. Van Duppen, M. Verlinde, E. Verstraelen, Th Walther, and A. Zadvornaya. A gas-jet apparatus for high-resolution laser spectroscopy on the heaviest elements at SHIP. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 463:272–276, 5 2019.
- [11] Jekabs Romans et al. High-resolution laser system for the S³ -Low Energy Branch. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 536(December 2022):72–81, 3 2023.
- [12] S. Rothe. *An all-solid state laser system for the laser ion source RILIS and in-source laser spectroscopy of astatine at ISOLDE/CERN*. PhD thesis, JGU Mainz, 2012.
- [13] Benedict Seiferle, Lars von der Wense, and Peter G. Thirolf. Lifetime measurement of the 229m-th nuclear isomer. *Physical Review Letters*, 118(4):042501, 1 2017.
- [14] Peter G. Thirolf et al. The thorium isomer 229m-th: review of status and perspectives after more than 50 years of research. *EPJ Special Topics*, 123, 2024.
- [15] J Tiedau, M V Okhupkin, K Zhang, J Thielking, G Zitzer, and E Peik. Laser Excitation of the Th-229 Nucleus. *Physical Review Letters*, 132(18):182501, 2024.
- [16] M. Verlinde. *Towards the In-Gas-Jet Laser Ionization Spectroscopy of the ²²⁹Th Isomer*. PhD thesis, KU Leuven, 2021.
- [17] M Verlinde et al. Single-longitudinal-mode pumped pulsed-dye amplifier for high-resolution laser spectroscopy. *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 91(10):103002, 10 2020.
- [18] L. A. Viehland and C. C. Kirkpatrick. *Viehland database*. www.lxcat.net, retrieved on November 10, 2023, originally compiled in, 1995.

Chapter 8

In gas jet laser spectroscopy optimization for high resolution measurement of actinides

Anjali Ajayakumar^a, Lucia Caceres^a, Wenling Dong^e, Serge Franchoo^e, Sarina Geldhof^a, Nathalie Lecesne^a, Vladimir Manea^e, Jekabs Romans^d, Antoine de Roubin^c, Herve Savajols^a and the S³-LEB collaboration

^a GANIL, CEA/DRF-CNRS/IN2P3, B.P. 55027, 14076 Caen, France

^b IRFU, CEA, Université Paris-Saclay, F-91191 Gif sur Yvette, France

^c Normandie Université, ENSICAEN, UNICAEN, CNRS/IN2P3, LPC Caen, F-14000 Caen, France

^d KU Leuven, Instituut voor Kern- en Stralingsfysica, B-3001 Leuven, Belgium

^e IJC Lab, Université Paris-Saclay, CNRS/IN2P3, IJCLab, 91405 Orsay, France

This contribution presents offline commissioning experiments and results of the Super Separator Spectrometer-Low Energy Branch (S³-LEB) setup. S³-LEB is a low-energy radioactive ion beam facility, which will be employed for the study of exotic nuclei, under commissioning as a part of the GANIL-SPIRAL2 facility. For the offline commissioning of the S³-LEB set-up with laser ionization and spectroscopy, a gas cell based technique called in-gas jet laser spectroscopy was implemented which aims to provide the optimum resolution. Technical development including implementation of a narrowband cw Ti:sapphire laser for in-jet laser spectroscopy was implemented as a part of this work. The first laser spectroscopy results with the coupling of a buffer gas cell to the system is reported. For the commissioning tests, a tantalum filament was installed in the gas cell for the production of stable isotopes of Er, ¹⁵²Er being one of the online experiments foreseen. Characterization of the Er ions in the gas cell and jet has been performed to obtain the minimum possible spectral resolution and maximum ionization efficiency.

8.1 Introduction

The S³-LEB setup is a part of the GANIL-SPIRAL2 facility. The main highlights of the S³-LEB setup are its efficiency in studying nuclei of very low cross-sections owing to high-intensity primary beams available from SPIRAL2, its *Z*-selectivity due to resonant laser ionization technique, mass selectivity provided by the mass separator coupled to it with a mass resolving power in the order of 10⁵ and its achievable spectral resolution down to the order of 200 MHz due to in-gas-jet laser-atom

interaction.

In online conditions at SPIRAL2, the ion beam produced and selected by S^3 will enter a gas cell through a titanium or Mylar entrance window of a few micrometers thickness. The gas cell will be filled with ultrapure argon buffer gas under constant flow, reaching a pressure of 200 - 500 mbar for efficient stopping of the atoms. The entrance window will separate the vacuum region of S^3 from the higher-pressure region of the gas cell. The radioactive ions reaching the gas cell will stop in the buffer gas cell, thermalize, and neutralize in the buffer gas. The neutralized ions will then be flushed out of the gas cell along with the buffer gas to form a gas jet. The lasers will interact with the atoms either in the gas cell or in the gas jet to ionize the neutralized species with Z -selectivity via resonant laser ionization. The ions are then transported through a series of radio-frequency quadrupoles (RFQs) to detection setups such as MCPs placed at different stages of the RFQs or to an MR-TOF-MS for mass purification and mass measurements. A deflector can then bend the purified ions to future experimental setups such as the decay station, SEASON, or DESIR facility. The layout of S^3 -LEB setup is shown in Figure 8.1. Thus S^3 -LEB project form a part of the LISA_ITN collaboration with its capabilities to laser ionize and perform spectroscopy on the actinides. A major part of the offline laser spectroscopy commissioning and characterization of the setup was performed in the context of the LISA_ITN.

Fig. 8.1: Layout of S^3 -LEB setup is shown, *a)* shows the applied laser scheme for resonance ionization of the erbium atoms and *b)* zoom of the gas jet portion in the setup with λ_1 and λ_2 indicating the first step and second step laser paths.

8.2 Milestones

The first milestone related to the project was the development, implementation and characterization of Ti:sapphire based laser systems for broad band and narrowband laser spectroscopy within the gas cell and gas jet respectively. A narrowband, injection-locked titanium sapphire laser was installed to perform high-resolution laser spectroscopy with the S^3 -LEB experiment at SPIRAL2. The laser system was implemented, optimized and characterized, then used for proof-of-principle measurements of the hyperfine structure of stable ^{167}Er in an atomic beam unit as well as in the S^3 -LEB setup[4]. An external cavity diode laser was used for seeding the injection-locked cavity. The deliverable report detailing the developments is available in [6]. In order to improve the the wavelength tunability of the injection locked laser system, a diode pumped continuous wave

Ti:sapphire laser system was also constructed and characterized. Details about its implementation and progress is presented in [7].

The second milestone was to perform the first high resolution laser spectroscopy measurements as a part of the offline commissioning tests carried out with S³-LEB set-up. The results of Er spectroscopy shows proof of concept of the technique. The resonance peak scans from the in-gas-jet spectroscopy for the stable Er isotopes are shown in Figure 8.2. In gas cell and gas jet ionization with S³-LEB set up was studied in detail allowing us to validate its performance. The transmission across the whole set up until the mass spectrometer was studied giving a relative efficiency of 20% from MCP1 (see Figure 8.1) to the end of PILGRIM. The gas cell has been characterized with gas cell ionization spectroscopy and the collisional broadening effects in gas cell and jet could be quantified for the transitions used. The isotope shift values and the hyperfine A and B constants were measured and they are in good agreement with the literature values (see Table 8.1). The predicted spectral resolution with the current gas cell and the jet setup has been proved experimentally with this work. In gas jet ionization technique gives a resolution of 280 MHz for a gas cell pressure of 300 mbar (see Figure 8.3). The gas cell and gas jet conditions for optimum efficiency and resolution could be deduced. A measurement of absolute efficiency of the gas cell is to be performed in the future. A qualitative comparison of the ionization efficiency in gas cell and gas jet could be realised with the tests performed. The results are published in [2]. These offline measurements thus pioneer for the future online experimental studies.

Fig. 8.2: Resonance peak scan of the excitation transition for the isotopes of stable Er in the gas jet with $\nu_0 = 721,995,050$ MHz. The measured data points are normalized with laser powers of both steps which are shown in black and the fit is shown in red. The reduced χ^2 values for the fits are labeled as χ_{red}^2 .

8.3 Outlook

The S³-LEB set up has been commissioned offline resulting in successful RIS measurement of isotope shifts and hyperfine structure of stable Er isotopes. From the above measurement results, several challenges were realized and further optimized with the aim to extract physics from the

Fig. 8.3: Resonance peak scan of the excitation transition for the isotopes of stable Er in the gas jet (blue) and in an ABU (black) with $\nu_0 = 721,995,050$ MHz. Their respective χ^2 fits are also shown. The measured data points are normalized with laser powers of both steps. The green plot shows the spectra expected theoretically, obtained by fixing I , J , and hyperfine A and B constants and fitting with a fixed spectral resolution of FWHM = 0.25 MHz to a Voigt function.

$\Delta\nu^{A',170}$ (MHz)			^{167}Er HFS coefficients				
$4f^{12}6s^2\ ^3H_6 \rightarrow 4f^{12}(^3H)6s6p\ J = 5$			$4f^{12}6s^2\ ^3H_6$		$4f^{12}(^3H_5)6s6p\ J = 5$		
Mass number	gas jet	ABU	Method	A (MHz)	B (MHz)	A (MHz)	B (MHz)
168	96(6)	97(8)	gas jet	-122(3)	-4847(237)	-148(4)	-2230(200)
167	138(8)	132(10)	gas jet	-121.8(fixed)	-4563(fixed)	-147.1(7)	-1936(24)
166	196(7)	193(8)	ABU	-121.80(75)	-4563(53)	-147.66(83)	-1888(58)
164	283(7)	298(7)	literature	-120.487(1)	-4552.984(10)	-146.6(3)	-1874(16)

Table 8.1: IS values $\Delta\nu^{A',170} = \nu^{A'} - \nu^{170}$ of stable $^{168-164}\text{Er}$ isotopes with respect to ^{170}Er and hyperfine A and B constants, for the $4f^{12}6s^2\ ^3H_6$ and $4f^{12}(^3H)6s6p\ J = 5$ atomic states of ^{167}Er deduced from the gas jet measurements, are shown and compared with the literature values reported in [4]. Fit values with A and B for the ground state kept free and fixed are shown. $\sigma(\Delta\nu^{A',170})$, $\sigma(A)$, and $\sigma(B)$ indicated in parenthesis represents the total uncertainties [4].

low cross section actinide nuclei in online cases. One technical challenge is the entrance windows requirements. For development and tests of these windows, an offline test bench was setup to improve the durability of the windows in the required pressure conditions. Upgradation of the existing Ti:sapphire laser system are being performed for mode-hop free tuning and stability. For continuous wavelength tuning, an alternative Ti:sapphire seed source was implemented. Further upgrades are under progress for implementing the frequency stabilization to be used in online conditions as well.

The S³-LEB setup with the end of offline commissioning has been recently coupled to the S³ setup. First online laser spectroscopy measurements will be performed on the radioactive neutron deficient isotopes of erbium and will also serve as the first experimental case for S³ spectrometer commissioning.

8.4 Acknowledgement

The S³-LEB setup results from the collaborative work of the IGLIS network, grouping many research centers and universities including CEA- Saclay (IRFU), CERN (CRIS), GANIL, GSI, IBS-RISP, IJCLab, IMP, JAEA, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz (Institut für Physik/LARISSA), JINR (GALS), JYFL (IGISOL/MARA), KEK (KISS), KU Leuven, MSU, Nagoya University, Normandie Université (LPC Caen), Peking University, RIKEN (SLOWRI/-PALIS), TRIUMF (TRILIS), Université de Strasbourg (IPHC), University of Manchester, University of Tsukuba and Laboratoire de Physique des 2 infinis Irène Joliot-Curie (IJC) S³ has been funded by the French Research Ministry, National Research Agency (ANR), through the EQUIPEX (EQUIPMENT of EXcellence) reference ANR-10EQPX- 46, the FEDER (Fonds Europeen de Développement Economique et Regional), the CPER (Contrat Plan Etat Re ´ gion), and supported by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Nuclear Physics, under contract No. DE-AC02-06CH11357 and by the E.C.FP7 INFRASTRUCTURES 2007, SPIRAL2 Preparatory Phase, Grant agreement No.: 212692. S³-LEB: This project has received funding from the French Research Ministry through the ANR-13-B505- 0013, the Research Foundation—Flanders (FWO)— under the International Research Infrastructure program (nr. I002219N), the Research Coordination Office—KU Leuven—the European Research Council (ERC-2011-AdG-291561-HELIOS) and the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 654002. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 861198-LISA-H2020-MSCA-ITN-2019

Bibliography

- [1] Déchery, F., et.al., 2016. The Super Separator Spectrometer S3 and the associated detection systems: SIRIUS & LEB-REGLIS3. Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms, 376, pp.125-130.
- [2] Ajayakumar, A., et.al., 2023. In gas jet laser spectroscopy with S3 LEB. Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms, 539, pp.102-107.
- [3] Romans, J., et.al., 2022. First Offline Results from the S3 Low-Energy Branch. Atoms, 10(1), p.21.
- [4] Romans, J., et.al., 2023. High-resolution laser system for the S3-Low Energy Branch. Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms, 536, pp.72-81.
- [5] Sonnenschein, et.al., 2017. Characterization of a pulsed injection-locked Ti:sapphire laser and its application to high resolution resonance ionization spectroscopy of copper. Laser Physics, 27(8), p.085701.

- [6] Anjali Ajayakumar. (2022). Optimized Ti:sa laser system for high resolution laser spectroscopy. In *Atoms* (1.0, Vol. 10, Number 1, p. 20). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6386547>

- [7] Anjali Ajayakumar. In gas jet laser spectroscopy optimization for high resolution measurement of actinides. Physics. Normandie Université, 2023. English. ⟨NNT : 2023NORMC267⟩. ⟨tel-04483471⟩

Chapter 9

Developments of laser techniques towards high-resolution laser spectroscopy of actinide homologs

Julius Wessolek^{a,b},

^a The University of Manchester, Manchester, United Kingdom

^b CERN SY-STI-LP, Geneva, Switzerland

In the following, the original plan of designing a Ti:Sa amplifier at M Squared Lasers in Glasgow is briefly introduced. The reasons for not completing this project are laid out. During a secondment at Prof. Tomita's group at Nagoya University, high-resolution spectroscopy of stable dysprosium was conducted and the results are presented. With the departure of M Squared from the LISA ITN, a transfer to the RILIS group at CERN was organized. There, third harmonic generation inside the cavity of a pulsed titanium sapphire (Ti:Sa) laser has been developed and is briefly introduced.

9.1 Original plan at the beginning of LISA

At the beginning of the LISA network, the project was introduced as "Development of low noise high power tunable pulsed narrow linewidth Ti:Sa (titanium-doped sapphire) amplifier for ion beam spectroscopy applications" hosted at M Squared Lasers in Glasgow, United Kingdom, one of the two industrial beneficiaries within the LISA network and located within Work Package 2, "Novel techniques and technologies for actinide research". The academic supervisor was Professor Kieran Flanagan at the University of Manchester, United Kingdom.

The aim of this project was to build on the experience and knowledge of M Squared in the design and manufacturing of continuous-wave Ti:Sa lasers to develop an injection-seeded Ti:Sa amplifier that produces laser pulses with linewidth, pulse length and peak power suitable for high-resolution laser spectroscopy. Different versions of this type of amplifier had been developed in the years previously at the Universities of Mainz, Jyväskylä and Nagoya [1, 2, ?]. These "home-made" systems should be a starting point to develop a commercial hands-off amplifier on the basis of M Squared's expertise.

9.2 The M Squared days

At the start of the project in September 2020, the access to the laboratories and offices at M Squared was inhibited due to the Covid-19 pandemic. During that time, an overview of the literature was put together and first simple simulations of the tuning behaviour of an injection-seeded amplifier cavity were made. Even when the UK moved out of lockdown, work continued remotely and communication with laser engineers at M Squared remained difficult. Therefore, it remained challenging to progress with the envisioned laser design.

To mitigate the access situation at M Squared, I was able to join the CRIS experiment at ISOLDE, CERN, in June of 2021 to support their high-resolution laser spectroscopy campaign of silver. After that, I stayed at CERN for a total of 6 weeks and gained hands-on experience with the injection-seeded Ti:Sa system at CRIS as well as with the broad-band Z-cavity-type Ti:Sa lasers at RILIS. Further trips to CERN were made to support the CRIS laser-spectroscopy campaigns of RaF, another run of Ag, and AcF.

In the beginning of 2022, access to the office and lab at M Squared was granted. However, due to further delays of access to resources and equipment necessary to advance with the amplifier design, M Squared finally decided to resign as a beneficiary of the LISA network at the end of February of 2023.

9.3 Secondment at Nagoya University

From mid January until the end of February 2023, I was able to visit Prof. Tomita and his group at Nagoya University in Nagoya, Japan. During the visit, the Ti:Sa amplifier system at Tomita’s lab was recommissioned, characterised, and high-resolution laser ionization spectroscopy of stable dysprosium (Dy, $Z = 66$) was conducted in a ToF-MS (time-of-flight mass spectrometer). The results of the secondment were presented at the LISA Conference 2023 in Leuven, Belgium, and will be summarised in the following.

The ionization scheme of Dy used in this work consists of two steps, shown in Figure 9.1. The 421.29 nm transition from the $4f^{10}6s^2, J = 8$ ground state to the $4f^{10}6s6p, J = 9$ state was used as spectroscopy step, while the subsequent ionization into an autoionizing resonance was done with 406.383 nm laser light.

The laser system used for the generation of the ns pulsed narrow-band laser light consists of an injection-seeded Ti:Sa amplifier that was seeded with a home-built diode-pumped continuous-wave Ti:Sa laser at a fundamental wavelength of 842.58 nm. This system was designed and assembled by Volker Sonnenschein during his time in Nagoya. Subsequent second harmonic generation (SHG) in a BBO crystal ($\theta = 27.8^\circ$) results in light of the required wavelength. The laser light for the resonant ionization step was generated with a grating-tuned Ti:Sa laser, again with subsequent SHG in a BBO crystal ($\theta = 28.8^\circ$).

In injection-seeded amplifiers, a beam of cw laser light (“seed”) is injected into a laser cavity, which is kept on resonance with the seed light by actively stabilizing the cavity length. For this, one of the cavity mirrors is attached to a piezo actuator. When the optical path length of the cavity is an integer multiple of the seed wavelength, i.e. the cavity is on resonance with the seed light, the round trips of the seed inside the cavity interfere constructively and a maximum of leakage of the light through one of the cavity mirrors can be detected with a photodiode. With this photodiode signal, a digital stabilization system (TEM LaseLock) is used to set up a feedback loop that actively

Fig. 9.1: Ionization scheme of dysprosium used for this work, taken from [4].

stabilizes (“locks”) the cavity length to the input wavelength. A pump pulse from a frequency-doubled Nd:YAG (Neodymium-doped Yttrium Aluminium Garnet) laser at 532 nm with 10 kHz repetition rate (Photonics Industries) with 12.5 W average power generates population inversion inside the active medium, a sapphire crystal (Al_2O_3) doped with Ti^{3+} -ions. The photons of the seed light circulating in the amplifier cavity give the seed mode an advantage over all other cavity modes, resulting in a laser pulse that has the same wavelength of the seed light and a linewidth of usually 10-30 MHz, close to the Fourier limit, the theoretical linewidth minimum for a pulse of a specific temporal length. To prevent spatial hole burning that is prevalent in standing-wave resonators and inhibits single longitudinal mode operation, a travelling wave resonator in bow-tie configuration is used. During the pump pulse, the photodiode of the locking setup is grounded to prevent it and the amplifier electronics from saturation. This is done with a fast-switching photodiode amplifier that receives a gate signal synchronously with the pump laser pulses. A scanning Fabry-Perot interferometer (Toptica FPI 100, FSR = 1 GHz) was used to analyze the linewidth of the amplified light. The extracted linewidth was 11.5(1.0) MHz which is about twice the Fourier limit, which is 6.3 MHz for a Gaussian pulse with 70 ns FWHM pulse length.

Additionally, the dependency of the pulse build-up time on the power of the seed light was studied. For the free-running case and four different seed power levels, the time between the peak of the pump pulse and the peak of the laser pulse in the amplifier cavity was measured with a photodiode, averaged over 128 pulses. It can be seen that the build-up time decreases with increasing seed power. This is due to the higher initial number of photons in the cavity, leading to a higher rate of stimulated emission and therefore reducing the time it takes to build up the laser pulse inside the amplifier.

The laser beams of both steps are overlapped in a cross geometry in front of a restively heated crucible, in which a sample of dysprosium metal is placed. The crossed beams only interact with

Fig. 9.2: Example linewidth measurement of the 842.58 nm laser light generated by the injection-seeded Ti:Sa amplifier.

Fig. 9.3: Left: Pump pulse and laser pulse that builds up in the amplifier cavity at 1.2 mW of seed light. Average trace of 128 pulses taken with a photodiode. Right: Pulse build-up time inside the amplifier cavity depending on the seed power injected into the amplifier. A higher initial number of photon in the cavity results in a higher rate of stimulated emission and a reduced build-up time.

a small part of the atom cone from crucible, reducing the Doppler broadening. Mass separation of the seven stable isotopes of Dy with masses 156, 158 and 160 - 164 is done in a ToF-MS with a microchannel plate detector and a 700 mm long drift tube. The mass resolution is just good enough to distinguish between neighboring masses in this region, although mass leakage can be seen especially in the hyperfine spectra of $^{163,161}\text{Dy}$ shown in Figure 9.4. The extracted isotope shifts and hyperfine parameters are given in Tables 9.1 and 9.2 respectively and agree with the values given by [5] within uncertainties. This shows nicely the high-resolution spectroscopy capabilities of compact systems like this one at the lab of Prof. Tomita at Nagoya University, Japan.

Table 9.1: Isotope shifts of the 421.29 nm $4f^{10}6s^2, J = 8 \rightarrow 4f^{10}6s6p, J = 9$ transition of dysprosium.

A	$\Delta\nu_{164,A}$ [MHz] [this work]	$\Delta\nu_{164,A}$ [MHz] [5]
163	-634(45)	-616.3(5)
162	-930(26)	-913.2(8)
161	-1640(49)	-1635(1)
160	-1916(74)	-1895(2)
158	-2900(230)	-2868(9)
156	-4250(360)	-4300(15)

Fig. 9.4: Spectra of stable Dy isotopes. Slight leakage of neighboring masses can be seen in the spectra of $^{163,161}\text{Dy}$ due to limited mass resolving power. The fits to extract the hyperfine coefficients and isotope shifts were done with the SATLAS 2 python package [6].

Table 9.2: Hyperfine coefficients of the $4f^{10}6s6p$, $J = 9$ excited state of dysprosium.

	A [MHz]		B [MHz]	
	[this work]	[5]	[this work]	[5]
^{163}Dy	122(8)	121.62(2)	1920(230)	1844.9(4)
^{161}Dy	-76(12)	-86.90(2)	1910(520)	1747.4(5)

9.4 Transfer to RILIS at ISOLDE, CERN

After the secondment in Nagoya, I was able to transfer to CERN, where I joined the RILIS team which runs ISOLDE’s laser ion source. One laser development project was to improve the way the third harmonic of the RILIS Ti:Sa lasers is generated. This was usually done outside the laser cavity in a single pass manner [7] which uses valuable table space and results in a beam of highly elliptical shape that requires tedious beam shaping to be transported 20 m from the laser room into the ion source. Generating the third harmonic inside the Ti:Sa laser cavity gives comparable power levels to the external generation and results in a beam shape that is circular. The setup had its first on-line applications for the delivery of radioactive indium and gold, where it performed reliably. A publication to summarize this development is in preparation.

In 2023, the yields of several different lanthanide elements (Pm, Gd, Dy, Er, Tm, and Yb) from a tantalum foil target with a LIST (Laser Ion Source and Trap) ion source unit were measured [8] and are pending publication. Yield measurements of further lanthanides from a similar target and ion source unit will follow in the near future [9] and will be used to benchmark the models developed for yield extraction from the first campaign.

Bibliography

- [1] Sonnenschein, V. (2014). Laser developments and high resolution resonance ionization spectroscopy of actinide elements. [PhD Thesis] Available at: <https://jyx.jyu.fi/handle/123456789/45033>.
- [2] Sonnenschein, V. et al. (2017). Characterization of a pulsed injection-locked Ti:sapphire laser and its application to high resolution resonance ionization spectroscopy of copper. *Laser Physics*, 27(8), pp.085701–085701. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1555-6611/aa7834>.
- [3] Reponen, M. et al. (2018). Towards in-jet resonance ionization spectroscopy: An injection-locked Titanium:Sapphire laser system for the PALIS-facility. *Nuclear instruments and methods in physics research. Section A, Accelerators, spectrometers, detectors and associated equipment/Nuclear instruments & methods in physics research. Section A, Accelerators, spectrometers, detectors and associated equipment*, 908, pp.236–243. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2018.08.073>.
- [4] Trappitsch, R. et al. Resonance Ionization Scheme Database. Available at: <https://rims-code.github.io/schemes/schemes/>. Accessed 30.06.2024.
- [5] Leefer, N. et al. (2009). Measurement of hyperfine structure and isotope shifts in the Dy 421 nm transition. *Optics Letters*, 34(17), 2548. <https://doi.org/10.1364/ol.34.002548>
- [6] van den Borne, B., Gins, W. SATLAS2 – Statistical Analysis Toolbox for Laser Spectroscopy, version 2. Available at: <https://iks-nm.github.io/satlas2/>
- [7] Rothe, S. et al. (2011). A complementary laser system for ISOLDE RILIS. *Journal of Physics. Conference Series*, 312(5), 052020. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/312/5/052020>
- [8] Chrysalidis, K. et al. (2022). Yield Measurements for Lanthanide Elements with Ta-Foil Target and a LIST Ion Source. Letter of Intent to the INTC. Geneva: CERN. <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2834598>.
- [9] Lynch, K. M. et al. (2024) In-Source Laser Spectroscopy of Neutron-Deficient Lutetium and Holmium Isotopes, towards the Proton Emitters. Letter of Intent to the INTC. Geneva: CERN. <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2894970>.

Chapter 10

The quest for laser spectroscopy of the heaviest actinide elements

Jessica Warbinek^{a,b,c,†}, Michael Block^{a,b,c}, Sebastian Raeder^{a,b}, on behalf of the RADRIS- and Fermium-Collaborations

^a Division Superheavy elements, GSI Helmholtzzentrum für Schwerionenforschung, 64291 Darmstadt, Germany, ^b Section Superheavy element physics, Helmholtz Institut Mainz, 55099 Mainz, Germany, ^c Department Chemie—Standort TRIGA, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz, 55099 Mainz, Germany, [†] Present address: Experimental Physics Department, CERN, CH-1211 Geneva 23, Switzerland.

Laser spectroscopy of the heaviest actinide elements is one of the pillars of the research conducted within the LISA framework. The research on these exotic elements performed at the GSI in Darmstadt revealed new insights into their atomic and nuclear structure and allowed benchmarking state-of-the-art theory models. Methodological advancements of the RADRIS technique achieved within this project gave access to new isotopes for the technique, which were previously not in reach. The developments and new experimental results achieved within the LISA work at GSI are summarized, and further prospects outlined.

10.1 Introduction

The actinide elements, and the heaviest ones of this kind, have recently been in the focus of various atomic and nuclear physics studies to understand their fundamental properties. Nuclear spectroscopy investigations on isotopes of the heaviest actinides have given insight into their single-particle structure, revealing a deformed shell gap at $N = 152$ in a region of strong prolate deformation [1]. With direct mass measurements in nobelium ($Z = 102$) and lawrencium ($Z = 103$) isotopes, the location of a deformed shell gap at $N = 152$ was confirmed and its size was determined accurately [2]. Although numerous previous studies in this region contributed to the understanding of the evolution of nuclear excited states around the shell gap, our knowledge of nuclear ground-state observables remains scarce. A comparison of state-of-the-art predictions by nuclear models with experimental data in this region will enhance our understanding of these quantum many-body systems [3].

Similarly, in these heavy elements, our experimental knowledge on their atomic structure is limited. Characteristics such as relativistic effects and electron correlations lead to modifications in the atomic structure which can, ultimately, change the chemical behaviour of these elements

compared to their lighter homologues [4]. Supported by significant efforts in atomic calculations, yielding predictions for atomic energy levels and transitions, unidentified levels can be unravelled experimentally. However, as the accuracy of these models is limited and usually smaller than the experimental one, such experiments remain challenging [5].

With recent achievements in the field of laser spectroscopy of the heaviest actinide elements, pioneered by first experiments on nobelium [6], nuclear structure investigations by studying atomic transitions of these elements became possible [4]. The experimental developments towards identifying suitable laser excitation schemes between atomic levels for nuclear structure studies go hand in hand. In this context, recent efforts at the GSI in Darmstadt, within the framework of LISA, focussed on studying nuclear ground-state observables by laser spectroscopy in the elements nobelium and fermium ($Z = 100$), among others, around the $N = 152$ shell gap. The ongoing search for atomic levels in the heaviest actinide element lawrencium marks another large focus of the work within LISA.

The milestones and advances achieved within the LISA work at GSI in the project of ESR 10 are summarized. Experimental results and new physics highlights of laser spectroscopy of the heaviest actinide elements are outlined.

10.2 New developments towards more exotic heavy actinide species

The study of the heaviest actinide elements bears several experimental challenges which have to be tackled. Besides the production yields of atom-at-a-time rates and the often short half-lives of the isotopes of interest, the scarce information on the atomic structure hampers laser spectroscopy investigations. In contrast to laser spectroscopy studies of other isotopic chains, there are no stable (or long-lived) reference isotopes and methodological studies have to be carried out with lighter homologues. Prior to the experimental efforts and results achieved within the LISA work at GSI, methodological advancements through several such developments of the technique had to be achieved. The following chapter describes the RADRIS technique, specialized to studies on the heavy actinides, and summarizes recent developments which opened pathways to studies of more exotic heavy actinide isotopes.

10.2.1 The RADRIS technique

Laser spectroscopy using the RADIation Detected Resonance Ionization Spectroscopy method is a relatively recent tool established specifically for the study of isotopes produced in heavy-ion fusion-evaporation reactions [6, 7]. A schematic representation of the method is shown in Figure 10.1.

The isotopes of interest are produced in complete fusion-evaporation reactions and are separated from the primary beam in the SHIP velocity filter [8]. The reaction products proceed in the direction of the primary beam with kinetic energies of tens of MeV (about 40 MeV for ^{254}No) and hence, need to be stopped for further investigations. The RADRIS setup consists of a stopping cell filled with about 90 mbar argon gas, allowing to efficiently stop the recoil nuclei in a small interaction volume after entering through a thin entrance window. Thermalized recoil ions are guided towards a catcher filament positioned opposite the entrance window and biased to an attractive potential. Attracted ions are accumulated and neutralized on the filament surface. After collecting ions for a sufficient time, the primary beam is stopped, the filament potential switched

to be repulsive, and the laser shutters are opened. A following short resistive heat-pulse on the filament desorbs the accumulated recoil products forming a "cloud" of neutral atoms around the filament. Two lasers following a two-step ionization scheme, illuminating the volume around the filament, enable subsequent resonant ionization of the atoms. Resulting laser ions are then guided by suitable electric field towards a silicon detector for unambiguous detection and identification of registered ions via their characteristic alpha-decay energy. After such a schematically described RADRIS cycle, the transport potentials are switched back to allow for collection on the filament, laser shutters are closed, and the primary beam is requested again for production of new recoil nuclei.

Fig. 10.1: Schematic drawing of the RADRIS setup. Recoil ions enter the gas cell through the thin entrance window and are accumulated and neutralized on the filament surface. After desorption from the filament, resonance ionization is achieved by two lasers illuminating the volume around the filament. Resulting laser ions are guided towards a silicon detector for detection via their characteristic alpha-decay energies. Figure adapted from Ref. [9] under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0.

10.2.2 Extending the reach of RADRIS to shorter-lived and longer-lived nuclei

The cyclic application bears various benefits, however along with efficiency losses for shorter-lived and longer-lived isotopes. In the RADRIS measurement cycle, produced recoil nuclei are collected on the filament approximately until radioactive equilibrium is reached. After completed collection, the primary beam is stopped and transport potentials are switched by several hundreds of volts to allow guidance of produced laser ions to the detector. A short break before the filament heat pulse is required, to allow the complete stop of the primary beam and the transport potentials to

reach their set point. The filament heat-pulse duration itself adds an additional delay before full desorption and laser ionization. In the previous RADRIS setup, the total delay between stop of the primary beam and the detection of laser ions summed up to about 2 s (more details in Ref. [9]). For species with half-lives of only 1 s or less, large efficiency losses occurred, preventing the access to short-lived nuclides featuring small production yields. In addition, an increased beam off-period reduces the overall efficiency of valuable beamtime usage.

With the implementation of a new rapid voltage switching scheme, including the application of a fast high-voltage switch, the overall delay time was reduced significantly. This allowed a simultaneous switching of transport potentials, including a reduction on the required potentials to be changed, with the application of the heat pulse. With this newly implemented short-cycle scheme, the delay time along with related efficiency losses was reduced by more than half and is now mainly limited by the ion mobility determining the transport time of investigated species in the argon buffer-gas atmosphere. More details can be found in Ref. [9]. With the increased sensitivity for shorter-lived species, first laser spectroscopy of ^{251}No ($t_{1/2} = 0.8$ s) became feasible, which was previously out of reach.

For longer-lived species with half-lives of several tens of minutes or hours, a different disadvantage in the technique appears. While half-life losses in the short RADRIS cycle beam break are negligible, the longer half-lives lead to an extended measurement time on the silicon detector, before a new wavenumber can be probed with the first-step laser. All laser ions created from one scan step have to decay, before a next measurement at a new scan step can be performed. This leads to an inefficient beamtime usage and longer measurement times, up to the point of preventing the experiment within the given beamtime.

To avoid these long waiting times, a rotatable multi-detector setup was developed, allowing to parallelize the collection of laser ions and the detection of subsequent alpha decays. A schematic picture is shown in Figure 10.2a). One detector is positioned on axis with the ion transport line to receive laser ions from one scan step. After concluding the collection from several RADRIS cycles, the setup is rotated, and a new, clean detector receives laser ions from the next scan step. The detection of remaining decays of ions from the previous scan step are concluded in an off-axis position on the respective detector.

This detector arrangement for longer-lived species recently allowed the study of the isotope ^{254}Fm with $t_{1/2} = 3.24$ h. With the conventional RADRIS method, measurement times of up to a day per scan step, depending on the necessary statistics, would have been required. The rotatable detector setup reduced the measurement time by a factor three. In the future, for even longer-lived species, arrangements with more detectors may give access to isotopes presently not in reach for the radiation detection-based approach.

10.2.3 Enhancing the RADRIS sensitivity

The RADRIS technique relying on the detection of the alpha decay of collected laser ions, yields the possibility for an unambiguous identification of the species of interest. Depending on the alpha branch, efficiency losses have to be taken into account. As part of the development work on RADRIS, the detection efficiency was greatly improved with the development of a new detector system and an overall improvement of the transport electrode structure [10, 11]. The typical RADRIS setup utilized a single silicon detector with the active surface oriented towards the filament. Laser ions are guided towards the detector and stick on its surface, where their decay is detected. The

Fig. 10.2: (a) Schematic drawing of the RADRIS rotatable multi-detector setup for studies of longer-lived isotopes. Laser ions created in one RADRIS scan step are guided towards and collected on one detector in the on-axis collection position. After concluded collection of laser ions from this scan step, the detector is rotated to allow probing the next laser scan step with a clean detector receiving new laser ions. The subsequent from laser ions of the previous scan step are concluded in an off-axis detection position. (b) Schematic drawing of the RADRIS movable double-detector setup. Laser ions are collected on a collection detector positioned on-axis during the beam break period in the RADRIS cycle. During the filament collection period, the detector is moved to a detection position off-axis, where it rests facing a second silicon detector. The additional detector allows to detect alphas emitted in the hemisphere opposite the collection detector active surface. Figures adapted from Ref. [9] under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0.

solid angle coverage for emitted alpha particles amounts to a maximum of 50 % for the detected decays.

To increase the solid angle coverage, a movable multi-detector setup was developed. Similarly as in subsection 10.2.2, the cyclic application of RADRIS gives one advantage to be used for species with half-lives of a few seconds or longer: during the filament collection time, the collection detector is not occupied and can be moved to an off-axis position using a linear actuator. In this position, the movable, collection detector is resting facing a second silicon detector, allowing to collect alphas emitted in the opposite hemisphere which would usually be missed. A schematic representation of this setup is shown in Figure 10.2b).

In on-line commissioning experiments, this new double-detector setup was tested and a significant increase in efficiency observed. For ^{254}No , 67 % of the alphas, which would usually be missed, were additionally registered [11]. With this new optimized setup, a total RADRIS efficiency of more than 15 % was extracted for this isotope. Ultimately, this setup was used extensively during the latest level search campaign for excited atomic states in lawrencium offering an increased sensitivity.

10.2.4 Optimization of the filament desorption

The application of the RADRIS technique for lawrencium required preceding developments towards an efficient and complete desorption of this element from the filament. Off-line studies on the chemical homologue element lutetium were performed to identify the optimum filament type among different refractory metals and geometries which were tested [12]. For lawrencium, a much higher desorption temperature of about 1800 °C is required compared to only 1100 °C sufficient for nobelium. Therefore, an increased surface-ion background resulting from these high-temperature heat pulses, elevated by the lower ionization potential of lawrencium compared to nobelium, had

to be prevented. A suitable type was identified in a hafnium-strip type filament, combining both, a minimized surface ion background and longevity of the filament [12, 13]. In a subsequent on-line commissioning experiment, the desorption of lawrencium from this filament type was investigated. The filament and desorption behavior was characterized and the desorption enthalpy extracted [14]. In the recent level search campaigns, as well as all other presented studies, this filament type was successfully applied in the RADRIS technique.

10.3 Shining light on the heavyweights: new experimental results

The recent developments described in this summary and further advances capitalizing on novel nuclide production approaches with RADRIS gave access to additional Fm and No isotopes along the $N = 152$ deformed shell gap. New indirect production schemes were implemented, which are based on the direct production of the mother nuclide, accumulation, and a breeding of the daughter isotope of interest from the radioactive decay of the mother on the filament (further described in Ref. [15]). The previously established isotopic chain of $^{252-254}\text{No}$ and the measured changes in mean-square charge radii [16] was extended beyond the shell gap by studying ^{255}No produced in such an indirect scheme [17]. With the new short-cycle developments, also the neutron-deficient ^{251}No came in reach as described in subsection 10.2.2.

These developments furthermore allowed studying fermium isotopes with RADRIS. Isotopes of this element were previously out of reach for the technique, due to the low production yields and unfavorable target-beam combinations [15]. Via the direct production and alpha decay of their respective nobelium mother, $^{248-250}\text{Fm}$ were available for laser spectroscopy using RADRIS [18]. In addition, ^{254}Fm , accessed via the small electron-capture branch of ^{254}No and its daughter ^{254}Md , was investigated using the newly developed rotatable multi-detector setup described in subsection 10.2.2. This data set allowed the study of changes in mean-square charge radii beyond the neutron shell gap at $N = 152$ featuring the proton sub-shell gap at $Z = 100$. The fermium isotopic chain was further complemented on the neutron-deficient side by recent measurements on directly produced $^{245,246}\text{Fm}$ [11].

The on-line results using the RADRIS technique were combined with measurements at the RISIKO mass separator at Mainz University (see contribution of ESR 05 for further details). Here, samples from reactor breeding gave access to macroscopic amounts of $^{255,257}\text{Fm}$ for off-line studies applying resonant ionization laser spectroscopy in a hot-cavity. A similar production and measurement scheme had previously also been demonstrated on californium ($Z = 98$) and einsteinium ($Z = 99$) isotopes [19, 20]. In total, a long chain of eight fermium isotopes covering both sides of the deformed shell gap was investigated through the combination of various production and off- and on-line measurement schemes. These experimental results gave new input for nuclear density functional theory models predicting the nuclear charge radius evolution and the impact of the neutron shell gap in this region. More information will be given in Ref. [17].

Lastly, major efforts were made in the search of atomic levels in the heaviest actinide element lawrencium. Guided by atomic theory predictions, two suitable, strong transitions in the range from 20 000-30 000 cm^{-1} were targeted in the search campaign. Here, the enhanced RADRIS detection efficiency and improved cycle schemes allowed for an optimal sensitivity of the setup for the level search. Large ranges around predictions from various computational approaches were

scanned, however the full theory uncertainty range of 500 cm^{-1} was not fully covered yet. Upcoming experimental campaigns will focus on the continuation to identify an atomic level in lawrencium. A summary of previous campaigns can be found in the Deliverable report 5.5 [10].

10.4 Summary and Outlook

The laser spectroscopy program of the heaviest actinide elements at GSI was extended to various new isotopes utilizing the RADRIS technique, and the experimental scope was increased. The new developments made within the LISA framework allowed tackling more exotic nuclides previously out of reach.

A long isotopic chain of fermium isotopes was investigated and isotope shifts were extracted. With further input from atomic calculations, changes in mean-square charge radii were studied. With the experimental insight in the nuclear size evolution in fermium around the $N = 152$ shell gap, nuclear model predictions were benchmarked and the experimental results interpreted [17]. New experimental input in this region will trigger more developments in state-of-the-art nuclear models and eventually help to increase their predictive power for the heaviest nuclei.

The search for atomic levels in the heaviest actinide element lawrencium was started and large ranges around the various atomic predictions within their theoretical uncertainties were scanned [10, 14]. Once an atomic level is identified, also access to further nuclear structure investigations by laser spectroscopy will be given. By studying the underlying hyperfine structure of an atomic level, nuclear moments can be extracted. This, for instance, will allow for the determination of the quadrupole moment also in the isomer ^{255m}Lr .

The new in-gas jet technique, with the JetRIS apparatus tailored for the hyperfine spectroscopy of fusion-evaporation products at GSI, features a higher spectral resolution compared to RADRIS (see contribution of ESR 07 for further details). It will in future give access to additional nuclear structure observables in the heaviest actinide nuclides, for example enabling the extraction of nuclear moments and spins. The recent on-line commissioning showed a sub-GHz resolution for an atomic transition in ^{254}No [21, 22], and with further developments towards a higher efficiency, more isotopes will come in reach for the technique.

Compilation of Milestones and Deliverables

In the following table a list of milestones and deliverables of the LISA Work Package 5 (WP5) associated to this contribution is reported.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 861198–LISA–H2020-MSCA-ITN-2019.

The authors would like to acknowledge the RADRIS- and Fermium-collaboration and members who participated in the on-line beamtime and off-line experiments and actively supported this work: Thomas Albrecht-Schönzart, Brankica Anđelić, Julian Auler, Benjamin Bally, Michael Bender, Sebastian Berndt, Alexandre Brizard, Pierre Chauveau, Bradley Cheal, Premaditya Chhetri, Arno Claessens, Antoine de Roubin, Charlie Devlin, Holger Dorrer, Christoph E. Düllmann, Julie

Code	Title	Description	Date
LISA-MS21	Optimum filament setup for efficient Lr evaporation	Report on the filament characterization and setup applied for the Lr level search campaigns	31.12.2020
LISA-MS24	Level search in lawrencium	See D5.5	30.04.2023
LISA-MS26	Setup for high-resolution in gas-jet laser spectroscopy	Report on the setup and developments of the JetRIS apparatus for heavy actinide laser spectroscopy at GSI	
LISA-D5.5	Level search in the heaviest actinide element, lawrencium	Report summarizing the developments towards and present experimental results from previous Lr level search campaigns	30.04.2023

Ezold, Rafael Ferrer, Vadim Gadelshin, Alyssa Gaiser, Francesca Giacoppo, Stephane Goriely, Manuel J. Gutiérrez, Ashley Harvey, Raphael Hasse, Reinhard Heinke, Fritz-Peter Heßberger, Stephane Hilaire, Magdalena Kaja, Oliver Kaleja, Tom Kieck, EunKang Kim, Nina Kneip, Ulli Köster, Sandro Kraemer, Mustapha Laatiaoui, Jeremy Lantis, Nathalie Lecesne, Andrea Tzeitel Loria Basto, Andrew Mistry, Christoph Mokry, Iain Moore, Tobias Murböck, Danny Münzberg, Witold Nazarewicz, Thorben Niemeyer, Steven Nothhelfer, Sophie Péru, Andrea Raggio, Paul-Gerhard Reinhard, Dennis Renisch, Emmanuel Rey-Herme, Elisabeth Rickert, Jekabs Romans, Elisa Romero Romero, Jörg Runke, Wouter Ryssens, Hervé Savajols, Fabian Schneider, Joseph Sperling, Matou Stemmler, Dominik Studer, Petra Thörle-Pospiech, Norbert Trautmann, Mitzi Urquiza-González, Kenneth van Beek, Shelley Van Cleve, Piet Van Duppen, Marine Vandebrouck, Elise Verstraelen, Thomas Walther, Felix Weber, and Klaus Wendt.

Bibliography

- [1] Theisen, Ch, et al. "In-beam spectroscopy of heavy elements". Nucl. Phys. A 944 (2015): 333-375.
- [2] Ramirez, E. Minaya, et al. "Direct mapping of nuclear shell effects in the heaviest elements". Science 337(6099) (2012): 1207-1210.
- [3] Nazarewicz, W., "The limits of nuclear mass and charge". Nat. Phys. 14 (2018):537–541.
- [4] Block, M. et al., "Recent progress in laser spectroscopy of the actinides". Prog. Part. Nucl. Phys. 116 (2021): 103834.
- [5] Smits, O.R. et al., "The quest for superheavy elements and the limit of the periodic table". Nat. Rev. Phys. 6(98) (2024): 86–98.
- [6] Laatiaoui, M. et al., "Atom-at-a-time laser resonance ionization spectroscopy of nobelium". Nature 538 (2016): 495–498.
- [7] Lautenschläger, F. et al., "Developments for resonance ionization laser spectroscopy of the heaviest elements at SHIP". Nucl. Instrum. Meth. B 383 (2016): 115–122.
- [8] Münzenberg, G. et al., "The velocity filter SHIP, a separator of unslowed heavy ion fusion products". Nucl. Instrum. Meth. 161 (1979): 65–82.

- [9] Warbinek, J. et al., “Advancing radiation-detected resonance ionization towards heavier elements and more exotic nuclides”. *Atoms* 10(41) (2022).
- [10] Warbinek, J. et al., "Level search in the heaviest actinide element, lawrencium". LISA Deliverable 5.5 report (2023).
- [11] Warbinek, J., "Probing the nuclear structure of fermium by laser spectroscopy". PhD Thesis, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz, Department of Chemistry (2023).
- [12] Murböck, T. et al., "Filament studies for laser spectroscopy on lawrencium". *Hyperf. Int.* 241 (2020): 1-9.
- [13] Warbinek, J. et al., "Optimum filament setup for efficient Lr evaporation". LISA Milestone 21 report (2020).
- [14] Rickert, E. et al., in preparation (2024).
- [15] Raeder, S. et al., “Opportunities and limitations of in-gas-cell laser spectroscopy of the heaviest elements with RADRIS”. *Nucl. Instrum. Meth. B* 541, (2023): 370-374.
- [16] Raeder, S. et al. "Probing sizes and shapes of nobelium isotopes by laser spectroscopy". *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 120(23) (2018): 232503.
- [17] Warbinek, J. et al., submitted, under review (2024).
- [18] Rickert, E., "Laser spectroscopy of fermium isotopes and development of an actinide ion mobility spectrometer". PhD Thesis, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz, Department of Chemistry (2023).
- [19] Weber, F. et al., "Nuclear moments and isotope shifts of the actinide isotopes Cf 249–253 probed by laser spectroscopy". *Phys. Rev. C* 107(3) (2023): 034313.
- [20] Nothhelfer, S. et al., "Nuclear structure investigations of Es 253- 255 by laser spectroscopy". *Phys. Rev. C* 105(2) (2022): L021302.
- [21] Lantis, J. et al., "In-gas-jet laser spectroscopy of ^{254}No with JetRIS". *Phys. Rev. Res.* 6(2) (2024): 023318.
- [22] Claessens, A., "Laser ionization spectroscopy of ^{254}No and ^{229}Th in hypersonic gas jets". PhD Thesis, KU Leuven, Institute for Nuclear and Radiation Physics (2024).

Chapter 11

Multi-element ultra-trace detection of radionuclides in environmental samples

Darcy van Eerten^a, Paul Hanemann^a, Laura Leifermann^a, Tobias Weissenborn^a, David Ohm^a, Magda Kaja^b, Mitzi Urquiza^c, Manuel Raiwa^d, Danielle Ziva Shulaker^d, Brett Isselhardt^d, Michael Savina^d, Klaus Wendt^b, Clemens Walther^a

^a Leibniz Universität Hannover, Hannover, Germany ^b Johannes Gutenberg Universität Mainz, Mainz, Germany ^c Hübner Photonics, Kassel, Germany ^d Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, Livermore, USA

A ‘hot particle’ is a microscopic fragment deriving from nuclear material. They have been observed in the environment as a result of nuclear accidents such as in Chernobyl and Fukushima, and continue to be a source of contamination. The history of a hot particle is contained in its isotopic composition, characteristic of its origin and interaction with the environment.

Resonant ionization mass spectrometry (RIMS) is a versatile technique that relies on the universality of atomic structure to selectively analyse isotope ratios in a target element. This work demonstrates advances in the SIRIUS RIMS instrument at Leibniz University Hannover for multi-element ultra-trace analysis in nuclear forensics and radioecology.

11.1 Introduction

Resonant ionization mass spectrometry (RIMS) is a technique for element-selective isotope analysis. The ratio between isotopes can be used in nuclear forensics to determine the origin of nuclear material, such as found in microscopic fragments that are emitted in a nuclear accident such as Chernobyl and Fukushima.

In this work, time-of-flight mass spectrometry (ToF-SIMS) was adapted to resonantly ionize secondary neutrals, allowing for spatially resolved solid-state analysis of so-called ‘hot particles’. The isotopic composition of these particles reflect reactor design and operation through ratios in U, Pu, and Cs, can be connected to a release event by analysing the time-dependent Sr, and show through Ba that Cs has been lost to the environment. Imaging isotopes in Zr and Sr show the interaction between fissionogenic and naturally occurring isotopes on the surface of hot particles [9].

Within the LISA project, this work achieved the following milestones:

- Application of fast scanning option for multi actinide detection;
- Development of high resolution excitation schemes for Pu;
- Application of narrowband excitation for $^{238}\text{Pu}/^{238}\text{U}$ discrimination.

These milestones detail advances in the SIRIUS RIMS instrument at Leibniz University Hannover, as highlighted by a small selection of relevant results. Isotope ratio analysis in the actinides and beyond is further described in works by Bosco, Raiwa, and van Eerten et al. [1, 7, 10].

11.2 Application of fast scanning option for multi actinide detection

Fig. 11.1: Laser ionisation schemes for elements relevant to the analysis of nuclear material, see van Eerten [9] for full attribution of schemes.

Theoretically, RIMS analysis is applicable to any element for which there is an efficient resonant scheme. The transition wavelengths must be accessible to the available laser systems. Further, the transition must be saturated within the power output of said laser system, in the geometry required by the mass spectrometer. Finally, the isotope shift across all relevant isotopes must be within range of the laser bandwidth, and considered against interferences from overlapping elements. In Figure 11.1, the total schemes used in the project [9] are summarized.

Fast switching is enabled in the two-step blue schemes by the grating Ti:Sa laser, while the red and UV schemes (for Cs, Ba and Pu in Figure 11.1) require manual wavelength changes by switching cavity mirrors and realigning the laser.

The grating lasers offer more flexibility by adjusting the angle of the grating, and adjusting the doubling crystal angle for maximum power output. There is no need for additional alignment, as it can be done automatically through LabView software [6]. Achieving saturation power is easily achieved in most schemes, however is more challenging for schemes in the far edges of the frequency range, such as in the Zr scheme (see [9] for full investigation of saturation powers in SIRIUS). The total range can be extended by adjusting input power and cavity alignment.

In this report, only one scheme will be discussed, a new scheme for Np developed through the LISA network [3]. As an actinide between U and Pu, it highlights the effectiveness and limitations

of using narrow-band lasers to enhance discrimination between elements.

11.3 Np Scheme testing on Chernobyl hot particle - application of narrowband excitation

In spectroscopic work by Kaja et al. on the exotic isotopes of Np [3], a scheme was developed on a Np sample that contained ^{237}Np and ^{239}Np generated in the TRIGA reactor in Mainz from a ^{238}U target. While the sample was chemically separated to contain only Np, ^{239}Pu will be rapidly produced by decay of ^{239}Np . Interference from Pu was seen in the initial analysis, and a question was raised whether a slight shift in the AI step would improve the Np/Pu ratio, or whether a narrow-band step would suppress it sufficiently.

Fig. 11.2: Wavelength scan over Np resonance measuring counts for ^{238}U , ^{239}Pu , and ^{237}Np , over 200s measurement time normalised to non-resonant UO. A Gaussian fit is plotted with the centre and FWHM for ^{237}Np .

A CEZ hot particle contains spent fuel radionuclides. The ratios between $^{237}\text{Np}/^{239}\text{Pu}/^{238}\text{U}$ in RBMK spent fuel are on the order of $1/1 \times 10^2/1 \times 10^5$ according to literature data [4]. As ^{238}U is the dominant ($> 98\%$ of the material) nuclide in hot particles, it also provided an opportunity to study the non-resonant ionisation of ^{238}U in a narrow-band excitation. An additional etalon was placed in the laser cavity for the scan of each step.

Shown in Figure 11.2, the centre for the ^{237}Np FES was fit with a Gaussian to be 398.803 ± 0.007 , with a broader AI step of 388.524 ± 0.022 . The ^{238}U shows narrow resonances at 398.819 ± 0.005 nm in the FES scan, and two resonances at 388.473 ± 0.018 nm and 388.54 ± 0.003 nm in the AI scan. There is a broad and inefficient resonance of ^{239}Pu throughout the range of the

Np FES, but this drops off in the AI with wavelengths beyond 388.52 nm.

It is clear from the results in Figure 11.2 that both ^{238}U and ^{239}Pu are not fully suppressed, even at low powers (1 mW for the FES and 13 mW for the AI). The use of the narrowband laser in the second step does improve the suppression, which can be attributed to avoiding the respective U and Pu resonances.

The measured ratio between $^{237}\text{Np}/^{238}\text{U}$ ranges from 1×10^{-3} at the U resonances to 1×10^{-1} at the Np resonance in the AI. A maximal suppression of ^{238}U on the order of 1×10^{-4} is in line with previous investigations on two-step ionisation [2]. An optimal ratio between $^{237}\text{Np}/^{239}\text{Pu}$ can be found at the outer edge of the Np AI resonance, at 388.532 nm. This is however to the disadvantage of $^{237}\text{Np}/^{238}\text{U}$, which is centred at 388.523 nm, a shift of 0.12 nm.

11.4 Pu analysis: High resolution excitation schemes for $^{238}\text{Pu}/^{238}\text{U}$ discrimination

By a further order of magnitude, even more ultra-trace in spent fuel is ^{238}Pu , which derives from ^{237}Np , itself deriving from ^{236}U . ^{236}U is an activation product of ^{235}U , and is sometimes elevated in recycled spent fuel. The isotope ratio $^{238}\text{Pu}/^{239}\text{Pu}$ is therefore a sensitive marker of recycling in the fuel production process.

As evident in the previous section, the complete suppression of ^{238}U is limited to four orders of magnitude in a double blue scheme. Non-resonant excitation is possibly caused by the photodissociation of UO, and so a three-step scheme using only one blue step is preferred. The principal method takes a resonant measurement, followed by a non-resonant measurement in near identical conditions, where the FES laser is offset by 0.1 nm. The resulting non-resonant spectrum serves at the background measurement of non-resonant U, with the difference at mass 238 showing plutonium.

Fig. 11.3: Three-isotope plot comparing the $^{242}\text{Pu}/^{239}\text{Pu}$ and $^{238}\text{Pu}/^{239}\text{Pu}$ in the CEZ particles to modelling [5] results for varying enrichment and literature data for RBMK type reactors [4], with recycled fuel in 2.1 %

The isotope ratios in CEZ particles are shown in Figure 11.3, compared to both literature and model values (see van Eerten [9] for full description), where recycling leads to an increase in $^{238}\text{Pu}/^{239}\text{Pu}$ at the same $^{242}\text{Pu}/^{239}\text{Pu}$ in non-recycled fuel. Just under half of the observed particles clearly align with the expected results for 2.0 % enriched fuel used in the Chernobyl nuclear powerplant in 1986. There is indication that some particles follow the recycled fuel trend. Beyond

low-level recycling, this indicates that the $^{238}\text{Pu}/^{239}\text{Pu}$ ratios are sensitive to further factors. Indeed, one outlying CEZ particle has exceptionally low ^{238}Pu and high ^{242}Pu , not explained by the model or literature data. These results point to the potential for strong local variations in ratios, caused for example by the skin effect, where the outer rim of a fuel pellet experiences drastically different neutronics from the centre [8].

11.5 Conclusions

Retrospective analysis of nuclear material offers valuable insight into its formation and interaction with the environment. The advances in RIMS technique, in its ability to quickly switch between actinides and fission products, expand the accessible isotope ratios for the purposes of nuclear forensics and radioecology. Every element is unique, and calls for targeted analysis. The isotopes in Pu, their trace concentration and value in nuclear forensics, call for special protocols outlined in this work. Not detailed in this work is the advances in RIMS imaging, whereby the interaction between environmental and fissionogenic isotopes can be understood on hot particles.

11.6 Acknowledgements

This Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action (MSCA) Innovative Training Network (ITN) receives funding from the European Union’s H2020 Framework Programme under grant agreement no. 861198. Parts of this work was performed under the auspices of the U.S. Department of Energy by Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory under Contract DE-AC52-07NA27344, and was partially supported by the National Nuclear Security Agency Office of Defense Nuclear Nonproliferation Research and Development. LLNL-JRNL-844531.

Bibliography

- [1] Hauke Bosco et al. New horizons in microparticle forensics: Actinide imaging and detection of ^{238}Pu and ^{242m}Am in hot particles. *Science Advances*, 7, 2021.
- [2] Paul Hanemann et al. Production and characterization of standard particles for rL-SNMS. *Journal of Radioanalytical and Nuclear Chemistry*, 331:5039–5045, 2022.
- [3] Magdalena Kaja, Dominik Studer, Felix Berg, Sebastian Berndt, Christoph E Düllmann, Nina Kneip, Tobias Reich, and Klaus Wendt. Resonant laser ionization of neptunium within an electric field excitation schemes and ionization potential, 2024.
- [4] T. P. Makarova, B. A. Bibichev, and V. D. Domkin. Destructive analysis of the nuclide composition of spent fuel of WWER-440, WWER-1000, and RBMK-1000 reactors. *Radiochemistry*, 50:414–426, 2008.
- [5] David Ohm. Berechnung isotopischer Fingerprints verschiedener Reaktortypen für die nukleare Forensik. 2020.
- [6] Manuel Raiwa. Zerstörungsfreie Analyse von Kernbrennstoffpartikeln aus der Sperrzone Tschernobyls. 2022.

- [7] Manuel Raiwa et al. Actinide imaging in environmental hot particles from Chernobyl by rapid spatially resolved resonant laser secondary neutral mass spectrometry. *Spectrochimica Acta - Part B Atomic Spectroscopy*, 190, 2022.
- [8] Michael R. Savina et al. Simultaneous isotopic analysis of U, Pu, and Am in spent nuclear fuel by resonance ionization mass spectrometry. *Analytical Chemistry*, 93:9505–9512, 2021.
- [9] Darcy van Eerten. Multi-element ultra-trace detection of radionuclides in environmental samples. 2024.
- [10] Darcy van Eerten et al. Multi-element isotopic analysis of hot particles from Chernobyl. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 452, 2023.

Chapter 12

Relativistic multiconfigurational calculations of the atomic structure of the actinides

Joseph S. Andrews^a

^a Helmholtz-Institut Jena, Jena, Germany

The study of the actinides has garnered much intrigue in recent years, driven by an interest in studying the effect of relativity, electron correlation and quantum electrodynamics on their atomic structure. In this report, we conduct large-scale multiconfigurational calculations on the hyperfine constants A and B of the levels $7s^26d\ ^3D_{3/2,5/2}$ in neutral ^{227}Ac . A single reference calculation was conducted using multiconfigurational Dirac-Hartree-Fock (MCDHF) including core effects down to the $n = 4$ shell alongside a sufficiently high layer to ensure convergence with solid agreement with experiment.

12.1 Introduction

The objectives we set out to achieve in these projects were to develop and utilise atomic structure calculations to study the effects of quantum-electrodynamical contributions on the hyperfine structure, isotope shift and low-lying level structure of heavy open-shell atoms such as the actinides.

Interest in the study of the actinides has grown significantly in recent years [2]. By using atomic structure calculations, we can confirm and predict the nuclear structure and properties of exotic nuclei [3], which may be difficult to study experimentally due to problems such as low abundance, limited production, and very short half-lives [15]. Theoretical atomic methods enable us to determine changes in the mean-square nuclear charge radii from isotope shifts in atomic energy levels, revealing 'kinks' at shell closures, and nuclear spins and moments from hyperfine splittings [2, 1]. Comparing theoretical predictions with experimental data allows us to evaluate the accuracy of theoretical models for the heavy elements. Evaluating the nuclear electric quadrupole and magnetic dipole moments against theoretical nuclear predictions, provides insights into nuclear structure and can validate nuclear models, allowing predictions on the 'island of stability' [2].

In this chapter, we utilise multiconfigurational methods to investigate the hyperfine structure of the most stable isotope of neutral actinium, ^{227}Ac , calculating the A and B hyperfine constants. There is much interest in ^{225}Ac due to its medical applications in targeted alpha therapy (TAT) [10], which holds significant promise in being an effective therapy for the treatment of a variety of

cancers. By linking the radionuclide to a targeting vector which seeks out cancers cells, targeted alpha therapy (TAT) allows alpha radiation can be directly delivered to the tumorous cells [12]. Previous calculations of neutral actinium include the hyperfine calculations and energy levels, conducted using the coupled cluster method [?]. Excited energy levels were experimentally verified using a two-step resonant laser-ionization spectroscopy [16] and [13, 7]. Transition rates and energy levels also include calculations utilising multiconfiguration Dirac-Hartree-Fock (MCDHF) and coupled cluster (CC) methods by [4] and [14].

12.2 Theory

The theory which is used to predict the hyperfine structure is MCDHF as implemented in GRASP18 [6]. Here, of the Dirac-Coulomb Hamiltonian is used which may be described as

$$\hat{H}_{DC} = \sum_i^N (c\boldsymbol{\alpha}_i \cdot \mathbf{p}_i + c^2 (\beta_i - I) + V_{\text{nuc}}(r_i)) + \sum_{j>i=1}^N \frac{1}{r_{ij}}. \quad (12.1)$$

Here r_{ij} represents the distance between electrons i and j , N is the total number of electrons in the system, c is the speed of light in a vacuum, $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ are the Dirac matrices, the nuclear potential $V_{\text{nuc}}(r)$ is a nuclear charge potential arising from a two-parameter Fermi distribution [9].

In the standard formulation of MCDHF, the atomic state function Ψ for a given state is represented by a linear combination of symmetry adapted configuration state functions (CSFs).

$$\Psi(\Gamma\pi JM) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{CSFs}}} c_i \psi(\gamma\pi JM) \quad (12.2)$$

Here, J is the total electronic angular momentum, M is its projection and the parity π and Γ being the identifying label, with γ_i containing all the other needed information for the state function. Configuration mixing coefficients c_i are obtained through diagonalizing the appropriate Hamiltonian [9].

The hyperfine structure contribution to the Hamiltonian is represented by a multipole expansion

$$\hat{H}_{hfs} = \sum_{k \geq 1} \mathbf{T}^k \cdot \mathbf{M}^k, \quad (12.3)$$

where \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{M} are spherical tensor operators of rank k in the electronic and nuclear spaces. The $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ terms represent the magnetic dipole (M1) and electric quadrupole (E2) [8].

12.3 Methods

To properly account for electron repulsion, electron correlation is included in MCDHF by systematically adding more configurations to the calculation. In the active space method, electron correlation is addressed by generating CSFs of a specific symmetry J and parity π through substitutions within an active space of orbitals. The electron correlation energy is defined as the difference between Hartree-Fock (HF) calculations and experimental results from the NIST ASD [11].

$$E_{\text{Correlation}} = E_{\text{HF}} - E_{\text{NIST}} \quad (12.4)$$

The active set (AS) is systematically increased to include additional correlation orbitals as a union of layers \mathcal{L} , whereby adding an additional layer increases the current AS as a union of the previous layers such that the active set (AS) $\text{AS} = \mathcal{L}_1 + \mathcal{L}_2 + \mathcal{L}_3 + \dots$. A layer represents a set of orbitals where at maximum one of each orbital angular momentum symmetry ℓ , is included [9]. Electronic correlation is typically divided into two categories, static and dynamic correlation. Static correlation involves electronic correlation arising from nearly degenerate HF energy levels, whereas dynamic correlation arises from the dynamic motion of electrons within a correlated system. Static correlation is typically resolved by including a multireference, whereas dynamic correlation is more challenging and is resolved by involving more correlation orbitals and increasing the AS.

12.4 Discussion

The hyperfine constants A and B are calculated for ^{227}Ac of the two ground state levels of $7s^27d\ ^3D_{3/2,5/2}$ with spin $I = 1.5$, magnetic dipole $\mu = 1.1$ and electric quadrupole moment $Q = 1.74b$.

The hyperfine structure is calculated by dividing up the calculation into four individual stages: (1) The orbital shapes are optimised in DHF mode, whereby no substitutions are allowed. The allowed the spectroscopic orbitals, orbitals which contain electrons, to have the correct number of nodes, which is crucial for calculations accuracy [5]. (2) The second stage of the calculations involves generating and optimising the correlation orbitals, important to account for electron correlation. Correlation orbitals are generated by substituting electrons from the spectroscopic orbitals, the shapes are then optimised, but with less strict criteria such as number of nodes. Only the valence orbitals, which is defined as the outer three electrons were allowed to substitute with singles and doubles (SD) to the correlation orbitals. The optimisation was done using the layer-by-layer method, where the maximum principal quantum number of correlation orbitals was increased by one for each layer. In total 9 layers were included in the calculation up to layer $\mathcal{L}_9 = \{16s, 15p, 15d, 13f\}$. (3) The third stage of the calculation involves using the relativistic configuration interaction (RCI). During this stage, electrons from the core are substituted to the correlation orbitals using singles restricted doubles (SrD) whereby in total two electrons are substituted, but only one may be substituted from the core. Using RCI, the shapes of the spectroscopic and correlation orbitals remain fixed and only the mixing coefficients are changed. The RCI calculation includes effects from the core into the calculation, typically in hyperfine calculations core effects are more important because the nucleus resides at the centre of the atom. In addition, radiative corrections are added perturbatively such as the Breit interaction, self-energy and vacuum polarisation. (4) The final stage of the calculation is to calculate the hyperfine constants A and B using the wavefunction built during the first three stages by involving the hyperfine structure contribution to the Hamiltonian in Equation 12.3.

The results are presented in Table 12.1, the A and B constants for two levels are calculated with different amounts substitutions allowed from the core. The first column uses a shorthand notation, whereby $5spd$ represents substitutions allowed from the $5s, 5p$ and $5d$ subshells. Three different amounts of core substitutions are considered, with each stage increasing the number of core substitutions down to a minimum principal quantum number of $n = 4$.

Fig. 12.1: The calculated average radii in Bohr radii units of the spectroscopic orbitals furthest from the nucleus in neutral actinium. The diagram demonstrates the radial differences between the core and the valence orbitals.

Figure 12.1 shows the average radius from the nucleus in Bohr radii of the spectroscopic orbitals furthest from the nucleus in neutral actinium. Note the clear differences in radius between the valence $6d$, $7s$ and the closed shell orbitals $6s$, $6p$, $5d$. This figure demonstrates that the $6s$ and $6p$ subshells are closer to the valence than the $5s$ and $5p$ and thus would be expected to affect the hyperfine calculation more significantly.

In conclusion, we have investigated the hyperfine structure of neutral actinium and calculated the values for the A and B hyperfine constants of the two levels closest to the ground state with reasonable agreement with experiment. As these calculations were performed in single reference, further work could consider including a multireference, the effect of including g orbitals and single-double-triple substitutions into the calculation. Future work could also investigate the effect of involving several separately optimised non-orthogonal orbital sets.

Table 12.1: The calculated hyperfine constants A and B for ^{227}Ac with a nuclear spin of $I = 1.5$, and nuclear magnetic dipole moment of $\mu = 1.1$ and a nuclear electric quadrupole moment of $Q = 1.74b$. Calculations are made for varying amount of core correlation for the energy levels of $7s^26d\ ^3D_{3/2,5/2}$. The results are compared to experiment in [?].

Opened core subshells	$^3D_{3/2}$		$^3D_{5/2}$	
	A (MHz)	B/Q (MHz/b)	A (MHz)	B/Q (MHz/b)
-	328	503	117	390
$6sp$	125	433	130	400
$5spd\ 6sp$	60	650	240	660
$4spdf\ 5spd\ 6sp$	55	630	276	573
Experiment	70	348	346	429

12.5 Summary

In this work atomic structure calculations were performed on actinium to obtain the hyperfine constants A and B , including quantum-electrodynamical contributions of actinium. Over the course of the LISA initiative, calculations on experimentally significant energy transitions in neutral lawrencium were also successfully computed with good agreement with recent theory and experiment where available. During these projects, we theoretically investigated the actinides and used new theoretical approaches to deal with relativistic open-shell atoms and ions, including the implementation of quantum-electrodynamical contributions. Accurate prediction of the level structure of heavy elements were provided alongside the theoretical treatment of atomic properties, such as hyperfine constants and excitation properties of open-shell elements. The calculations of the energy levels of lawrencium will be shortly submitted to a peer-reviewed journal while the work on actinium has been submitted as part of the LISA deliverable.

12.6 Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 861198–LISA–H2020-MSCA-ITN-2019.

Bibliography

- [1] Jacek Bieroń et al. *Ab Initio* calculations of the hyperfine structure of zinc and evaluation of the nuclear quadrupole moment Q (Zn 67). *Physical Review A*, 97(6):062505, June 2018.
- [2] Michael Block et al. Recent progress in laser spectroscopy of the actinides. *Progress in Particle and Nuclear Physics*, 116:103834, January 2021.
- [3] V. A. Dzuba et al. Atomic properties of superheavy elements No, Lr, and Rf. *Physical Review A*, 90(1):012504, July 2014.
- [4] Ephraim Eliav et al. Transition energies of lanthanum, actinium, and eka-actinium (element 121). *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 109(10):3954–3958, September 1998.
- [5] Charlotte Froese Fischer et al. Advanced multiconfiguration methods for complex atoms: I. Energies and wave functions. *Journal of Physics B: Atomic, Molecular and Optical Physics*, 49(18):182004, September 2016.

- [6] C. Froese Fischer et al. GRASP2018—A Fortran 95 version of the General Relativistic Atomic Structure Package. *Computer Physics Communications*, 237:184–187, April 2019.
- [7] C. Granados et al. In-gas laser ionization and spectroscopy of actinium isotopes near the $N = 126$ closed shell. *Physical Review C*, 96(5):054331, November 2017.
- [8] I. P. Grant, editor. *Relativistic Quantum Theory of Atoms and Molecules*, volume 40 of *Springer Series on Atomic, Optical, and Plasma Physics*. Springer New York, New York, NY, 2007.
- [9] Per Jönsson et al. An Introduction to Relativistic Theory as Implemented in GRASP. *Atoms*, 11(1):7, December 2022.
- [10] Young-Seung Kim and Martin W. Brechbiel. An overview of targeted alpha therapy. *Tumor Biology*, 33(3):573–590, June 2012.
- [11] Alexander Kramida and Yuri Ralchenko. NIST Atomic Spectra Database, NIST Standard Reference Database 78, 1999.
- [12] Bryce J. B. Nelson et al. Targeted Alpha Therapy: Progress in Radionuclide Production, Radiochemistry, and Applications. *Pharmaceutics*, 13(1):49, December 2020.
- [13] S. Raeder et al. Developments towards in-gas-jet laser spectroscopy studies of actinium isotopes at LISOL. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, 376:382–387, June 2016.
- [14] Güldem Ürer and Leyla Özdemir. Energy Levels and Electric Dipole Transitions for Neutral Actinium ($Z = 89$). *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 37(1):239–250, January 2012.
- [15] Jessica Warbinek et al. Advancing Radiation-Detected Resonance Ionization towards Heavier Elements and More Exotic Nuclides. *Atoms*, 10(2):41, April 2022.
- [16] Ke Zhang et al. Detection of the Lowest-Lying Odd-Parity Atomic Levels in Actinium. *Physical Review Letters*, 125(7):073001, August 2020.

Chapter 13

High Precision Calculations of Energies, Lifetimes and Hyperfine Structure of Ac^+ for Laser Resonance Chromatography

Genevieve Geehan, Johan Polet, Marten Luit Reitsma and Anastasia Borschevsky

Van Swinderen Institute for Particle Physics and Gravity, University of Groningen, Groningen, The Netherlands

In this work a summary of the project to calculate energy levels, lifetimes and hyperfine structure of low lying states in Ac^+ is presented. In this summary, key milestones are highlighted along with a brief summary of the true progress of the project with relation to the milestones. Details of computational methods are described. Preliminary results and discussions of these are shared as well as a discussion of the final stages of the project.

13.1 Introduction

This project focused on the high precision calculation of energies, lifetimes and hyperfine structure parameters of six excited states of Ac^+ ; $7s7p$ ($^3P_1^o$), $7p6d$ ($^1P_1^o$), $6d7s$ (3D_1), $6d7s$ (3D_2) and (1D_2), and $6d2$ (3F_2). The first three of these states form an excitation scheme for a novel spectroscopy approach for Ac^+ called Laser Resonance Chromatography (LRC)[4], while the final three states are investigated for the purpose of additional comparison of values for method validation.

The principle of LRC involves measuring the drift time of the ion through an inert gas such as helium. In this scheme, an ion beam is sent through a drift tube filled with an inert gas. A laser scans close to the resonant frequency of an excited state at the start of the drift tube. The electronic configuration of the ion will have an effect on its interaction cross section with the inert gas, which will in turn effect its drift time. A peak in the drift time spectrum will be seen indicating the ground state. When the laser hits the resonant frequency of the excited state, a new peak in the drift time spectrum will appear, indicating the excited state.

The Ac^+ ion has low lying short lived states $7s7p$ ($^3P_1^o$) and $7p6d$ ($^1P_1^o$). Since these states are very short lived, they will be efficiently excited with the laser at the resonant frequency, making them suitable for probing with LRC. The excitation scheme works as follows. The Ac^+ ion is

excited by a laser scanning close to the resonance frequency of either of states $7s7p$ ($^3P_1^o$) or $7p6d$ ($^1P_1^o$). The excited state will immediately decay to the metastable $6d7s$ (3D_1) state. This long lived state will be detected as a peak in the LRC drift time spectra when the resonant frequency of the short lived state is met by the scanning laser.

In order to make the LRC scheme possible, high precision calculations were needed for the energy, lifetime and hyperfine structure parameters of the states involved in the scheme. This project involved calculation of these parameters using the configuration interaction method combined with many body perturbation theory (CI+MBPT) implemented in the AMBiT program[3]. Energies and hyperfine structure parameters have also been calculated using an alternative computational method called Fock Space Coupled Cluster (FSCC)[1] implemented in the DIRAC program[6]. Since the methods are very different, a comparison of calculations between them is a good validation process.

In this report I will outline the expected milestones and compare with these the true progress of the project and any difficulties encountered that veered from the expected milestones and time frame (section 14.2). I will describe the computational methods used, present the results and discuss the next steps of the project in section 13.3 and section 13.4. Although the project is not completed, it is very close to completion. Results given here are preliminary.

13.2 Milestones

In this section I will outline the milestones of the project and then document the project progress in relation to these milestones.

1. Preliminary calculations:

The first milestone is to make very simple calculations with a small basis using only CI (not MBPT) and leaving out any QED effects. From these calculations, the levels of interest can be identified by energy, configuration and quantum number J.

Progress: This milestone was met with no issues.

2. Fine tuning and converging:

Once the energy levels are identified and preliminary energy calculations are within reasonable uncertainty from experimental values, the calculation should to be improved to sufficient precision. Firstly the basis set for CI will be increased until the calculation converges, then MBPT will be added and the basis of MBPT increased until convergence. Then QED effects (Breit, Uheling, self-energy) will then be calculated to see if they are necessary for the calculation.

Progress: This milestone was completed with no issues. It was found that of the QED effects only breit and self-energy resulted in non-negligible changes, so these were included in the calculation while Uheling was not.

3. Comparison of Energy and Hyperfine Structure Parameters with alternative computational method:

The calculated values of energy and hyperfine structure (HFS) parameters are compared with those calculated by the Fock-Space Coupled Cluster (FSCC) method. Since CI+MBPT and FSCC are very different methods, agreement of these values indicates an accurate calculation.

Progress: Energy values showed very good agreement (also good agreement with experiment). As for the HFS parameters, A_0 was in good agreement but q had significant disagreement. The q values differed by about a factor of two for most states. The cause of this discrepancy has been found. However, as is discussed in section 13.4, calculations still need to be finalised. This issue has caused the project to be extended by 5 months longer than expected.

4. Calculation of spontaneous decay rates:

The final step of the project is to calculate the spontaneous decay rates (and radiative lifetimes) of the states of interest.

Progress: Spontaneous decay rates have been calculated. Comparisons to literature values suggest high accuracy of the calculation even without the final corrections being added. However, the values will be updated when final corrections are integrated to ensure consistency.

13.3 Energy and lifetime

13.3.1 Calculation details

Our starting point is with an approximation of the core orbitals using the Dirac-Fock method. This calculation formed the self consistent potential of the Dirac-Fock method from the electron occupying orbitals up to 6p (all but the two electrons of highest energy). Breit and self-energy effects were included in the calculation by modifying the calculation as described by [3].

Valence interactions are included in the calculation with CI. Our initial single electron orbitals for the valence electrons and virtual states in shells 7s, 6d and 7p were constructed from the wavefunction solutions of the Dirac-Fock procedure. The single electron wavefunctions of the remaining shells up to s, p, d and f shells of principle quantum number $n=22$ were constructed from B-splines. Single and double electron excitations in s- and p- orbitals with orbitals $7 \leq n \leq 22$, d-orbitals with $6 \leq n \leq 22$ and f-orbitals with $5 \leq n \leq 22$ were included, while single hole excitations in 6s and 6p orbitals were included. Inclusions in the CI calculation greater than these (increasing basis size or excitations) resulted in a change in energy smaller than $< 0.01\%$ meaning that the CI calculation converged at this point.

One, two and three body diagrams of core-valence interactions and core excitations were incorporated with MBPT. The excitations were included in virtual orbitals up to $7 \leq n \leq 30$ for the s- and p- orbitals, $6 \leq n \leq 30$ for the d-orbitals and $5 \leq n \leq 30$ for f- and g-orbitals.

Spontaneous decay rates, Γ , were calculated by the following relation, These rates are derived from the matrix elements,

$$\Gamma_K = \frac{\kappa(2K + 2)[K](\frac{\omega}{c})^{2K+1} \langle ||\mathcal{M}|| \rangle^2}{K([K]!!)^2 [J_i]}, \quad (13.1)$$

where K is the multipolarity of transition, $\kappa = 1$ for electric and $\kappa = 1/4c^2$ for magnetic multipole transitions, ω is the energy of the transition and \mathcal{M}_K is the hyperfine electric or magnetic operator of multipolarity K . The reduced matrix element $\langle ||\mathcal{M}|| \rangle$ and energy ω used, was that given by the CI+MBPT calculation. Radiative lifetimes are the inverse of the sum of rates of spontaneous emission.

13.3.2 Results and discussion

The results in this section are given by the methods outlined in subsection 13.3.1. The corrections described in section 13.4 are not included in these calculations.

In Table 13.1, a comparison of our current theoretical values compared with existing experimental values for the six states of interested are presented. It can be seen here that the values are all in good agreement, meaning the methods used were highly accurate.

Table 13.1: Energy values of the excited states are compared between FSCC and CI+MBPT methods and experimental values.

State	Energy cm^{-1}		
	FSCC	CI+MBPT	Expt.[2]
$7s^16d^1$ 3D_1	5673	4907	4740
3D_2	6201	5429	5267
1D_2	10156	9140	9088
$6d^2$ 3F_2	14906	13547	13236
$7s^17p^1$ $^3P_1^o$	22711	22531	22181
$7p^16d^1$ $^1P_1^o$	30683	29663	29250

The current values calculated of radiative lifetimes τ are displayed in Table 13.2. These calculations show that the two odd states $7s^17p^1$ $^3P_1^o$ and $7p^16d^1$ $^1P_1^o$ are indeed very short lived and the $7s^16d^1$ 3D_1 is metastable. These states provide an excellent excitation scheme for the proposed LRC experiment. Either of the odd states $7s^17p^1$ $^3P_1^o$ and $7p^16d^1$ $^1P_1^o$ would be suitable to probe as they will have a high rate of excitation. They will immediately decay to the long lived $7s^16d^1$ 3D_1 state which will be stable enough to detect as a peak in the drift time spectrum.

Table 13.2: Values of radiative lifetimes, τ , for the excited states of interest. These values are calculated using the CI+MBPT method.

State	τ (s)	Dominant Channel
$7s^16d^1$ 3D_1	5.194×10^5	M1
3D_2	179.8	M1 & E2
1D_2	1.900	M1 & E2
$6d^2$ 3F_2	2.032	M1 & E2
$7s^17p^1$ $^3P_1^o$	2.284×10^{-8}	E1
$7p^16d^1$ $^1P_1^o$	4.844×10^{-9}	E1

Spontaneous decay rates are displayed in Table 13.3 and compared with those from [5]. These rates were calculated with energies and reduced matrix elements from the CI+MBPT calculation. Good agreement is found between these values except for the transition $7s2$ (1S_0) \rightarrow $6d7s$ (3D_1) which differs by a few orders of magnitude. However, for practical purposes in relation to the LRC experiment, this difference is not significant. With either possible decay rate, the state is metastable and will be measured within its radiative lifetime.

13.4 Hyperfine structure parameters

As mentioned in Milestone 3 in section 14.2. There were difficulties in calculating the hyperfine structure (HFS) parameters. The electric field gradient, q , calculated with the method outlined

Table 13.3: A comparison of the energies and spontaneous decay rates, Γ , calculated by the CI+MBPT method with theoretical values from [5].

Transition	Type	Transition energy (cm^{-1})		Γ (s^{-1})	
		This work	Lit.[5]	This work	Lit.[5]
6d7s ($^3\text{D}_1$) \rightarrow 7s2 ($^1\text{S}_0$)	M1	4906.661081	4739.631	1.93×10^{-6}	1.10×10^{-14}
6d7s ($^3\text{D}_2$) \rightarrow 7s2 ($^1\text{S}_0$)	E2	5428.505193	5267.147	2.52×10^{-3}	3.20×10^{-3}
6d7s ($^3\text{D}_2$) \rightarrow 6d7s ($^3\text{D}_1$)	M1	688.905193	527.516	3.04×10^{-3}	3.11×10^{-3}
6d7s ($^1\text{D}_2$) \rightarrow 7s2 ($^1\text{S}_0$)	E2	9140.031783	9087.517	2.68×10^{-1}	3.20×10^{-1}
6d7s ($^1\text{D}_2$) \rightarrow 6d7s ($^3\text{D}_1$)	M1	4400.431783	4347.886	6.54×10^{-1}	2.55×10^{-1}
6d7s ($^1\text{D}_2$) \rightarrow 6d7s ($^3\text{D}_2$)	M1+E2	3873.031783	3820.37	2.46×10^{-2}	2.91×10^{-2}
6d2 ($^3\text{F}_2$) \rightarrow 7s2 ($^1\text{S}_0$)	E2	13546.87176	13236.418	4.92×10^{-1}	1.00×10^{-1}
6d2 ($^3\text{F}_2$) \rightarrow 6d7s ($^3\text{D}_1$)	M1+E2	8807.271763	8496.787	2.50×10^{-1}	2.50×10^{-1}
6d2 ($^3\text{F}_2$) \rightarrow 6d7s ($^3\text{D}_2$)	E2	8279.871763	7969.271	9.99×10^{-2}	1.20×10^{-1}
6d2 ($^3\text{F}_2$) \rightarrow 6d7s ($^1\text{D}_2$)	M1	4459.371763	4148.901	3.80×10^{-2}	2.90×10^{-2}
7s7p ($^3\text{P}_1^o$) \rightarrow 7s2 ($^1\text{S}_0$)	E1	22531.12533	22180.533	1.97×10^7	2.13×10^7
7s7p ($^3\text{P}_1^o$) \rightarrow 6d7s ($^3\text{D}_1$)	E1	17624.46425	17440.902	9.14×10^6	1.04×10^7
7s7p ($^3\text{P}_1^o$) \rightarrow 6d7s ($^3\text{D}_2$)	E1	17264.12533	16913.386	1.47×10^7	1.58×10^7
6d7p ($^1\text{P}_1^o$) \rightarrow 7s2 ($^1\text{S}_0$)	E1	29662.52118	29250.366	1.11×10^8	1.11×10^8
6d7p ($^1\text{P}_1^o$) \rightarrow 6d7s ($^3\text{D}_1$)	E1	24922.92118	24510.735	1.44×10^7	1.09×10^7
6d7p ($^1\text{P}_1^o$) \rightarrow 6d7s ($^3\text{D}_2$)	E1	24395.52118	23983.219	6.10×10^7	7.00×10^7
6d7p ($^1\text{P}_1^o$) \rightarrow 6d7s ($^1\text{D}_2$)	E1	20575.02118	20162.849	1.51×10^7	1.20×10^7
6d7p ($^1\text{P}_1^o$) \rightarrow 6d2 ($^3\text{F}_2$)	E1	16426.52118	16013.948	1.14×10^7	1.86×10^7

in subsection 13.3.1 showed a large discrepancy when comparing the values to those calculated by the FSCC method, as can be seen in Table 13.4.

Table 13.4: Values of HFS constants (A_o & q) of the excited states are compared between FSCC and CI+MBPT methods. Three values are shown for the CI+MBPT calculations. The first "Initial" is calculated using the methods described in subsection 13.3.1. RPA values are those with frequency-dependent "RPA" included in the matrix element calculation and "CI in Core" are calculated with the CI basis set was extended to the core states, as discussed in section 13.4.

State	A_o (MHz)				q (MHz/b)			
	CI+MBPT			FSCC	CI+MBPT			FSCC
	Initial	RPA	CI in Core		Initial	RPA	CI in Core	
7s ¹ 6d ¹ $^3\text{D}_1$	-5116	-4858	-4418	-5282	140	184	205	225
$^3\text{D}_2$	4654	4164	4263	4983	227	325	271	368
$^1\text{D}_2$	-2288	-2268	-1473	-2455	222	497	137	400
6d ² $^3\text{F}_2$	719	772	441	782	89	90	169	169
7s ¹ 7p ¹ $^3\text{P}_1^o$	11953	11100	10481	12791	-514	-525	-458	587
7p ¹ 6d ¹ $^1\text{P}_1^o$	-2314	-2933	-2720	-2809	207	421	366	359

The calculation was modified to include the contributions of the core states by two approaches. The first approach was to include frequency-dependent random phase approximation (RPA) in the calculation of the matrix elements. This was included in the same method described in subsection 13.3.1 with no further changes. The second approach was to extend the CI basis to include the core states. Since this would greatly increase the computational cost, the CI basis upper limit was decreased from $n = 22$ to $n = 8$ for s-, p-, d- and f- shells. Aside from this change to the CI basis, every other aspect of this calculation was the same as that described in subsection 13.3.1.

The HFS parameters resulting from these changes are displayed in Table 13.4. It can be seen

that for some states the inclusion of frequency-dependent RPA brings the HFS parameters in agreement with the FSCC values and for some states the inclusion of the core states in the CI bases does. The next step of this calculation will be to combine the RPA corrections and the inclusion of core states in the CI basis.

13.5 Conclusion

In this report I have given a summary of the progress of the project to calculate energies, lifetimes and hyperfine structure of Ac^+ . Highly precise and accurate calculations have been made for values of energies and lifetimes of the six states of interest. However, final calculations are still being made to include the core states in the CI calculation and to include the frequency-dependent RPA in the calculations of the matrix elements. When these calculations are finished, energy and lifetime calculations will be updated and accurate HFS parameter values will be given.

Bibliography

- [1] L. Visscher et al., "Formulation and implementation of the relativistic Fock-space coupled cluster method for molecules" *The Journal of Chemical Physics* 115 (2001): pp. 9720-9726.
- [2] J.E. Sansonetti et al., "Handbook of Basic Atomic Spectroscopic Data (version 1.1.3)" National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg, MD. (2005), [Online] Available: <http://physics.nist.gov/Handbook> [2023, Nov 23].
- [3] E. V. Kahl and J. C. Berengut, "AMBiT: A program for high-precision relativistic atomic structure calculations" *Computer Physics Communications* 238 (2019): pp. 232-243.
- [4] M. Laatiaoui et al., "Laser Resonance Chromatography of Superheavy Elements" *Physical Review Letters* 125 (2020): 023002.
- [5] A. Kramida, "Update of Atomic Data for the First Three Spectra of Actinium" *Atoms* 10 (2022): 2218-2004.
- [6] DIRAC, a relativistic ab initio electronic structure program, Release DIRAC24 (2024), written by L. Visscher et al. (available at <https://doi.org/110.5281/zenodo.10680560>, see also <https://www.diracprogram.org>)

Chapter 14

C-WAVE laser development as a turn-key solid-state alternative to CW dye laser.

Mitzi Urquiza-González^{a,b}, Dag Hanstorp^b and Korbinian Hens^a

^a Division HÜBNER Photonics, Hübner GmbH & Co KG, Kassel, Germany

^b Department of Physics, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden

Studies of the atomic spectrum through resonant laser excitation provide access to the nuclear structures. Precise measurements of the interactions of the nuclear ground state with the electronic shell permit the extraction of nuclear properties that are closely related to the nucleus' configuration and shape. With atomic transitions of the valence electrons in the range of a few eV, these are accessible with lasers. However, this method is limited by the low production yields of the isotope of interest, scarce knowledge of the atomic structure, and the capacity to produce the relevant wavelength. For high-resolution laser spectroscopy, the optical linewidth must be low enough to resolve the atomic lines up to the hyperfine structure (HFS). Still, it should not be much narrower than the resolution-limiting effect of the specific experimental setup to maximize the efficiency. Depending on the spectroscopy technique, resonance peak linewidths can be as low as 40-70 MHz, sufficient to resolve the HFS in most elements. In the context of the LISA-ITN project, this work presents an optical parametric oscillator (OPO) seeded PDA system that has a comparable performance in the range near 330 nm with an optical linewidth in the order of 100 MHz.

14.1 Introduction

Studies of atomic spectra through resonant laser excitation and ionization provide information on nuclear structure. Interactions of the nuclear ground state properties with the electronic shell induce small perturbations in the atomic level structure, known as the hyperfine structure (HFS) and the isotope shift (IS). Precise measurements of these effects allow the extraction of the nuclear spin I , the magnetic dipole moment μ_I , the electric quadrupole moment Q_s and changes in mean square charge radii δr^2 , all of which are closely related to the nucleus' configuration and its shape [1].

As the atomic transitions of the valence electrons are in the range of a few eV, these are accessible with lasers. A very successful laser spectroscopy technique to study exotic isotopes is

collinear resonance ionization spectroscopy (CRIS) [2]. It is based on efficient resonant excitation of individual hyperfine components using a narrow-band pulsed laser and subsequent selective resonant laser ionization of the isotope of interest while minimizing the Doppler and pressure broadening by collinearly overlapping a fast atom beam with the laser beam. This technique is mainly performed with pulsed lasers since they can provide sufficiently high power densities as needed for efficient ionization and in addition also for single-pass nonlinear frequency conversion [3].

The required optical linewidth needed for high-resolution laser spectroscopy needs to be low enough to resolve the atomic lines up to the HFS. Still, it should not be much narrower than the resolution-limiting effect of the specific experimental setup to maximize the efficiency [4]. In a fast beam collinear geometry, the resonance peak linewidth is in the order of 40-70 MHz, [3] which is sufficient to resolve the HFS in most elements. The generation of pulsed laser light with an optical linewidth, measured as the full width at half maximum (FWHM), of less than 50 MHz has been reported [5] by pulsed dye amplification (PDA) of a cw dye laser beam, and in the order of 20 MHz [6] by injection-locking of a titanium:sapphire laser (Ti:Sa) with a narrow-linewidth cw Ti:Sa. With both methods, the final emitted pulse is limited by the width of the Fourier transform of the laser pulse, at the cost of rather challenging experimental setups including maintaining power stability and a narrow optical linewidth [11, 12, 10].

Although dye lasers still serve as a popular and frequently used system in the field of laser spectroscopy [7, 8, 2, 9], the degeneration or aging of most dyes and the use of solvents, which are both flammable or toxic, are prominent disadvantages [10] that discourage their use. Depending on the dye, and to a lesser degree the solvent, the fundamentally achievable wavelength covers a range of 370 to 900 nm, considering pump options at 532 nm and 355 nm and using about 30 different dyes [10]. On the other hand, there are solid-state laser systems at hand today, which are a more convenient alternative to dye lasers in terms of handling. However, often the tuning range of such systems is limited to only a few to tens of nanometers. Exclusively solid-state systems based on Ti:Sa crystals can provide an exceptionally wide tuning range from 680 to 1000 nm, which makes Ti:Sa lasers the most commonly used systems for numerous applications in laser spectroscopy.

In the scopes of the LISA-ITN, this project's main objective is the use of high-reliability industrial solid-state lasers for scientific purposes, in the form of adapting HÜBNER Photonics's turn-key 'C-WAVE' OPO system (model: C-WAVE GTR) [13] to the needs of the community in terms of wavelength and optical linewidth. This was done using a PDA from a tunable cw single-mode OPO. The resulting laser system was characterized and validated with a real-world test performing high-resolution laser spectroscopy on stable silver using the CRIS experiment, situated at the CERN-ISOLDE facility.

As a benchmark evaluation for the suitability of this system, pulsed light at 328 nm was produced by three different lasers to have their performance compared: the new OPO-based PDA setup (1) and a cw single-frequency ring dye laser amplified by a PDA (2), both with subsequent single-pass frequency doubling, as well as an injection-locked Ti:Sa laser seeded by a cw single-frequency ring Ti:Sa laser, which is sum-frequency mixed with a pulsed 532 nm single longitudinal mode Nd:YVO₄ laser to reach the UV spectral range [3].

14.2 Milestones

As background work to adapt the ‘C-WAVE’ OPO system, an evaluation of linewidth customization concepts was done and submitted as the first milestone report of this project. It presents a brief overview of the optical linewidth of the C-WAVE OPO, to be used for high-resolution laser spectroscopy. Linewidth customization concepts for this system were explored to achieve the desirable characteristics for laser spectroscopy on actinides. To narrow down the most feasible option, an assessment of each concept’s strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) was explored, emphasizing the simplest and most versatile design for future testing and implementation. Four concepts were explored, including the implementation of an EOM, changing the resonant cavity mirrors characteristics, and the redesign of the optical platform. Priority was given to the concepts that signified less complexity in their design, time of fabrication, and optical alignment. Under these criteria, the best option was determined to be the implementation of an additional EOM for phase modulation outside the resonant cavity. While this concept is suitable for a scientific setup, it would require further legal investigation for commercialization due to a possible patent infringement [14].

As part of the second milestone and the system’s characterization, the suitability of the C-WAVE OPO for on-line experiments was validated by performing high-resolution spectroscopy of radioactive silver isotopes at the CRIS experiment. As discussed previously, the aim of this experiment was the study of the atomic spectrum via resonant laser excitation, which provides access to underlying effects caused by the nuclear structure, that is of special interest in short-lived radioisotopes produced at Isotope Separator On-Line (ISOL) facilities. Current implementations of resonant laser ionization techniques often limit the extraction of the nuclear observables due to the low spectral resolution of the pulsed laser systems deployed. Several high-resolution spectroscopy techniques demand spectral widths in the order of hundreds of MHz and below. A proven solution to reduce this linewidth is the pulsed amplification of a narrow-band cw laser. This report presents the demonstration of a pulsed dye amplifier seeded by an OPO system and its performance. Spectral bandwidths of the systems were measured using a high finesse Fabry-Pérot Interferometer (FPI), resulting in an optical linewidth between 140 to 156 MHz at a wavelength of 328 nm. Suitability for on-line experiments was validated by performing high-resolution spectroscopy of radioactive silver isotopes at the CRIS experiment. The results of this validation were published in the conference proceedings volume 12399 SPIE LASE [15], where the HFS of ^{109}Ag was resolved using three different laser systems, as well as the measurements of their optical linewidth, presented in Table 14.1

Table 14.1: Optical linewidth calculated from the FPI patterns.

Setup	Optical linewidth (MHz)	Relative error
OPO PDA	156(17)	11%
Dye PDA	140(17)	12%
SFG	141(14)	10%

14.3 Outlook

As more exotic nuclides are accessible, new laser techniques are needed to produce adequate wavelengths, such as for fermium and nobelium, which have some transition lines from the ground-state between 333 nm [7] to 355 nm [16]. Knowing the comparable performance to that of the Ti:Sa and dye lasers in this range, a new setup is proposed for further studies with an OPO-seeded amplifier system.

To produce high-energy pulses in the range of 1000 nm to 1530 nm to be subsequently frequency doubled or tripled, to obtain the desired experimental range, the use of a narrow-band cw-OPO seeded optical parametric amplifier (OPA) is presented in Figure 14.1. A preliminary characterization is needed to match the pulse length and optical linewidth to the specific experimental requirements, as well as to verify that the OPO-driven mode-hop-free tuning is in a suitable range for the target application.

Fig. 14.1: Schematic diagram of the suggested laser system. The OPO system utilizes a two-stage configuration, with the potential for cascaded SHG of the primary OPO output. The cw-OPO signal is subsequently fiber coupled to seed the OPA, which is pumped by a 780 nm high-power pulsed laser source, resulting in pulsed amplification. The final power output must be significant enough to undergo frequency doubling or tripling, to achieve the desired experimental wavelengths.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 861198 (LISA).

Bibliography

- [1] Campbell, P., Moore, I., and Pearson, M., “Laser spectroscopy for nuclear structure physics,” *Progress in Particle and Nuclear Physics* 86, 127–180 (2016).
- [2] Cocolios, T. E. et al., “High-resolution laser spectroscopy with the Collinear Resonance Ionisation Spectroscopy (CRIS) experiment at CERN-ISOLDE,” *Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res., B* 376, 284–287 (2016).

- [3] de Groote, R. P. et al., “Use of a Continuous Wave Laser and Pockels Cell for Sensitive High-Resolution Collinear Resonance Ionization Spectroscopy,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 115, 132501 (Sep 2015).
- [4] Fedosseev, V. et al., “Ion beam production and study of radioactive isotopes with the laser ion source at ISOLDE,” *J. Phys. G* 44(8), 084006 (2017).
- [5] Mishin, V. et al., “Ultrasensitive resonance laser photoionization spectroscopy of the radioisotope chain 157-172Tm produced by a proton accelerator.,” *Soviet Physics, Journal of Experimental and Theoretical Physics* 66, 235–242 (1987).
- [6] Reponen, M. et al., “Laser developments and resonance ionization spectroscopy at IGISOL,” *European Physical Journal A* 48, 1–15 (2012).
- [7] Laatiaoui, M. et al., “Atom-at-a-time laser resonance ionization spectroscopy of nobelium,” *Nature* 538(7626), 495–498 (2016).
- [8] Ferrer, R. et al., “In-gas-cell laser ionization spectroscopy in the vicinity of 100Sn: Magnetic moments and mean-square charge radii of N=50–54 Ag,” *Physics Letters B* 728, 191–197 (2014).
- [9] Marsh, B. et al., and Zemlyanoy, S., “New developments of the in-source spectroscopy method at RILIS/ISOLDE,” *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms* 317, 550–556 (2013).
- [10] Raeder, S. et al., Performance of Dye and Ti:sapphire laser systems for laser ionization and spectroscopy studies at S3,” *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B-beam Interactions With Materials and Atoms* 463, 86–95 (2020).
- [11] Reponen, M. et al., “Evidence of a sudden increase in the nuclear size of proton-rich silver-96,” *Nature Communications* 12, 1–8 (December 2021).
- [12] Verlinde, M. et al., “Single-longitudinal-mode pumped pulsed-dye amplifier for high-resolution laser spectroscopy,” *Review of Scientific Instruments* 91(10), 103002 (2020).
- [13] Sperling, J. et al., “Breakthrough instruments and products: Laser light tunable across the visible up to mid-infrared: Novel turnkey cw OPO with efficiency-optimized design,” *Review of Scientific Instruments* 92 (12 2021).
- [14] Williamson III, R. S., (2005) "Laser Coherence Control Using Homogeneous Linewidth Broadening", US 2005/0047454 A1.
- [15] M. Urquiza-González et al., “Benchmark evaluation for a single frequency continuous wave OPO seeded pulsed dye amplifier for high-resolution laser spectroscopy,” in *Solid State Lasers XXXII: Technology and Devices*, vol. 12399 W. A. Clarkson and R. K. Shori, eds., International Society for Optics and Photonics (SPIE, 2023), p. 123990.
- [16] S. Allehabi et al., “Theoretical study of electronic structure of erbium and fermium,” *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transf.* 253, 107137 (2020).

Closing remarks

As we now come to the end of the LISA era, we think back on the last few years, filled with challenges and hopes, highs and lows, joy and strife. But first and foremost, a network like LISA is one made of people.

Our Early Stage Researchers come naturally first to mind. They form the core of LISA and they are the reason of being for LISA. It all started with a large-scale recruitment journey: how can we attract top young researchers to fill 15 diverse positions? We sent our call to the wind (and through 1001 mailing lists, LinkedIn, and all sorts of websites), and 160 excited persons answered that call. A thorough and challenging screening followed, from counting days to match eligibility criteria, to studying background and motivation. Half of those candidates were then invited to answer a second round: the famed SONRU videos, where they each got 5 minutes to impress us with clever answers to technical and motivational questions. While powerful, this tool is as awkward for the candidates as it is for the recruiters! (80 candidates x 5 minutes + loading time and quick feedback = forever!) In spite of this all, we quickly spotted the clever people we wanted to shape LISA.

And this is when it all went strange. It was early March 2020, we had heard about this virus coming from far away. We had stopped shaking hands and were playing footsies instead. The other critical group of LISA got together at CERN: the supervisors. We were full of hope and ideas, sharing our impressions and wishes, sometimes having to argue with one another as to where each ESR would be best placed. But most importantly, it was the last time any of us would see each other - or any colleague for that matter - for a long time. COVID had invited itself to Europe and it was online that our first contacts were made. Little by little, COVID and ESR starting waves intertwined one another, as the new recruits joined the network. The process got a bit more challenging for some, with embassy closures preventing visa applications being processed, or travel bans challenging the mobility at the core of a Marie Skłodowska Curie Action.

But once the train leaves the station, nothing can stop it! We had started LISA, our ESRs were coming in, the training was to start. We had thought of great plans: sheep herding as a form of team building, coached by the European champion of sheep herding, for example, or exploding pig eyes as a form of laser safety training. However, one after the other, our trainings had to take a different turn. An online turn. Rather than complain about it, the ESRs embraced the situation and our online gatherings became regular get-togethers that would break the monotony of isolation, whether it was raining in Hannover or middle of the night in Mexico City. We replaced the social activity at the Strasbourg Christmas market by a gift exchange to celebrate Sinterklaas. Some might say that these were poor replacements, but seeing true bounds form between the ESRs was way more satisfying than gluewein underneath a giant Christmas tree. The magic was there; it had taken hold.

While COVID rippled through the whole project, pushing events around, substantially delaying secondments, we eventually caught up to our plans, culminating with a few key events. The double summer school held in Cabourg and Bagnolles-de-l'Orne was a unique experience where all got together and shared as well on scientific level, as on a human level. We remember a crazy karaoke night where the organisers had to take away the mic from the Training Officer, because it was time, or “the cow”, both a rally point and a mark telling us where our noise would be tolerable. And then there was climbing. First in Caen, where a large delegation drove away to the sunset, literally, to spend an evening of indoor wall climbing. And then, the second week, someone just looked around and said “Wouldn't it be nice to climb that wall?” And it was directly challenge accepted! The following afternoon, the LISA crowd was scaling the cliff behind the spa of Bagnolles-de-l'Orne, under the watching eyes of surprised visitors in their bathrobe. More need not be said, our ESRs were simply climbing to the top. And then the LISA Conference in Leuven, under the constant gaze of a full size Jesus, listening to the story of time to a broad audience. But as if a pandemic was not enough, war came in the way of LISA. One of our key societal impacts is about environment monitoring and threat prevention. In that context, we had planned a large LISA-4-Society Action, where our ESRs were meant to showcase their skills and knowledge during a field trip to Chernobyl. And just as the planning was done and all was in place, the Russian incursion in Ukraine threw it all down the drain. Even worse, Chernobyl and Zaporizhzhia, two nuclear sites, became fighting grounds of this conflict. That inspired our ESRs to communicate to the world about what people should be concerned about on a dedicated Instagram page. Eventually, LISA brought its attention to Fukushima, where we organised a workshop with a public lecture.

At that point, we thought we had seen it all. Pandemic and war, what else could we face? None of us had seen the worst coming: the loss of our Network Coordinator, Bruce Marsh. The news resonated through LISA like an earthquake coupled to a nuclear detonation. We could not believe it. Once again, we witnessed how LISA was built: with people, coming together, supporting one another, and having become more than just colleagues: a family. It is in the hardest moments that we see how close we all are. And this was, without any doubt, the hardest moment for all of us.

And now the journey is wrapping up. This book is a testament to the achievements of all of our ESRs. Some have already defended their PhD thesis and can proudly call themselves Dr. Some are anxiously waiting for their defence and others have some time to go. However, all of them have a bright future ahead of them, one in which we will accompany them and look forward to collaborating with them. The world is your oyster, now is your time to shine like a pearl!

Thomas Elias Cocolios

The Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network LISA (Laser Ionization and Spectroscopy of Actinides), funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program, aimed to train the next generation of atomic, nuclear and laser scientists by conducting research to increase our understanding of the atomic and nuclear properties of the chemical elements known as the actinides. Of long-standing interest to the fields of fundamental atomic and nuclear physics, this effort is an essential prerequisite for unravelling the structure of the superheavy elements at the end of Mendeleev's table. This knowledge is required for the effective production, identification and handling of these elements, and is thus a necessary foundation for our goals of understanding and exploiting the potential for practical applications of the actinides in the fields of medical physics, nuclear applications and environmental monitoring. Our consortium of world-leading experts in radioactive ion beam research and applications, laser spectroscopy, scientific laser technologies (industrial partners) and nuclear and atomic theorists recruited and trained 15 Early Stage Researchers. LISA formed a cohesive and symbiotic collaboration for training young scientists in the pursuit of the following research objectives: Development of laser-based actinide ion beam production and purification techniques; development of laser technologies; measurement of ionization potentials and electron affinities; extraction of atomic and nuclear properties from laser spectroscopy studies; enhancement of the prospects for direct use of the actinide isotopes themselves (theranostic applications), or the application of techniques for their detection (environmental monitoring). LISA was structured into 7 work packages (WP), separated according to specific types of technical or research challenges, training, communication and management, but highly interlinked to ensure a close interaction between the ESR fellows. This structure was designed to expose all trainees to the breath of activity types across the network and also to foster working relationships that will endure long after the project ends.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program (Grant No. 861198 project LISA MSCA ITN)